

Deliverable 3.1

Implementation Framework & Baseline Description

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Project Consortium

Coordinator:

Executive summary

The NexusLabs project focuses on the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystems (WEFE) Nexus. Its goal is to develop a solid understanding of how these resources are connected. The project is being implemented in nine key pilot locations across the Mediterranean and Europe to help stakeholders implement Nature-Based Solutions (NbSs) and adopt scalable innovations to increase the resilience of agricultural systems.

This document provides an overview of the pilot sites and details the characteristics of each area. These include information on water sources and usage, agriculture, energy, ecosystems, climate, demographics, and land use.

Each pilot site is described in terms of its challenges, innovation demands, technical and organizational infrastructure, and knowledge capacities. Detailed information on the NbSs currently implemented, along with those planned within the project framework, is provided here, serving as a central reference point for further discussion and analysis in subsequent project tasks and work packages.

In line with NexusLabs's commitment to addressing the fundamental needs of these territories, stakeholder requirements play a central role in building this knowledge base through all participatory activities conducted in each pilot.

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Acronyms

- CLC: Corine Land Cover
- EbA: Ecosystem-based Adaptation
- EO: Earth Observation
- LL: Living Lab
- MET Biodistrict: Biodistretto Maremma Etrusca e Monti della Tolfa
- NbSs: Nature-Based Solutions
- PDO: Protected Designation of Origin
- PGI: Protected Geographical Indication
- PNIEC: National Plan for Energy and Climate
- SIC: Site of Community Importance
- SMEs: Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
- SPA: Special Protection Area
- UAA: Utilized Agricultural Area
- WEFE: Water, Energy, Food, Ecosystem
- WFD: Water Framework Directive
- WPs: Work Packages
- WUA: Water User Association
- WWTP: Wastewater Treatment Plant

1. Introduction

1.1 Objectives

The NexusLabs deliverable 3.1 “Implementation Framework & Baseline Description” aims to provide a standardized, structured, participatory framework for developing a multi-dimensional knowledge base of the current situation in the Living Labs (baseline). This will serve as the benchmark for impact assessment of the NexusLabs solutions, including NbSs, smart-farming, and resource-efficiency tools developed throughout the project (implementation framework) across all project Partners. This integration ensures cross-WP consistency, helps address complex environmental challenges throughout the project and strengthens strategies by supporting evidence-based decision-making at both local and regional scales.

The specific objective of this baseline report is to provide a comprehensive overview of the NexusLabs living labs and to serve as a foundational reference for the implementation of NexusLabs strategies. It supports the alignment of activities across the different project Work Packages (WPs). The document is structured into two main parts: a general overview of each study area and a detailed description of NexusLabs solutions and demonstration sites.

1.2 Relevance to the overall study

The nine Living Labs selected for the NexusLabs project represent a diverse range of Multi-Actor Innovation Communities from Europe and the Mediterranean. Each LL reflects distinct geographical, climatic, economic and institutional conditions. This variety represents a wide range of challenges and opportunities and serves the project’s goal of working towards context-specific Nexus solutions. The pilot sites include coastal farming areas, urban outskirts, flat plains, and hilly and mountainous watersheds. They demonstrate how issues such as water scarcity, resource inefficiency, land degradation and loss of biodiversity manifest themselves in different ways across Mediterranean regions. But they also hold a huge potential for new ideas, driving NbSs, digital technologies, and above all stakeholder involvement for co-creation and validation.

The LLs serve as real-world laboratories where field implementation, EO data, and local knowledge converge to promote Ecosystem based Adaptation (EbA) and effective resource management. The real value of the LLs network lies in its ability to test tailored solution packages, combining smart farming, digital technologies, and Nature-based Solutions (NbSs), to inform policy frameworks and upscaling the transition to resilient, sustainable WEFEE systems.

While working together to advance the project’s goal of driving systemic change through practical and collaborative innovation, each LL provides a unique perspective on the overall study, as presented in the next chapters.

1.3 Living Lab teams

Figure 1. NexusLabs, Living Lab sites

The Living Lab teams are listed below.

Table 1. Living Lab team list – NexusLabs

n°	Living Lab	Country	Partners' mail
1	Pinios River Basin	(GR) 	<u>SWRI (Soil and Water Research Institute)</u> Andreas Panagopoulos – a.panagopoulos@elgo.gr Vassilios Pisinaras – v.pisinaras@elgo.gr Christos Pavlakis - c.pavlakis@elgo.gr
2	Koiliaris	(GR) 	<u>TUC (Technical University of Crete)</u> Nikolaos Nikolaidis – ninikolaidis@isc.tuc.gr Maria Lilli – mllilli@isc.tuc.gr Evangelia Koukianaki Antonia Maragkaki
3	Tarquina Plain	(IT) 	<u>CREA (Council for Agricultural Research and Economics)</u> Silvia Vanino – silvia.vanino@crea.gov.it Valentina Baratella – valentina.baratella@crea.gov.it Fabrizio Pucci – fabrizio.pucci@crea.gov.it Stefano Fabiani – stefano.fabiani@crea.gov.it Antonella Di Fonzo – antonella.difonzo@crea.gov.it Maria Valentina Lasorella – mvalentina.lasorella@crea.gov.it Ileana.Iocola – ileana.iocola@crea.gov.it

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4	Torre Guaceto	(IT) 	<u>IRSA (The Water Research Institute) – CNR</u> Ivan Portoghese - ivan.portoghese@cnr.it Virginia Rosa Coletta – virginiarosacoletta@cnr.it Claudia Panciera - claudiapanciera@cnr.it
5	Veneto Region	(IT) 	<u>UNIPD (University of Padua)</u> Mauro Masiero - mauro.masiero@unipd.it Alessandra Santini – alessandra.santini@unipd.it Laura Secco – laura.secco@unipd.it
6	Tensift River Basin	(MA) 	<u>UCAM (Université Cadi Ayyad)</u> Lahoucine Hanich - lahoucine.hanich@gmail.com Ali Rhoujjati - a.rhoujjati@uca.ma Adnane Chakir - adnane454@gmail.com
7	Júcar River Basin	(ES) 	<u>AGRISAT IBERIA SL – UCLM</u> Anna Osann – anna.oasann@gmail.com Esteban Henao - esteban.henao@agrisat.es Mllanos Lopez – mllanos.lopez@agrisat.es
8	Middle Jordan Valley	(JO) 	<u>NARC (National Agricultural Research Centre)</u> Sami Awabdeh – sami_awabdeh@yahoo.com Rawad Sweidan – rawados@gmail.com Abeer Balawneh - aberfer@yahoo.com Deema Alzoubi - deemaalzoubi@yahoo.com Safaa Aljaafreh - safabj@yahoo.com
9	Menemen Plain	(TR) 	<u>UTAEM (International Agricultural Research and Training Centre)</u> Zübeyde Albayram Dogan – zubeydealbayram.dogan@tarimorman.gov.tr Tuncay Topdemir – tuncay.topdemir@tarimorman.gov.tr

2. Pathways to Impact

The Living Labs are the operational heart of NexusLabs, where field data and local knowledge converge to produce tested, transferable approaches to resource management under real-world constraints. Working across nine sites simultaneously is what gives the NexusLabs project its analytical strength: solutions that hold across the Mediterranean, carrying a knowledge that no single case study can provide.

Each LL contributes a distinct perspective in terms of climate, governance, cropping systems, and NbSs maturity, while sharing a common analytical framework. The baseline documented here is the starting point for translating that diversity into scalable insights.

2.1 Contribution to impacts (expected impacts & other impacts)

D3.1 is the foundational output of Task 3.1 and the intended benchmarking reference for the WP3 demonstration cycle. It is designed to support SO3 by providing a documented starting point against which demo campaign results (D3.3) could be assessed, and to enable the ex-ante Innovation Readiness Level assessment (T3.4, CNR-IRSA) that would map each LL's social, institutional, and technical readiness for NbS adoption. A well-structured baseline of this kind could also help make the project's quantitative targets more meaningful in practice — including the >10% reduction in water and nutrient use, the >10% improvement in WEFEEi scores, and measurable gains in soil organic carbon referenced in the project KPIs — by offering a clear reference condition for comparison.

Looking ahead, the knowledge assembled here on governance structures, institutional actors, and existing NbS practices across the nine LLs may also prove useful in informing the enabling environment analysis planned under WP6, and in supporting the multi-actor community activities central to SO1 and WP1.

2.2 Connections with other WPs: Interdependencies & synergies

D3.1 is intended as a shared reference that multiple Work Packages could draw on as the project progresses. WP4 may use the LL characterisations to help define system boundaries and ground the participatory modelling process. WP5 could draw on data assembled here to support footprint calculations and LCA inventory construction. WP6 may find the baseline useful in assessing adoption readiness and informing upscaling action plans, particularly in combination with the Innovation Readiness Level framework (CNR-IRSA, T3.4), which is designed for iterative comparison against ex-ante reference. WP2 could use the description of existing infrastructure and NbS gaps to help tailor solution packages to the specific conditions of each site. WP1, while not directly involved in producing this deliverable, is expected to engage closely with its content as stakeholder activities unfold, and its outputs will in turn help refine and update the baseline picture over time.

2.3 Aspects of implementation in LLs

The nine LLs vary in scale, from farm clusters and small catchments to large river basins, and in implementation maturity. Some LLs enter NexusLabs with operational smart irrigation systems and

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stakeholder-endorsed NbS, ready for validation and upscaling. Most other sites are in active piloting mode. Others, given their scale and governance complexity, are oriented more toward co-design and institutional innovation than direct field demonstration.

This gradient is not a limitation but a deliberate feature of the network: sites at more advanced stages generate evidence that informs design choices at earlier-stage ones, enabling a form of accelerated cross-LL learning that a set of homogeneous pilots could not provide.

3. Baseline description of the Tarquinia LL (Italy)

3.1 Geographic and environmental context

The Italian Living Lab is located in central Italy, within the Lazio Region, approximately 80 Km north of Rome. The extended area includes the municipalities of Tarquinia (VT), Tolfa (RM), Monte Romano (VT), and Allumiere (RM), with a total surface area of approximately 58,000 ha (Fig. 2). The area features a diverse topographic and environmental profile, ranging from coastal plains to volcanic uplands and transitional hill zones.

In this extensive territory, the area of Tarquinia, located on the coast, serves as the central hub for both administrative and economic purposes and represents the largest and most productive agricultural center. It is characterized by flat terrain and deep alluvial soils that support intensive agricultural production. The area covers roughly 27.000 ha, of which 67% is used for agriculture. Around 45% of this agricultural land is classified as irrigable, and in 2014, approximately 4000 ha were actively irrigated. The Marta and Mignone rivers serve the plain, and water resources are managed by the Water User Association (WUA) “Consorzio di Bonifica Litorale Nord”. Due to the intensity of agricultural activity, 85% of the area has been designated as a Nitrate Vulnerable Zone, reflecting concerns over groundwater contamination and nutrient leaching.

Figure 2. “Tarquinia Living Lab area”. Source: CREA.

In 2004, Tarquinia entered the UNESCO World Heritage List mainly for its Etruscan necropolises,

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regarded as remarkable examples of pre-Roman urban life. Tolfa and Allumiere also have a rich historical background with medieval town centers and evidence of past mining activities that influenced their economic and social development. Such activities shaped economic paths and social ties in lasting ways.

The “Saline di Tarquinia” Natural Park covers about 170 ha (Fig. 3). The area has considerable environmental significance because of rare bird species along with halophytic plants adapted to salty conditions. This renowned biodiversity is the reason the area qualifies as a Site of Community Importance (SCI), and a Special Protection Area (SPA), contributing to the European Union Natura 2000 network.

Figure 3. “Saline di Tarquinia” Natural Park. Source: www.lextra.news 2025.

Additional Natura 2000 sites include several Natural Reserves as the “Litorale” between Tarquinia and Montalto di Castro (SCI), Fiume Mignone (SPA), the Acropolis and Necropolis of Tarquinia (SCI), the marine and fluvial habitats between Marina di Tarquinia and Punta della Quaglia (SIC) and the mouths of the Arrone and Marta rivers (SCI). There are also protected area for safeguarding water for human consumption: Tarquinia Gebelletta Monterozzi (SPA) and Tarquinia Pozzi Nardi – Marina Velca – Pozzi Mainardi (SPA).

The municipalities of Tolfa, Monte Romano, and Allumiere play a key role for the ecological integrity across the Living Lab. The volcanic origin of the soils, combined with low population density and extensive land use, has preserved large tracts of native vegetation and ecological corridors. These areas are particularly suitable for the implementation of agroecological practices, silvo-pastoral systems, and habitat restoration projects. Tolfa and Allumiere host important remnants of Mediterranean maquis, oak woods and grasslands, which provide refuge for fauna such as wild boar, foxes and pollinators.

Monte Romano, with its transitional landscape between the coast and the inland hills, offers opportunities for ecological diversification and multifunctional land use. The diverse landscapes and rich biodiversity found in the Living Lab are well-suited for integrated resource management approaches designed to address the interconnected challenges of the WEF E Nexus, serving as an ideal real-world laboratory for realizing the NexusLabs objective of translating "knowledge into practice."

3.1.1 Climate

The climate across the Living Lab is Mediterranean with hot, dry summer and warm, wet winter. This climatic condition is common in coastal and sub-coastal areas of central Italy, where it significantly impacts on agricultural activities, water usage and functionality of natural systems. The variation of temperature does not only depend on the elevation but can also be affected by proximity to the sea and exposure to prevailing winds. These fluctuations have a high impact on crops ecophysiology, irrigation needs, and soil conservation measures. The climate on the Tarquinia coast is characterized by higher temperatures and extreme dryness, especially during the summer months, leading to a rise in evapotranspiration and a high demand for irrigation. As shown in (Figure 4), over the past ten years in the Tarquinia area, rainfall has decreased while temperatures have increased by more than 1.6 °C for both the minimum and the mean values. In contrast, the upland areas of Tolfa and Allumiere, situated at higher altitudes on the Tolfa Mountains, benefit from cooler temperatures and relatively higher annual precipitation. These conditions favour the development of extensive livestock farming systems and integrated forestry-agriculture systems and have less pressure on water resources than lowlands.

Monte Romano is situated in a transitional area between the coast and the uplands, which shows intermediate climatic characteristics, namely moderate rainfall depths and temperature gradients that allow for diversified cropping systems.

Figure 4. Climatic data (temperature and rainfall) of the Tarquinia station for 2015, 2020, and 2025. (Source: CREA elaboration from ARSIAL data, 2025)

3.1.2 Soil

The plain of Tarquinia is dominated by alluvial and fluviomarine deposits with medium to high fertility, showing good physical properties. These soils are well drained, used for intensive cropping systems, and prone to nitrate accumulation because of long-term use of synthetic fertilizers. The porous sublayers and shallow wells result in fast percolation, posing a threat of leaching and aquifer contamination. The upland regions of Tolfa and Allumiere feature soils of volcanic origin, developed from leucitic and trachytic substrates. These parent materials give rise to andosols—specifically cambisols of moderate fertility—which are notable for their excellent water-retention capabilities. These soils are frequently acid, have high organic content and can be used for extensive grazing and forestry. Monte Romano has a pedologic profile of transition, since soils are mixed types formed from sediments and recent volcanic activities. These are clayey vertisols and loam cambisols, which are soil types with promising agronomic potential, but they must be well managed to avoid the damage of structure by crusting and water-logging conditions.

A few regions across the Living Lab undergo soil degradation processes, including loss of organic carbon and biological activity, due to mechanization and monoculture. These processes are most pronounced in highly managed fields and hilly areas with short crop rotations. The lack of community-based soil conservation measures exacerbates these dynamics. The region's soil heterogeneity is both a challenge and an opportunity for Nexus interventions, since site-specific solutions become necessary for water use and control, fertilisation, and soil recovery.

One of the main issues concerns the potential siting of the National Repository for radioactive waste, managed by SOGIN, the Italian company responsible for the decommissioning of nuclear plants and the safety of radioactive materials. Among all the eligible Italian sites selected, three are placed near Tarquinia (VT-8, VT-27, and VT-36) and have been identified as “very good” candidates for disposal. This decision, which has been appealed by Tarquinia and nearby municipalities, citizens, private companies, and local NGOs, is currently under review. If confirmed, the repository will cover an area of about 150 ha, with long-term implications for land management, environmental safety, area monitoring, and public perception.

3.1.3 Water

The management of water resources is a critical component of territorial sustainability and agricultural productivity of the Tarquinia Plain. The area is managed by the WUA (Consorzio di Bonifica Litorale Nord), which plays a central role in regulating irrigation and in the protection of hydrographic stability. Historically established for land reclamation and irrigation activities, the WUA has progressively expanded its mandate to include soil protection, hydrogeological risk mitigation, and rational use of water resources in agriculture. The WUA is also responsible for the management and maintenance of the hydrographic network, ensuring an adequate water flow and the distribution of water across the territory. The network includes canals, pumping stations, reservoirs, and control structures that need regular monitoring and maintenance. As of 2017, the Consorzio managed a total area of approximately 160,000 ha, extending well beyond the Living Lab extension. Focusing on the Living Lab, only about 4,000 ha are currently irrigated, reflecting both infrastructural limitations and the need for energy-efficient

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solutions. The distribution of water remains complex due to structural and management challenges, including outdated infrastructure and high energy costs associated with pumping operations. These restrictions directly affect water availability and the reliability of the irrigation service, particularly during the summer months when water demand is at its maximum.

Quantity is not the only issue affecting water; quality also poses a significant concern. Groundwater of the Tarquinia Plain is characterized by nitrate pollution, which is mainly due to intensive fertilization in conventional agriculture.

Surface waters are also affected by scattered discharges of greywater and sewage, resulting from illegal activities or the overloading of treatment plants during peak tourism months. The classification of the area as a Nitrate Vulnerable Zone (NVZ) under regional and EU regulations highlights the urgency of implementing corrective measures, including improved nutrient management, crop rotation, and the adoption of agroecological practices.

Drinking water services in the municipality of Tarquinia are managed by public authorities, separate from the WUA's mandate. These services are regulated under regional and national frameworks, ensuring compliance with health and safety standards, although they are not directly involved in agricultural water distribution.

3.1.4 Energy

Tarquinia and its neighbouring municipalities undergo national and regional energy policies. The area also hosts one of Italy's most impactful fossil fuel infrastructures: the "ENEL Torrevaldaliga Nord" thermoelectric plant, with a total installed capacity of 1,980 MW across three coal-fired units. The plant has historically ranked as the second-highest emitter of CO₂ in the country, with annual emissions approaching 11 million tons (via Decree No. 680/2003). In response to the national decarbonization targets, the plant is undergoing a transformation process that will replace coal combustion units with a new gas unit. This aligns with the Integrated National Plan for Energy and Climate (PNIEC), which expects a full decarbonization of existing plants and a 40% reduction in national CO₂ emissions by 2030. Over the years, multiple environmental monitoring campaigns have been carried out to evaluate the impact of plant emissions on local agroecosystems, particularly concerning heavy metals and airborne pollutants.

In parallel, the Lazio Region has approved the development of several large-scale photovoltaic fields on agricultural land, the largest of which is planned to cover 304 ha in the Pian d'Arcione area, a highly productive agricultural site of Tarquinia. While the initiative aligns with renewable energy goals, it has raised concerns among local stakeholders and the municipality regarding potential negative impacts on agriculture, tourism, and landscape integrity. This tension highlights the importance of balancing energy transition objectives with territorial compatibility, especially in areas of high agro-ecological and cultural value.

3.2 Socio-economic characteristics

3.2.1 Demographic profile

The extended Living Lab hosts a total population of approximately 26,200 inhabitants across four municipalities: Tarquinia (16,000), Tolfa (4,700), Allumiere (4,000), and Monte Romano (1,900). The demography indicates general rurality and population aging, with an average age of 47 years, which is higher than the national average. Population density varies significantly, with Tarquinia presenting more urbanized and coastal settlements, while Tolfa, Allumiere, and Monte Romano maintain low-density, dispersed rural communities. shows population trends in the Lazio Region and in the four municipalities Monte Romano, Tarquinia, Allumiere, and Tolfa, between 2005 and 2025.

Table 2. Population in the municipalities of Tarquinia, Tolfa, Monte Romano, and Allumiere: Source ISTAT, 2005 –2025.

Y	Lazio Region	Monte Romano (VT)	Tarquinia (VT)	Allumiere (RM)	Tolfa (RM)	Total 4 Municipalities
2005	5.240.603	1.928	15.665	4.152	5.037	26.782
2010	5.516.026	1.991	16.160	4.249	5.202	27.602
2015	5.744.899	2.077	16.524	4.011	5.224	27.836
2020	5.755.700	1.928	16.148	3.879	4.954	26.909
2025	5.710.272	1.868	15.829	3.788	4.663	26.148

The four cities present a population trend with a moderate increase until 2015 and a slight decrease from then on. Collectively, their population dropped from 26,782 in 2005 to 26,148 by the year 2025, with a small but steady decline noted the past years.

During the last two decades, moderate depopulation has occurred especially in upland zones as a result of the out-migration of young people and reduced diversification of employment. The birth rate is lower than the replacement rate, and the natural demographic balance is negative in all municipalities. In the summer there is an increase in the population of Tarquinia due to tourism, although this does not counteract the overall decline in demography.

3.2.2 Gender mainstreaming

Gender distribution in the Living Lab is fairly balanced but slightly skewed toward women (approximately 51.5% women vs. 48.5% men) (Table 3). Yet, gendered division of labour in the local economy and civic engagement remains asymmetrical. In agriculture, male farm ownership and management is still predominant, although female involvement is on the rise, primarily in organic farming, agritourism and cooperatives.

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Table 3. Population and distribution per gender from 2005 – 2025. Source: ISTAT

Y	Gender	Lazio Region	%	Monte Romano (VT)	%	Tarquinia (VT)	%	Allumiere (RM)	%	Tolfa (RM)	%	Total 4 Municipalities	%
2005	Male	2.510.660	48%	950	49%	7.652	49%	2.040	49%	2.532	50%	13.174	49%
	Female	2.729.943	52%	978	51%	8.013	51%	2.112	51%	2.505	50%	13.608	51%
2010	Male	2.642.675	48%	988	50%	7.875	49%	2.100	49%	2.618	50%	13.581	49%
	Female	2.873.351	52%	1.003	49%	8.285	49%	2.149	50%	2.584	50%	14.021	51%
2015	Male	2.762.744	48%	1.023	49%	8.024	51%	1.995	50%	2.628	50%	13.670	49%
	Female	2.982.155	52%	1.054	51%	8.500	51%	2.016	50%	2.596	50%	14.166	51%
2020	Male	2.779.181	48%	971	50%	7.843	49%	1.927	50%	2.500	50%	13.241	49%
	Female	2.976.519	52%	957	50%	8.305	49%	1.952	50%	2.454	50%	13.668	51%
2025	Male	2.771.470	49%	926	50%	7.714	49%	1.882	50%	2.360	51%	12.882	49%
	Female	2.938.802	51%	942	50%	8.115	51%	1.906	50%	2.303	49%	13.266	51%

3.2.3 Economic activities and territorial specialization

In the province of Viterbo, as of 31 October 2025, there are 32,268 economically active companies, representing a decline of 0.8% compared to the same month in 2024. The main economic sector is agriculture, accounting for 33.8% of the total (**Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.**)

Table 4. Number of activities in Viterbo province grouped by sectors in October 2025. Source: opendata.marche.camcom.it – CCIAA Marche on data InfoCamere.

Sectors	Active companies (n.)	% respect total
Agriculture	10900	33.8
Wholesale and retail trade	5949	18.4
Constructions	4612	14.3
Activities of accommodation and catering services	2058	6.4
Other service activities	1946	6.0
Manufacturing activity	1623	5.0
Real estate activities	1009	3.1
Administrative and support services activities	948	2.9
Others	3223	10.1
Total	32268	

Similarly, in the LL territory, the local economy is strongly rooted in agriculture, with differentiated specializations across the Living Lab. Tarquinia is the most productive zone, with intensive cultivation of durum wheat, vegetables (tomatoes, melons, artichokes), olive groves, and vineyards. The presence of irrigation infrastructure managed by WUA, and proximity to logistics hubs (SS1 Aurelia, Port of Civitavecchia) supports market-oriented farming and agro-industrial processing.

Tolfa and Allumiere are characterized by extensive livestock farming (cattle, sheep), forage production, and agroforestry. These areas maintain traditional agro-pastoral systems and host several organic farms certified under EU regulations. Monte Romano presents a transitional profile, with cereal cultivation, small-scale horticulture, and emerging interest in agroecological practices.

Beyond agriculture, the territory benefits from tourism, especially in Tarquinia, which attracts national

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and international visitors due to its UNESCO-listed Etruscan necropolises. Tolfa and Allumiere offer historical town centers, artisanal crafts, and nature trails, contributing to rural tourism and local identity. Agritourism is well expanded across the area, often linked to organic production and landscape valorization. The BioDiscript known as “Maremma Etrusca e Monti della Tolfa” (MET) acts as a territorial platform for coordination of initiatives and cooperation between producers, institutions, and consumers.

3.3 Land use and infrastructures

The Living Lab presents a diversified land use shaped by geomorphological and climatic conditions, historical settlement patterns, and agricultural specialization. The territory covers approximately 58,000 ha, with land use distributed among agricultural fields, forested areas, urban settlements, and natural ecosystems (Tab. 5).

Table 5. Reports the Utilized Agricultural Area (UAA) for the main crops in both the Lazio Region and the four municipalities of the Tarquinia LL.

Crops type	UAA - ha	Farms - UAA
	2020	2020
Lazio Region		
Arable crops	353.746	38.715
<i>Cereals</i>	100.531	11.346
<i>Rotational fodder crops</i>	180.177	23.822
Permanent crops	120.843	45.233
<i>Vineyards</i>	14.292	10.899
<i>Olive trees for table olives and oil production</i>	52.703	39.219
<i>Fruit Orchards</i>	45.453	10.998
Family vegetable gardens	895	10.200
Permanent meadows	166.799	14.677
Monte Romano (VT)		
Arable crops	2.684	205
<i>Cereals</i>	434	51
<i>Rotational fodder crops</i>	2.156	178
Permanent crops	168	114
<i>Olive trees for table olives and oil production</i>	166	114
Family vegetable gardens	1	11
Permanent meadows	4.757	46
Tarquinia (VT)		
Arable crops	17.648	980
<i>Cereals</i>	7.541	643
<i>Dried pulses</i>	1.288	171
<i>Vegetables crops</i>	2.096	231
<i>Rotational fodder crops</i>	5.500	491
Permanent crops	736	426
<i>Vineyards</i>	156	126

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<i>Olive trees for table olives and oil production</i>	293	378
<i>Fruit Orchards</i>	275	55
Family vegetable gardens	11	107
Permanent meadows	6.532	89
Allumiere (RM)		
Arable crops	671	52
<i>Cereals</i>	103	10
<i>Rotational fodder crops</i>	460	42
Permanent crops	42	29
Family vegetable gardens	2	18
Permanent meadows	6.750	63
Tolfa (RM)		
Arable crops	2.242	114
<i>Cereals</i>	447	39
<i>Dried pulses</i>	238	8
<i>Rotational fodder crops</i>	1.376	84
Permanent crops	104	51
<i>Vineyards</i>	50	20
<i>Olive trees for table olives and oil production</i>	30	39
<i>Fruit Orchards</i>	24	12
Family vegetable gardens	1	16
Permanent meadows	8.370	86

Agricultural fields occupy about 65% of the land, mainly cropland along the coastal plain of Tarquinia, while mixed-use systems are found in the upland areas of Tolfa, Allumiere, and Monte Romano. Most of the land has been reclaimed for agriculture with large-scale cereal cultivation, horticulture, olive groves, and vineyards.

The flat topography of Tarquinia and fertile soils support intensive farming, facilitated by irrigation infrastructure managed by the WUA. The presence of the Marta and Mignone rivers, along with a network of canals and wells, ensures water distribution across irrigable parcels, although seasonal scarcity and nitrate vulnerability remain critical issues. However, the area continues to largely depend on meteoric water, surface, and groundwater sources.

In the upland municipalities of Tolfa and Allumiere, land use is more extensive, and agricultural fields are more scattered. These areas are structured by volcanic soils and comprise of forested ridges, and pastures used for livestock grazing. Agro-pastoral systems blend with natural habitats, and land management practices often reflect traditional knowledge and low-input approaches. Monte Romano, situated in a transition zone, features diverse cropping systems and forage production, with growing interest in organic and regenerative agriculture (Figure 5. Crops UAA for the 4 municipalities of the pilot..

Urban settlements are mainly concentrated in the historic centers of Tarquinia, Tolfa, Allumiere, and Monte Romano, while coastal areas such as Lido di Tarquinia, Marina Velca, Voltone have experienced residential and tourism development. The built environment occupies approximately 9% of the total

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surface, and urban expansion remains limited due to landscape protection regulations and regional planning constraints.

Figure 5. Crops UAA for the 4 municipalities of the pilot.

3.4 Unlocking opportunities for NexusLabs

The Tarquinia Living Lab presents complex environmental, socio-economic, and infrastructural challenges relevant to WEF Nexus approaches and Nature-Based Solutions (NbSs). Its heterogeneous land use, agricultural systems, and governance structures make it a strategic Mediterranean testing ground for replicable, resilient strategies.

Water is the most critical challenge. Climatic scarcity is compounded by management inefficiencies and high pumping energy costs. Summer tourism sharply increases coastal water demand, competing directly with agriculture. Groundwater quality is compromised by nitrate pollution from synthetic fertilizers, while surface water suffers from illegal or overloaded sewage discharges during peak tourist months. This makes Tarquinia a valuable testbed for integrated water governance and NbSs targeting efficiency, pollution reduction, and resilience.

Soil degradation — driven by intensive monoculture and mechanized farming — is reducing long-term productivity and climate resilience through erosion and organic matter loss. Site-specific, heterogeneity-aware fertilization and soil management strategies are needed.

On energy, the area is transitioning from traditional to renewable infrastructures. The NexusLabs co-creation framework offers an opportunity to keep local communities engaged in integrated solutions supporting multifunctional land use and minimizing conflicts between energy and agricultural sectors.

3.4.1 NbSs and Smart Tools Currently Implemented

In Tarquinia, the Water User Association (WUA) is modernizing irrigation and pumping infrastructure — including flow meters — following an unexplained water capacity shortfall, funded through national and EU sources. Extraordinary hydraulic maintenance is also underway to reduce hydrogeological risk.

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Several large photovoltaic and agrivoltaic projects characterize the ongoing renewable energy transition in the area.

The “Maremma Etrusca e Monti della Tolfa” (MET) Bio-district provides a governance framework that promotes organic agriculture across the Living Lab’s four municipalities by creating NbSs-enabling conditions. It coordinates sustainable land-use by prioritizing Nature-Based Solutions that directly overlap with organic crop management, such as hedgerow restoration for landscape connectivity, natural pest control, and diversified crop rotations. By aligning these technical interventions with multi-stakeholder cooperation among local authorities, farmers, and civil society, the Bio-district ensures that agricultural practices actively support integrated WEF management, securing water quality, enhancing soil energy cycles, and protecting food-system ecosystems at multiple scales.

Farm numbers have declined, but Utilized Agricultural Area (UAA) has remained stable, indicating farm enlargement. Nevertheless, agriculture remains fragmented and small-scale, limiting modernization, credit access, innovation, and market competitiveness. Targeted interventions are needed to strengthen local value chains and enhance product quality and distinctiveness.

The MET Bio-district, together with farmers' cooperatives (COT and COPA, active in fruit and vegetable production, processing, and distribution), can act as organizational backbones supporting territorial identity, traceability, and value-added supply chains.

Finally, the River, Lake, and Coast Contract (CO.LA.FI.CO.) adds another governance layer, coordinating integrated water body management, hydraulic risk prevention, and ecosystem preservation through voluntary agreements among public authorities, communities, and stakeholders. Despite only partial success in delivering governance and environmental improvements so far, it remains a relevant institutional asset for WEF-integrated management.

2.4.2 NbSs and Tool Implementation in the LL

Within the framework of the NexusLabs project, the Living Lab in Tarquinia and its surrounding municipalities will serve as a living laboratory for testing innovative approaches to resource management, climate resilience, and sustainability. Aligning with the Sustainable Development Goals, these approaches will include the introduction of NbSs related to water efficiency, soil health improvement, and biodiversity enhancement for climate adaptation. Specifically, the Living Lab will address the challenge of water scarcity by improving irrigation efficiency through precision agriculture (field monitoring system). On the other hand, the implementation of NbSs focusing on ecosystem-based agronomic practices, mainly sustainable, regenerative soil management practices, will naturally enhance ecosystem functions without relying only on high-input technologies. These approaches have been proven to mitigate soil erosion, thereby increasing resilience against extreme precipitation events, improving soil health and water retention, and enhancing biodiversity in both the pedosphere and the above-ground biosphere. These efforts are especially critical in the Tarquinia plain, where intensive farming, combined with extreme seasonal precipitation and droughts, places increasing pressure on crop cultivation, particularly in the hilly areas, as mentioned in the previous paragraphs.

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The designation of the area as a Nitrate Vulnerable Zone further underscores the need for coordinated interventions that optimize crop nutrient and water use while restoring ecosystem functions. The agronomic and ecophysiological crop monitoring planned for this area will help improve water and nutrient management, ultimately reducing the negative impact of fertilization practices on groundwater quality. At the same time, the pilot will promote active, continuous engagement with the MET Biodistrict, supporting all initiatives developed to enhance high-value agricultural production, Nexus values, and circular economy models. The main objectives are to facilitate knowledge dissemination and co-creation among producers, researchers, institutions, and civil society, and enabling peer-to-peer sharing of best practices. Stakeholder engagement is, in fact, a cornerstone of the NexusLabs approach.

Through agronomic activities conducted by the Living Lab, participatory initiatives, and educational programs, the Tarquinia pilot will foster the active involvement of farmers, practitioners, schools, and local institutions in the co-design and implementation of resource management strategies. Participatory dynamics will strengthen community ownership and ensure that innovation is grounded in local needs and capacities, enhancing its long-term feasibility. This approach will not only support Nexus solutions across the Living Lab but also positively reinforce the cultural and ecological identity of the territory.

3.4.3 Description of experimental demo sites

The experimental demo site is located at "Casale Poggio Nebbia" farm in Tarquinia, certified organic since 2012 (Fig. 6). Spanning nearly 50 hectares in a historically cereal-rich region known as the "Granary of Rome", its main activities include rainfed cereals (wheat, barley, spelt), fodder (alfalfa hay supplied exclusively to local organic farms), olive orchards, small orchards, and a vegetable garden. Cereals are processed on-site into flour and pasta; olives — native varieties Canino, Leccino, and Moraiolo — are manually harvested, and same-day milled into extra virgin olive oil. Artisanal jams and preserves, along with other specialties, are sold primarily through the on-site agritourism facility.

The 2.50-hectare vineyard — planted with red (spurred cordon) and white (Guyot) varieties, relying solely on subsistence irrigation — serves as the experimental demo site for technology and strategy innovations within the pilot. A farm winery completes the cycle with organic wine production.

Figure 6. “Casale Poggionebbia” vineyards and fist soil sampling points.

3.5 Data sources and methodology

A wide variety of data sources were screened to establish a comprehensive baseline understanding of the pilot's current state, including the components: *Clima, Crop, Demo, Economy, Energy, Geo, Land, Use, Water, Soil, Management and Policy*.

The resulting WP3 Database summarizes the data types collected, detailing the specific sources and providing comments on the methodology and scope of each dataset (see the following **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.**6 as an illustrative extract). This baseline data is intended to serve as a shared resource, potentially functioning as a centralized, common reference point for all NexusLabs WPs.

The WP3 database concept was designed to ensure both consistency, by sharing the same verified starting information, and efficiency, by avoiding redundant data collection across different WPs teams. Additionally, it supports extensive integration of the Nexus approach, where data from different sectors (Climate, Crop, Energy, ...) are analyzed together, ensuring a robust and multidisciplinary assessment.

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Table 6. Data sources and methodology for the Tarquinia pilot (from WP3 database).

	Data	Comments/Specs	Info
Clima	Hydrometeorological data	incl. historical variability	Regional Agency ARSIAL
	Climate change/variability and sinks.	incl. sinks (atmosphere, outflows to sea, percolation to groundwater) etc	University of Tuscia , ARPA Lazi, Regione Lazio previous studies (Vanino et al., 2025)
Crop	Crop types and features		ISTAT Agricultural Census, interviews and bibliographic data.
	Crop prices		ISMEA (2000–2025) (Not all crops are included; to be integrated with the Italian database), ISTAT data
	Crop types and their practices (primarily irrigation)	LPIS	ISTAT Agricultural Census, SIGRIAN (National Irrigation Information System) for the year 2022, Regional Geotopographic Database (code 060106 - CL_AGR), scale 1:5000, version 2014 — Class “Agricultural crop”, WUA
	Irrigation water requirements and cost		WUA, agricultural literature, interviews
Demo	Demographic data at the pilot scale		ISTAT data
	Social characterization of the Living Lab		“Piano di Zona” report (2021–2023) for the VT/2 Social and Health District (Province of Viterbo), National Atlas of Rural Territories – Local System of Tarquinia
Economy	Territorial economic data		1st Economic Report of Upper Lazio – 2021
	Management costs		Prezzario delle opere agricole e forestali – Lazio 2022 (Lazio Region’s Agriculture Department)
	Energy prices		Electricity costs for farms: 0.12–0.18 € /kWh (to be verified)
Energy	Energy consumption for agriculture	e.g. for pumping and irrigation	Energy/pumping or on-farm pressurization (e.g., groundwater extraction): estimates from agricultural literature range between 0.09–0.24 € /m ³ for energy/lifting costs (to be verified)
	Current primary energy sources		National Energy Balance (BEN) – Eurostat methodology, data 1990–2020 Regional Statistics 2022 – TERNA
	Energy allocation		National Energy Balance (BEN) – Eurostat methodology, data 1990–2020 Regional Statistics 2022 – TERNA
	Primary energy sources requiring water		National Energy Balance (BEN) – Eurostat methodology, data 1990–2020 Regional Statistics 2022 – TERNA
Geo	Cartography study area and pilots (cadaster, water management unit,...)	shapefile georeferenced	WUA, Regione Lazio geoportale
	Rivers and lake bodies		University of Tuscia, ARPA Lazio Regione Lazio
Land Use	Land Use/Cover data and its dynamic changes	RS data Classification + LPIS + CLC	LIPs (https://geodati.gov.it/geoportale/visualizzazione-metadati/scheda-metadati/?uuid=agea:OPENIACS:LPIS:m002)
	Land use maps definition (period of time, spatial scale, and legend)		Regione Lazio geoportale, Corine Land Cover and Land Use maps (at the national level, 10 m pixel resolution from Sentinel data) are also available on the ISPRA website for the years 1990, 2000, 2006, 2012, 2018, 2022, and 2023
	Records of natural disasters (floods, fires, erosion, etc)	Copernicus, etc.	Inventory of landslide phenomena managed by ISPRA, Regione Lazio geoportale
	Future land use/ land use change scenarios		Study on three future scenarios (LULCC) up to 2030 in Lazio Region, using the InVEST Scenario Generator and the Habitat Quality model (Pirri et al, 2021)
Water	Renewable (surface and groundwater) water sources and stocks		University of Tuscia, ARPA Lazio, Regione Lazio “Tempo Reale”
	Water demand and its distribution among uses (for potable use, irrigation/agriculture, industry),	spatially distributed/historical when possible	ISTAT, District Basin Authority of the Central Apennines
	Description of water management (irrigation systems, policy, assignment of volumes,...)		Ex Reclamation Consortium of the Maremma Etrusca – Classification Plan for the Distribution of Consortium Charges; Irrigation Regulation for the Tarquinia Plain – Updated 24 September 2025

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	Treated water	Treated wastewater data in Lazio from Acea S.p.A.
Soil	Soil types and/or hydrologic groups	Soil observations of the Lazio Region
	Soil map types (classification of soils)	Soil Map of the Lazio Region – Scale 1:250.000 – version 2019
Management and Policy	Relevant local/regional/national planning documents and/or regulations	Autorità di Bacino, Lazio region, WUA
	Relevant international regulations	EU Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC); EU Nitrates Directive (91/676/EEC); EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) 2023–2027; EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030.
	List of key stakeholders	Public authorities and governance bodies: Consorzio di Bonifica Litorale Nord (CBLN); Biodistretto “Maremma Etrusca e Monti della Tolfa (MET)” con i comuni Allumiere, Monte Romano, Tarquinia, Tolfa; Research and education institutions: CREA, CNR, Università della Tuscia, Scuole e istituti tecnici agricoli locali; Environmental and civil society organizations ; Private sector and producers: Aziende agricole locali; Cooperative agricole e imprese agroalimentar - see Baratella et al. 2023 https://doi.org/10.4081/ija.2023.2200
	Main WEFE challenges at the pilot scale	Pressure on water resources for irrigation; Water quality (nitrates); Balance between agriculture and ecosystem conservation; Energy efficiency. <i>Previous projects in the Area: LENSES, FATIMA, DIVERFARMING</i>
	Potential funding sources for NEXUS relevant solutions (green deal, Interreg, etc)	Horizon Europe (Cluster 6); LIFE Programme (subprogram Environment & Climate); Interreg Euro-MED; Green Deal Calls; PSR Lazio 2023–2027 Misure su gestione risorse idriche e sostenibilità.
	Scenarios of interest in the Living Lab	Sustainable management scenarios for soil and water resources including climate change adaptation scenarios focused on reducing irrigation demand, increasing water use efficiency, and enhancing soil water retention

4. Baseline description Torre Guaceto LL (Italy)

4.1 Geographic and environmental context

The Torre Guaceto Living Lab is located in southern Italy, in the Apulia Region (Province of Brindisi), along the Adriatic coast between the municipalities of Carovigno and Brindisi. The Living Lab integrates a coastal protected area and the surrounding agricultural district, forming a tightly coupled coastal–agricultural socio-ecological system where irrigated farming, groundwater resources, wetlands and marine ecosystems interact directly.

The core protected terrestrial area is the Torre Guaceto State Nature Reserve, whose extent is reported around 1,114–1,120 ha, including Mediterranean scrublands, agricultural patches, and a brackish wetland system located at the terminal sector of the Canale Reale basin (see Figure 7). The wetland is fed primarily by perennial freshwater springs, with additional episodic runoff contributions during intense rainfall events, and it is physically separated from the Canale Reale channel by embankments regulating inflows (Portoghese et al. 2022). Different documents describe the wetland extent depending on the mapped units considered (core wetland vs. broader wetland/pond system), with values ranging from about 120 ha to 180–230 ha.

Figure 7. Torre Guaceto State Reserve, illustrating the location of the wetland, Canale (from Passarella et al. 2025).

Torre Guaceto is internationally recognized for its ecological value. The site has been designated as a Ramsar wetland since 1981 and is part of the Natura 2000 network; the management framework includes the Special Area of Conservation (SAC/ZSC) “Torre Guaceto e Macchia di San Giovanni” (designation referenced in the management documentation and regional measures). The coastal–marine component is protected through the Torre Guaceto Marine Protected Area (MPA), which is zoned (A/B/C) for different protection levels, and has been subject to discussions on boundary revision and enlargement,

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highlighting its strategic role for marine habitats and biodiversity conservation (eFrame, 2023).

The surrounding agricultural district is dominated by Mediterranean cropping systems (notably olive groves, vineyards, and irrigated horticulture such as artichokes and summer vegetables), with irrigation largely dependent on groundwater abstraction from the coastal aquifer (Perrino et al. 2014). This setting makes Torre Guaceto a representative hotspot for WEFE-Nexus pressures in coastal Mediterranean contexts: intensive seasonal irrigation and climate variability reduce aquifer recharge and promote salinization processes that threaten both agricultural productivity and wetland ecological integrity. Recent scientific analyses specifically identify interacting drivers of salinization at Torre Guaceto, including seawater intrusion/upconing induced by pumping, salt recycling from irrigation with saline groundwater, and marine aerosol deposition with subsequent mobilization during the wet season.

The coexistence of a protected wetland–dune–scrub mosaic (Figure 8), a coastal aquifer vulnerable to salinization, and an intensive agricultural district creates strong interdependencies among water, food production, energy use (notably for irrigation pumping), and ecosystem services. This makes Torre Guaceto particularly suitable for NexusLabs’ objective of testing integrated, place-based solutions that can balance environmental protection with the sustainability of irrigated agriculture under changing climate conditions.

Figure 8. The multi-faceted mosaic of the different ecological components of the Torre Guaceto Living Lab.

4.1.1 Climate

The Torre Guaceto Living Lab is characterized by Mediterranean climate, with hot, dry summers and mild to warm, wetter winters, typical of coastal Apulia. Over the last decades, the area has been described as dry-sub-humid Mediterranean, with long, hot and dry summers, during which temperatures can exceed 40°C and rainfall may be absent for two to three consecutive months, resulting in high evapotranspiration and strong seasonal irrigation demand (Passarella et al. 2020).

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Average annual precipitation in the area is reported at about 600 mm/year (long-term reference), with the majority of rainfall concentrated in the wet season (Lo Presti et al. 2010). Recent assessments based on local meteorological stations indicate a trend toward increasing aridity, consistent with regional climate-change signals in the Mediterranean and with stakeholders' perceptions of more frequent and intense drought periods.

Climate variability is also expressed through the alternation of dry periods (high evaporative demand) and rapid, intense rainfall events, which can limit effective aquifer recharge and enhance soil and groundwater salinity risks. This pattern is particularly relevant for the Torre Guaceto coastal aquifer–wetland system, where groundwater is the primary irrigation source and is already vulnerable to salinization processes.

For baseline characterization and future monitoring, precipitation series for the Torre Guaceto area can be consistently represented using the closest stations from the Regional Weather Monitoring Network (e.g., S. Vito dei Normanni and Brindisi), as done in a recent scientific study on Torre Guaceto groundwater salinization dynamics (Passarella et al. 2025, (data source: <https://protezionecivile.regione.puglia.it/bollettini-pluviometrici>). These data sources support the integration of climate drivers (precipitation and temperature proxies) into scenario analysis of irrigation needs and salinity pressures, coherent with NexusLabs' WEFE approach.

4.1.2 Soil

Soils in the Torre Guaceto Living Lab reflect the coastal–karst transition setting of the Brindisi plain and the Messapian structural threshold. At the regional scale (Figure 9 and 10), the agricultural landscape is underlain by a fractured and karstified carbonate basement, locally covered by porous calcarenites, terraced marine deposits (mainly sands over marly-clayey layers), and younger alluvial–marsh–coastal sediments in low-lying areas (Ciaranfi et al. 1988). This stratigraphic variability controls soil texture, drainage behavior and the vulnerability of the root zone to salt accumulation, especially in the coastal sector and near the wetland system.

A distinctive pedological element of the area is the presence of “*terra rossa*” (clayey red soils) interspersed within carbonate formations, together with soils developed on calcarenite and sandy marine deposits (Passarella et al. 2025). These soils can support high-value Mediterranean crops (vineyards, olives and irrigated horticulture), but their performance is strongly constrained by summer water stress and by the quality of irrigation water.

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Figure 9. Geological map focusing on the main formations outcropping in the study area (from Passarella et al. 2025).

A major soil-related pressure in Torre Guaceto is agricultural soil salinization, which is one of the most impactful consequences of groundwater overexploitation and climate variability in coastal areas. In fact, this condition is linked to the combined effects of: (i) irrigation with brackish/saline groundwater during the dry season, (ii) high evapotranspiration, and (iii) soil and subsoil conditions that locally limit leaching and promote salt build-up in upper layers.

Recent investigations in the Torre Guaceto coastal aquifer system highlight feedbacks between irrigation practices and soil degradation: repeated use of saline groundwater and marine aerosol deposition favour progressive salt accumulation in surface soil layers, which is then mobilized during wet-season infiltration, reinforcing groundwater salinity and the soil–water salinity loop (Passarella et al. 2025). Beyond the total salt load, studies also indicate that the ionic composition of irrigation water matters for soil functioning (Tarolli et al. 2024). When the sodium hazard is relevant (often expressed through sodium adsorption ratio, SAR), soils may progressively lose structural stability due to clay dispersion and surface sealing, which reduces infiltration and drainage and can further promote salt build-up in the root zone. Farmers report field symptoms consistent with reduced soil permeability in some irrigated plots. In such cases, gypsum amendments (CaSO_4) are commonly recommended to mitigate sodium-related impacts and help maintain soil structure and infiltration capacity.

The soil heterogeneity of the Torre Guaceto area is both a challenge and an opportunity for NexusLabs. The challenge lies in the need for site-specific measures to prevent salinity-driven degradation and maintain soil physical functionality under intensive seasonal irrigation. The opportunity is that soil-

regenerative practices (e.g., cover cropping, crop rotations and improved irrigation strategies combined with alternative water sources) can be targeted to the most vulnerable zones, supporting both agricultural productivity and the conservation objectives of the adjacent protected ecosystems.

4.1.3 Water

Water resources are a central sustainability issue in the Torre Guaceto Living Lab, where irrigated agriculture coexists with a coastal wetland system and a marine protected area within a tightly connected hydro-ecological setting. In this coastal Apulian context, groundwater represents the primary conventional source for irrigation, while limited surface-water availability, high summer evapotranspiration and recurrent drought periods make agricultural production strongly dependent on seasonal pumping.

The Torre Guaceto wetland is located at the terminal sector of the Canale Reale basin and is hydraulically linked to the local groundwater system; scientific evidence indicates that the wetland is primarily sustained by perennial freshwater springs, with additional episodic runoff contributions during intense rainfall events, and that inflows from the Canale Reale are regulated by embankments. In parallel, the Canale Reale itself is a key surface-water feature of the wider catchment (≈ 50 km long; basin ≈ 210 km²) and is classified as a heavily modified water body with an ephemeral–intermittent regime; its low flows are strongly supported by treated effluents discharged from multiple WWTPs along the channel. Portoghese et al. (2022) estimate that treated wastewater accounts for about 3.82 Mm³/year ($\approx 16.5\%$) of the annual channel drainage along the Canale Reale, and—crucially—quantify significant channel–aquifer transmission losses: the annual infiltrated volume is estimated at around 6.25 Mm³/year, with 61% attributable to treated wastewater discharges, highlighting the relevance of effluent-supported flows for groundwater recharge in this semi-arid setting.

At the same time, the surrounding agricultural district abstracts groundwater from a coastal aquifer in which the freshwater body naturally overlies intruded seawater, making the system intrinsically vulnerable to salinization (Passarella et al. 2025); over the last decades, large withdrawals for irrigation have contributed to an imbalance between freshwater and underlying saltwater, enhancing salinization phenomena and progressively extending salinity risks inland. Crop-based estimates reported for the Torre Guaceto agricultural basin, indicate that irrigation plays a key role in stabilizing yields, with total groundwater withdrawals estimated around 2.5 Mm³/year, mainly driven by irrigated horticulture (e.g., artichoke and summer vegetables), and complemented by olives and vineyards.

Water quality is therefore a major concern, with groundwater salinization representing the dominant limitation for both agriculture and ecosystem integrity; recent studies describe multiple interacting drivers, including pumping-induced salinization, salt recycling from irrigation with brackish groundwater and marine aerosol deposition, reinforcing a soil–water salinity feedback loop (see Figure 10).

Figure 10. Hydrological conceptual model of the Torre Guaceto Living Lab (from Passarella et al. 2025).

In this context, a key management direction in the area is the reuse of tertiary treated municipal wastewater as an additional irrigation resource, explicitly aimed at reducing groundwater abstraction and mitigating salinization trends; such a transition necessarily involves multiple actors with complementary mandates, including the Torre Guaceto Management Consortium (protected area governance), the regional water utility AQP (wastewater treatment and reuse infrastructure), irrigation service actors and regional authorities responsible for water governance and rural development.

4.1.4 Energy

The Torre Guaceto Living Lab operates within the national and regional energy policy framework, and energy use in the pilot is primarily associated with agricultural activities, with irrigation pumping representing the main farm-level energy demand (grid electricity for pumps), followed by diesel consumption for field operations.

In Torre Guaceto, the water–energy link is particularly relevant because the current irrigation model relies largely on groundwater abstraction from a coastal aquifer affected by salinization, making both irrigation costs and energy exposure (price volatility and operational constraints) a practical driver of farmers’ decision-making.

Importantly, the ongoing revision of the Torre Guaceto Management Plan and its Action Programme explicitly frames a transition toward integrated water management measures, notably the reuse of reclaimed wastewater from the Bufalaria WWTP and the adoption of high-efficiency irrigation practices, as priority strategies to reduce pressure on brackish groundwater, mitigate salinization trends, and support adaptive management through enhanced monitoring. Within this framework, energy becomes a key feasibility component: shifting from individual well pumping to reclaimed-water supply implies different energy requirements linked to water conveyance and pressurization, while efficiency-oriented practices (precision irrigation, monitoring) are expected to reduce overall abstraction and pumping needs.

4.2 Socio-economic characteristics

4.2.1 Demographic profile

The Torre Guaceto Living Lab is embedded in the coastal–rural system of northern Salento (Apulia, Adriatic side), and its socio-economic “functional area” includes the municipalities that directly interact with the Reserve through farming, tourism and service provision (notably Carovigno and Brindisi, and the wider surrounding catchment considered in the Management Plan socio-economic assessment). The area is characterized by a mixed settlement pattern: consolidated urban centers and coastal tourism nodes coexist with dispersed rural settlements and farmsteads. Demographic dynamics are consistent with broader regional trends, including ageing and gradual restructuring of the rural workforce, with seasonal population peaks in summer linked to coastal tourism.

Table 7. Resident population and population density in the Torre Guaceto functional area (2001–2023) (Sources: ISTAT for years 2001, 2011 and 2021; <https://www.tuttitalia.it/> for 2023; adapted by eFrame). Territorial area in 2001, 2011, and 2021 has changed/modi

Territory	Territorial area (kmq) 2023	Resident population 2001	Population density (Inhab/kmq) 2001	Resident population 2011	Population density (Inhab/kmq) 2011	Resident population 2021	Population density (Inhab/kmq) 2021	Resident population 2023	Population density (Inhab/kmq) 2023
Brindisi (Municipality)	333	89.081	268	88.812	267	83.317	250	82.883	249
Carovigno	107	14.980	140	15.898	149	16.925	159	16.984	159
Mesagne	124	27.587	222	27.753	224	28.114	211	28.179	211
Ostuni	228	32.901	146	31.860	141	30.302	134	30.171	134
San Vito del Normanni	67	20.070	299	19.520	292	18.267	272	18.112	270
Brindisi (Province)	1.882	402.422	216	400.801	215	381.273	205	379.522	204
Apulia Region	19.543	4.020.707	206	4.052.566	207	3.922.941	201	3.907.683	200
Italy	302.110	58.995.744	189	59.433.744	197	59.030.133	195	58.997.201	195

4.2.2 Gender mainstreaming

At the population level, gender distribution is generally balanced, but the gendered division of labour emerges more clearly when focusing on agriculture and related rural services. Evidence collected during individual interviews with local actors suggests that gender disparities are perceived, especially in the distribution of roles within farms and related rural activities. Women are more often associated with administrative, managerial-support, harvesting, and product-related tasks, whereas men are still more commonly linked to machinery operation, irrigation management, and other field activities involving heavier physical work. Some interviewees also reported differences in wage conditions and access to leadership or representative roles, with women still less visible in technical and decision-making positions within the local agri-food system. Stakeholders also emphasized that capacity-building and “operational translation” of opportunities (calls, incentives, technical pathways) are critical to avoid concentrating the costs and risks of innovation on individual farmers, an issue that can indirectly reinforce existing inequalities. These elements provide an initial qualitative baseline for gender mainstreaming in Torre Guaceto and will be further refined through the project’s structured interviews and stakeholder profiling activities.

4.2.3 Economic activities and territorial specialization

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The local economy around Torre Guaceto reflects a typical Mediterranean coastal Nexus: irrigated agriculture in the low-lying plain and peri-wetland belt, tourism concentrated along the coast, and marine-related activities linked to the protected area (professional and recreational uses). Agriculture remains a key territorial specialization, but the structural evolution of the sector shows a long-term reorganization of the farming system. According to the ISTAT Agricultural Census, the number of agricultural holdings has markedly decreased over time (Table 8), indicating consolidation processes and changes in farm structure typical of Mediterranean rural areas.

Table 8. Number of farms compared between 1990, 2000, and 2020 (Source: ISTAT Agricultural Census).

Territory	Farms 1990	Farms 2000	Farms 2020	Absolute change 2000-2020	Percentage change 2000-2020
Brindisi (Municipality)	3.689	4.355	1.595	-2.760	-63%
Carovigno	2.556	2.307	2.336	29	1%
Mesagne	3.173	1.942	1.429	-513	-26%
Ostuni	6.320	6.475	3.143	-3.332	-51%
San Vito dei Normanni	2.050	2.539	1.756	-783	-31%
Brindisi (Province)	48.960	51.171	29.252	-21.919	-43
Puglia	350.604	354.720	194.497	-160.223	-45

At the same time, crop specialization is strongly driven by permanent crops: the area shows a clear dominance of olive groves and vineyards, with municipality-level statistics confirming the relevance of these two sectors (Table 9).

Table 9. Agricultural land and farms for woody crops, vines, and olive trees 2020 (Source: ISTAT Agricultural Census).

Territory	Woody crop areas	Woody crop farms	Vineyard area	Vineyard farms	Olive grove area	Olive grove farms
Brindisi (Municipality)	3.803	1.180	1.414	342	2.168	1.019
Carovigno	4.814	2.295	29	76	4.862	2.290
Mesagne	3.265	1.321	408	238	2.557	1.284
Ostuni	8.122	3.060	132	238	7.643	3.063
San Vito dei Normanni	4.017	1.739	61	65	3.795	1.732
Brindisi (Province)	78.294	28.134	8.888	3.777	67.161	27.648
Apulia Region	497.832	173.354	96.971	36.562	351.980	163.508
Italy	2.181.367	810.777	629.517	255.514	985.481	619.375

In addition to permanent crops, horticultural production (notably artichoke and tomato) represents an important component of local farming systems and is often associated with seasonal irrigation demand. Irrigation is largely dependent on groundwater abstraction and, in recent years, the system has faced compounding stresses from groundwater salinization and climate variability; moreover, the *Xylella fastidiosa* outbreak has accelerated land-use change pressures in olive-dominated landscapes, with implications for both agricultural income and landscape management.

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Tourism and recreational uses generate relevant local income and visibility for the area, but also create seasonal demand peaks and trade-offs with environmental objectives; dedicated socio-economic investigations connected to protected-area management further document the importance of tourism/recreation and fisheries-related uses in the broader Torre Guaceto socio-economic system (eFrame, 2023).

4.3 Land use and infrastructures

The Torre Guaceto Living Lab presents a coastal–rural land-use mosaic shaped by Mediterranean climatic constraints, the presence of a protected wetland–dune system, and a long-established agricultural specialization in permanent crops and irrigated horticulture.

Land use is dominated by agricultural areas in the hinterland surrounding the Reserve, interspersed with natural and semi-natural habitats (Mediterranean scrub, coastal dunes, wetlands) within the protected area. The agricultural system has undergone long-term structural changes, with a marked reduction in the number of farms over time (see Table 8), while agricultural land remains a defining component of the territorial identity and local economy. Crop specialization is strongly oriented toward permanent crops: municipality-level statistics confirm the relevance of olive groves and vineyards (Table 9), while irrigated horticulture (notably artichoke and tomato) contributes significantly to seasonal water demand and farm income.

From an infrastructure perspective, the area is characterized by a strong dependence on groundwater abstraction through on-farm wells, which supports irrigation but also amplifies pressures on the coastal aquifer already vulnerable to salinization. The Canale Reale represents the main surface-water feature of the catchment and plays a role in the hydro-ecological functioning of the system; in the wider basin, treated effluents contribute to sustaining low flows and to recharge dynamics through transmission losses, highlighting the relevance of managed surface–groundwater interactions in a water-limited context (Portoghese et al. 2022). A key infrastructural and management opportunity for the pilot is the ongoing discussion on integrating reclaimed wastewater as an additional irrigation resource (linked to the Bufalaria WWTP), explicitly framed within the Management Plan revision and Action Programme as a strategy to reduce pressure on brackish groundwater and support adaptive management through improved monitoring and efficient irrigation practices.

Urban settlements are concentrated in nearby municipal centers (e.g., Carovigno and Brindisi), while the coastal fringe hosts tourism-related infrastructures (access points, beaches, visitor facilities) closely regulated by protected-area governance. The combination of intensive seasonal irrigation, protected habitats, and coastal tourism produces a complex land–water management setting where infrastructures and land-use decisions directly affect both agricultural viability and conservation targets, making Torre Guaceto an appropriate context for integrated WEF E Nexus interventions.

4.4 Unlocking opportunities for NexusLabs solutions

The Torre Guaceto Living Lab is characterized by strong WEF E interdependencies, where irrigated

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agriculture operates in proximity to a coastal wetland system and a marine protected area. This setting generates a clear set of interconnected challenges but also a high potential for demonstrating integrated solutions. The primary constraint is water: irrigation relies predominantly on groundwater pumping from a coastal aquifer that is intrinsically vulnerable to salinization, and where prolonged dry summers, high evapotranspiration and recurrent drought conditions intensify abstraction pressures and reduce the resilience of both farming systems and protected ecosystems. Water quality is a parallel concern, as salinity is the dominant limitation for agricultural use and wetland functioning; recent studies in the area highlight interacting drivers (pumping-induced upconing/seawater intrusion, salt recycling from irrigation with brackish groundwater, marine aerosol deposition) that reinforce a soil–water salinity feedback loop. Soil-related challenges are therefore tightly coupled with water management: repeated use of brackish groundwater and high evaporative demand promote salt accumulation in the root zone, potentially affecting soil structure and infiltration, and ultimately increasing vulnerability to drought and productivity losses. In this context, Torre Guaceto offers a valuable testing ground for pragmatic pathways that combine alternative water sources, efficient irrigation strategies and locally adapted NbS, while operating under the constraints and opportunities provided by protected-area governance and ongoing management planning.

3.4.1 NbSs and Smart Tools Currently Implemented

Several NbSs and agroecological practices are already present in the Torre Guaceto system, implemented either at farm level (autonomous adoption) or under the Reserve management actions. Examples of farm-level practices include cover cropping/vegetated inter-rows in vineyards and crop rotations/diversification in horticultural systems, while individual organic farms have introduced site-specific regenerative approaches (e.g., permaculture-inspired management). At the protected-area level, the Management Consortium has implemented ecosystem restoration measures such as wetland restoration actions (e.g., new wetland cell/management interventions) and vegetation restoration/reforestation on coastal slopes, accompanied by biodiversity monitoring and periodic reporting. These existing measures provide a baseline of “already active” NbS that can be built upon and better connected to irrigation efficiency and salinity mitigation objectives within the WEFÉ nexus.

3.4.2 NbSs and Tool Implementation in the LL

Within NexusLabs, Torre Guaceto will focus on realistic, outcome-oriented innovations aligned with the ongoing revision of the Reserve Management Plan and its Action Programme, which prioritizes strategies to reduce pressure on brackish groundwater and mitigate salinization trends. In particular, the pilot will explore the integration of reclaimed wastewater (Bufalaria WWTP) into irrigation supply, together with operational and agronomic measures to improve water-use efficiency. Complementary actions will include the consolidation and scaling of farm-level soil-regenerative practices that support soil structure and water retention (e.g., cover crops and crop rotations where feasible), and participatory processes to co-design feasible implementation pathways and scenario exploration under different climatic and operational conditions. In addition, synergies can be established with UNIVERSWATER, a parallel project in which an IRSA-CNR team is involved, whose data collection and analyses in Torre Guaceto provide complementary evidence on irrigation practices, crop water requirements and efficiency-oriented

management options; where relevant, such evidence can support baseline refinement and scenario testing without overlapping with NexusLabs implementation commitments.

3.4.3 Description of experimental demo sites

The experimental demo site for the Torre Guaceto Living Lab is located within the Torre Guaceto Irrigation District and is hosted by a long-established farm (starting year 1950) situated in the reclaimed/coastal agricultural belt close to the protected area (approx. 40.6950 N, 17.7821 E). The farm covers approximately 221.6 ha, with about 211 ha cultivated under a mixed system combining annual irrigated horticulture and permanent crops. The demo site cultivates three representative crop systems that capture the core local WEFÉ pressures: artichoke fields (around 35 ha) as the main irrigated winter vegetable, wine-grape vineyards (around 35.09 ha, irrigated), and traditional olive groves (around 14.10 ha; typically, rainfed/supplemental irrigation). These cropping systems are representative of the Torre Guaceto agroecosystem and its current vulnerabilities, where irrigation relies on groundwater abstraction via on-farm wells and is increasingly challenged by drought, high pumping energy costs, and salinity risks.

Baseline management is predominantly conventional. In the artichoke system, crop sequences and field books document rotation patterns and intensive summer–autumn operations including ploughing/secondary tillage, transplanting (July–August), and repeated irrigation/fertigation events typically extending from late July to mid-November. Irrigation is delivered through drip systems supplied by the on-farm well, with representative irrigation events (e.g., 25/07, 08/08, 21/08, 28/09, 18/10, 10/11) and seasonal application in the order of around 160–180 mm ($\approx 1,600$ – $1,800$ m³/ha), resulting in an indicative total of around 56,000–63,000 m³ for 35 ha in a season. The same irrigated groundwater source supports vineyards and (when applied) olive irrigation. Farm-level evidence also highlights the energy–water coupling, with high pumping requirements (installed power reported at around 37.5 kW) and costs linked to groundwater abstraction. Within the vineyard system, management records indicate cordon training and frequent disease control (notably downy and powdery mildew) and weed control, with multiple fungicide applications during the growing season (typically April–August) and herbicide use under rows; in the artichoke system, the phytosanitary programme is concentrated in the summer–autumn window (July–November), reflecting both weed pressure and disease/pest dynamics.

The demo site provides a robust, policy-relevant baseline for NexusLabs because it combines: (i) high water-demand cropping (artichoke) and salinity-sensitive crops (vineyards); (ii) clear documentation of operational practices through farm registers; and (iii) direct exposure to Torre Guaceto’s key coupled pressures (water scarcity/salinization, soil structure risks under frequent tillage, and rising energy costs).

4.5 Data sources and methodology

A wide variety of data sources were screened to establish a baseline understanding of the Torre Guaceto pilot across the main WEFÉ components (Climate, Crops, Demography, Economy, Energy, Geo, Land Use, Water, Soil, and Management and Policy). The resulting WP3 Database organizes the datasets collected for the pilot by data category, specifying for each item the intended scale and format (e.g., time series vs. spatial layers), the scope and key methodological notes, as well as data availability and the

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partner/source providing the information (Table 10).

In several categories, the database also records current gaps where data are not yet available at the pilot scale (e.g., quantitative energy consumption for agriculture, detailed water-demand disaggregation among uses, soil classification layers), which will inform prioritization of additional data collection or the use of proxies and scenario assumptions during subsequent modelling and assessment activities.

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Table 10. Data sources and methodology for the Torre Guaceto pilot (from WP3 database)

CATEGORY	Data needed	Specifications (Ideal/Estimated) e.g. Timescale, location/area, spatially distributed etc.	Comments	Availability flag if data are available	Provided by Partner who provides the data
Clima	Hydrometeorological data	daily and annual precipitation, radiation, temperature, wind speed, humidity, precipitation record, temperature record etc.	incl. historical variability	<input type="checkbox"/>	Weather station available in another project
	Climate change/variability and sinks.	Water and Climate	incl. sinks (atmosphere, outflows to sea, percolation to groundwater)etc	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Crop	Crop types and features	List of crops produced in the pilot area (types, varieties, yields, area cropped)		<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Crop prices	List of crops produced in the pilot area and their prices (time series)		<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Crop types and their practices (primarily irrigation)	Shapfile and text for crops and practices (irrigation pattern), text info	LPIS	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Irrigation water requirements and cost	(m3/ha, Kwh, €/ha)		<input type="checkbox"/>	
Demo	Demographic data at the pilot scale	Population and distribution - age, gender...		<input type="checkbox"/>	Report from eFrame srl
	Social characterization of the pilot area	Reports, official plans		<input type="checkbox"/>	Report from eFrame srl
Economy	Territorial economic data	N., type and size (production, turnover, n. of employees) of water-demanding economic activities.		<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Management costs	Agriculture management practices (including irrigation) and their unit costs (e.g. per ha or per crop production unit e.g. kg)		<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Energy prices	Energy prices (Euro/KWh)		<input type="checkbox"/>	Data extrapolated by farm bills
Energy	Energy consumption for agriculture		e.g. for pumping and irrigation	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Current primary energy sources	(oil, biomass, gas, coal, nuclear, renewables etc)		<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Energy allocation	(e.g. % eolic, % hydroelectric)		<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Primary energy sources requiring water	(power plants, hydroelectric, etc.)		<input type="checkbox"/>	
Geo	Cartography study area and pilots (cadaster, water management unit,...)	Shapefile	shapefile georeferenced	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sharepoint NexusLabs
	Rivers and lake bodies	Shapefile, river flow records, levels etc		<input type="checkbox"/>	Contratto di Fiume
Land Use	Land Use/Cover data and its dynamic changes	Shapefile or raster data	RS data Classification + LPIs + CLC	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sharepoint NexusLabs
	Land use maps definition (period of time, spatial scale, and legend)	Land use map (crops and forest)		<input type="checkbox"/>	Sharepoint NexusLabs
	Records of natural disasters (floods, fires, erosion, etc)	Shapefile or raster data (e.g. flood zones. historical data etc)	Copernicus, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Future land use/ land use change scenarios			<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Demand for natural resources - water and land (current and future)	Text/Statistics (geospatial data if possible)		<input type="checkbox"/>	

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Water	Renewable (surface and groundwater) water sources and stocks		<input type="checkbox"/>		
	Water demand per land use type/class	Shapefile or data records	<input type="checkbox"/>		
	Water demand and its distribution among uses (for potable use, irrigation/agriculture, industry),	Text/Statistics	spatially distributed/historical when possible	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Description of water management (irrigation systems, policy, assignment of volumes,...)			<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Desalination			<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Treated water			<input type="checkbox"/>	Local wastewater municipal treatment plant
	Water footprint		if already available	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Soil	Soil types and/or hydrologic groups	Shapefile or raster data	<input type="checkbox"/>		
	Soil map types (classification of soils)		<input type="checkbox"/>		
Management and Policy	Relevant local/regional/national planning documents and/or regulations	Reports/docs	<input type="checkbox"/>	Natural Reserve Management Plan	
	Relevant international regulations	Regulations	<input type="checkbox"/>		
	List of key stakeholders		<input type="checkbox"/>	WP1	
	Main WEFE challenges at the pilot scale	Reports, official plans, previous studies	<input type="checkbox"/>	WP2	
	New or under consultation action plans/strategies for WEFE management	Text (geospatial data if possible)	<input type="checkbox"/>	New Natural Reserve Management Plan	
	Potential funding sources for NEXUS relevant solutions (green deal, Interreg, etc)	Reports, official plans	<input type="checkbox"/>		
	Scenarios of interest in the pilot area		<input type="checkbox"/>	Wastewater reuse policy combined with grou	

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5. Baseline description of Veneto Region LL (Italy)

5.1 Geographic and environmental context

Veneto region is largest Italian pilot site. Located in the Northeast of Italy, Veneto covers an area of 18,390 km² stretching from the Eastern Alps in the north to the Adriatic Sea in the south. The region is characterized by multifaced landscapes that include mountainous areas, foothills, the Padana alluvial plain, and coastal zones hosting lagoon areas (Figure 11).

Administratively, the Veneto Region is divided into the provinces of Venice, Verona, Padua, Vicenza, Treviso, Belluno, and Rovigo. Major urban and economic centers include Venice, the regional capital and a UNESCO World Heritage Site, as well as Verona, Padua, and Vicenza, which play an important role in the regional industrial, agricultural, and service sectors. The territory also includes environmentally significant areas such as the Dolomites mountain system in the Northern part of the region and the Venice Lagoon along the Adriatic coast, both of which represent key ecological and hydrological systems.

Figure 11. Veneto Living Lab.

Agriculture represents a key economic, territorial, and cultural component of Veneto, one of the most productive farming areas in Northern Italy. The agricultural sector is characterized by a highly diversified production structure, including wine, cereals, fruit and vegetables.

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A significant share of agricultural outputs, especially wines, is marked under quality schemes such as protected designation of origin (PDO) and protected geographical indication (PGI).

The total agricultural area amounts to about 900,000 hectares (ha), of which roughly 600,000 ha are equipped with irrigation infrastructure and are therefore considered irrigable. Regarding the irrigable area, a distinction can be made between areas with structured irrigation systems, covering about 200,000 ha, mainly located in the foothill zone and areas relying on non-structured irrigation or supplementary irrigation.

Overall, Veneto represents a complex socio-ecological system where mountainous water sources, lowland agricultural production, and coastal ecosystems are strongly interconnected, making it a particularly relevant case study for integrated water-energy-food-ecosystem (WEFE) Nexus analyses.

5.1.1 Climate

The climate is predominantly humid temperate, with marked spatial variability due to diverse topography. Mountain areas experience colder temperatures and high precipitation regimes, contributing significantly to regional water availability through snowmelt-fed rivers. The central and southern plains are characterized by hot summers, relatively cold winters, and annual precipitation generally between 700 and 1,100 mm, mainly concentrated in spring and autumn.

Climate change is already occurring in the region. The increase in the mean annual temperatures (+0.57 per decade) reflects on warmer winters and hotter summers as well as on an increase in extreme events frequency and intensity (Regione del Veneto, 2024a). Future climate projections also show an increment in droughts and flood hazards, though not uniformly distributed across the regional territory (Fig. 12). Water bodies and the agricultural sector results among the most exposed elements to climate change effects and are characterized by a medium relative risk index for both hazards (i.e., droughts and floods) in all Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs) scenarios (Regione del Veneto, 2024b). Indeed, fluctuations in temperatures and precipitation have a high impact on crop irrigation needs, crop quality, and yields (Figure12).

Figure 12. a. Spatial distribution of the normalized anomaly of the Consecutive Dry Days (CDD) index in summer over the Veneto Region for the time horizons 2021–2050 (left panel) and 2071–2100 (right panel), under the emission scenarios RCP2.6, RCP4.5, and RCP8.5, relative to the reference period 1976–2005; b. Spatial distribution of the precipitation events over the 95th percentile (R95p) index anomaly in autumn over the Veneto Region for the time horizons 2021–2050 (left panel) and 2071–2100 (right panel), under the emission scenarios RCP2.6, RCP4.5, and RCP8.5, relative to the reference period 1976–2005. Source: Regione del Veneto (2024)

4.1.2 Soil

Soils in the LL reflect the strong geomorphological variability of the territory. Alpine and pre-Alpine areas are mainly characterized by shallow, coarse-textured soils with limited suitability to agriculture, while the central and southern plains are dominated by deep alluvial soils formed of fluvial deposits from major rivers such as the Adige, Brenta, and Piave rivers. These lowland soils are generally fertile, with good water retention capacity and high agricultural productivity, which have historically supported intensive agriculture development.

However, soil quality in the alluvial plain is subject to several environmental pressures. Agricultural intensification, long-term use of fertilizers and pesticides, and livestock production have contributed to localized soil and groundwater pollution, particularly by nitrates. In addition, industrial activities and urban settlements have generated areas affected by heavy metals and other pollutants, especially in peri-urban zones.

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Soil degradation and consumption (referring to soil sealing) represent another major issue in Veneto, which is among the Italian regions with the highest levels of soil sealing. Veneto ranks second among Italian regions in terms of relative soil consumption (11.86%) i.e., as a percentage of land consumption over the total regional surface area. This figure is mainly due to urban and industrial expansion. The areas with higher % soil consumption are located in Figure 13 (13)

Figure 13. Total soil consumption in Veneto municipalities (2024), as a percentage of municipal areas, excluding water bodies. Source: ARPAV, 2024

Soil degradation and consumption also had a negative impact on soil-related ecosystem services, reducing soil capability for agroforestry and agricultural uses, soil permeability that directly influences the hydrological cycle regulating surface runoff and soil natural water retention capacity that in turn affects multiple ecosystem services, including water cycle and microclimate regulation, food production, the transport of nutrients, pollutants, and sediments, as well as groundwater recharge (ARPAV, 2021).

In the coastal areas, soil salinity is becoming an increasingly serious issue for agricultural land. The situation is exacerbated by two local factors: land subsidence, and drought, which further reduces freshwater availability, facilitating the inland advancement of saline water.

4.1.3 Water

Water availability is largely sustained by Alpine-fed rivers, including the Adige, Brenta, Piave, Livenza and Tagliamento together with aquifers in the high plain and resurgence zone (locally “risorgive” area) that constitute a major source of drinking water supply. At river basin level, the management of water

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resources falls within the jurisdiction of the Eastern Alps District Basin Authority and the Po River District Basin Authority. These authorities perform coordination and planning functions within their respective river basins, being responsible for mitigating flood and landslide risks; ensuring water quality for citizens, agriculture, industry, and natural ecosystems; assessing the water balance; and coordinating the management of water scarcity events.

Besides hosting surface and groundwater water sources, the pilot site is characterized by a dense and extensive network of 18,000 km of water canals managed by ten Water Users Associations (WUAs) (Figure 14) and developed for irrigation, drainage, and flood protection. About 8,000 km of these (44%) are primarily if not solely aimed at supplying water for food and feed crops. Water is conveyed from major basins such as Adige, Brenta, Piave and Po rivers and distributed to the territory and fields. The irrigated area amounts to roughly 600,000 ha and is divided in 137 irrigation districts that are supplied through one or more intake points—around 800 in total across the region—connected to the water canal main distribution network. Irrigated areas can be divided into two categories: structured irrigation areas, covering about 200,000 ha mainly located in the foothill zones, and non-structured irrigation areas, where water distribution relies on more dispersed or less formalized systems. In the areas served by structured irrigation systems, approximately 54% of the irrigated land is supplied through sprinkler irrigation, while about 36% relies on surface (furrow or gravity) methods. Lateral infiltration accounts for roughly 7.6%, whereas submersion and localized (i.e., drip) irrigation remain marginal, each slightly above 1%. When considering the entire irrigated territory—without distinguishing between structured irrigation and supplementary/emergency irrigation—sprinkler irrigation is by far the most widespread method, covering about 73% of the area.

Figure 14. Living Lab with WUAs administrative limits and the irrigation canals infrastructure. Source: UNIPD elaboration based on Regione Veneto data.

Despite the overall abundance of surface and groundwater resources, water availability in Veneto is increasingly affected by climate change and a growing demand by multiple users. In recent decades the region has experienced more frequent drought periods due to decreased precipitation and reduced snow accumulation in the Alpine catchments. This, combined with declining groundwater levels mainly due to

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overexploitation, reflects broader climate change trends and increasing pressure on water resources. Irrigation represents one of the main water uses, particularly during summer when precipitation combined with prolonged dry spells are often insufficient to meet crop requirements.

Water quality also represents a critical issue in some areas of the region, where diffused pollution from the agricultural sectors such as nitrate and industrial pollutants such as Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) have affected both groundwater and surface waters.

These pressures, combined with competing demands among agriculture, urban supply, industry, and ecosystems, make integrated water resource management a strategic priority for ensuring long-term water security and environmental sustainability in the Veneto Region.

5.1.4 Energy

Energy production relies on a diversified mix of conventional and renewable sources, reflecting both geographical characteristics and the highly industrialized economy of the area. Electricity generation includes thermoelectric power plants fueled mainly by natural gas, which historically represent a major share of regional production (49.8% over total energy production), alongside a growing contribution from renewable energy sources (50%), mainly hydropower and photovoltaic. (Figure 15).

Figure 15. Renewable energy contribution to electricity generation in Veneto Region in 2024. Source: UNIPD elaboration based on Terna data, 2024)

Hydropower plays an important role in the Northern mountainous areas, where Alpine rivers and reservoirs support a network of hydroelectric plants that contribute significantly to renewable electricity generation. In the lowland areas, photovoltaic installations have expanded rapidly in recent years, both as large-scale plants and distributed rooftop systems in urban, industrial, and agricultural settings.

Biomass and biogas production, often linked to agricultural residues, livestock waste, and agro-industrial by-products, also contribute to the regional renewable energy portfolio.

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Energy consumption is strongly driven by industrial activities, which account for 50.6% of the total regional consumption. The dense urban settlements also largely contribute to energy consumption with domestic and service use. Agricultural production, including irrigation and intensive processing systems, accounts for 2.7% of the total consumption (Figure 16). The ongoing regional energy transition aims to increase the share of renewables, improve energy efficiency, and reduce greenhouse gas emissions, while ensuring system reliability and energy security. The interconnections between water availability, agricultural production, and bioenergy generation further highlight the importance of integrated resource management within the WEFE Nexus.

Figure 16. Energy consumption (GWh) by sector in 2023 in the pilot site. Source: UNIPD elaboration based on the Terna data, 2023)

5.2 Socio-economic characteristics

5.2.1 Demographic profile

Veneto is one of the most populated areas in northern Italy, with a total population of 4,853,472 in 2025 (ISTAT, 2025). Population is densely concentrated within provincial capitals—including Venice, Verona, Padua, Vicenza, and Treviso (Figure 17)—connected by a dense infrastructure network and characterized by the presence of industrial districts. In addition to major urban centers, small and medium-sized municipalities contribute to a relatively dispersed urbanization pattern, particularly in the central plain where most of the agricultural activities are located. Rural and mountain areas - particularly in the province of Belluno and in marginal inland municipalities - have experienced long-term population decline mainly driven by outmigration of young toward urban areas. Population decline in rural and mountainous areas is only partly mitigated by immigration flows and is often accompanied by the loss or downsizing of essential services, including healthcare facilities, schools, public transport, and local commercial activities. The reduction in service accessibility further weakens the socio-economic resilience of these territories, creating a feedback loop that reinforces outmigration.

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Figure 17. Population distribution by province in 2025. Source: UNIPD elaboration on ISTAT data (2025).

In recent decades, the region has experienced demographic aging, with an increasing share of elderly population and low birth rates, in line with broader national trends. In 2025, the mean age in the region is 47.1 (ISTAT, 2025) (Figure 18).

Figure 18. Mean age in the Living Lab. Source: UNIPD elaboration on ISTAT data (2025).

At the same time, international migration has partially offset population decline and has contributed to the regional labor force, particularly in agriculture, manufacturing, and services.

5.2.2 Gender mainstreaming

The gender distribution in Veneto Region is balanced, with women representing a slight majority of the total population (women 50,7%; men 49,3%). Despite the relatively balanced population structure, gender disparities persist particularly in labour force participation. Indeed, female participation in the Veneto labour market remains among the lowest in Europe. In 2023, the labour force participation rate for women aged 15–64 was 66.3%, significantly below that of comparable European regions and 14.5% lower than the corresponding male rate (Regione del Veneto, 2025). In agriculture, male farm ownership and management is still predominant, although female involvement is on the rise with more than 12,000 female-owned agricultural enterprises registered in the Living Lab, accounting for 25% of the total (CIA; ISMEA, 2024).

5.2.3 Economic activities and territorial specialization

Veneto is one of the most economically dynamic areas in Italy, characterized by a diversified production system and a strongly export-oriented economy. The regional economic structure is traditionally based on a dense network of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), often organized in industrial districts specialized in manufacturing sectors. Another relevant sector is tourism and related services that contribute substantially to the regional economy (Table 11).

Table 11. Number of activities in Veneto grouped by sectors in 2025, Source: Regione Veneto based on data InfoCamere

Sectors	Active companies (n.)	% respect total
<i>Agriculture</i>	59.568	14.38%
<i>Mining</i>	184	0.04%
<i>Manufacturing</i>	45.168	10,91%
<i>Utilities and environmental services</i>	1.659	0.40%
<i>Construction</i>	60.311	14.56%
<i>Wholesale and retail</i>	85.786	20,72%
<i>Transportation</i>	11.718	2.83%
<i>Accommodation and food service activities</i>	28.914	6,98%
<i>It</i>	9.729	2.35%
<i>Financial services</i>	13.097	3.16%
<i>Real estate</i>	32.531	7.86%
<i>Arts, entertainment and recreation</i>	4.909	1.19%
<i>Service activities</i>	35.261	8.51%
<i>Education</i>	2.460	0.59%
<i>Healthcare</i>	2.788	0.67%
<i>Other services activities</i>	19.640	4.74%
<i>Unclassified</i>	361	0.09%
Total	414.085	

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Agriculture remains a key sector, with high-value productions including viticulture, horticulture, fruit cultivation, and livestock farming, often integrated with processing industries and quality certification schemes. The Living Lab is characterized by a strong presence of protected designation of origin (PDO) and protected geographical indication (PGI) labels with 53 labels for wines and 36 for agri-food products (CREA, 2024).

5.3 Land use and infrastructures

The pilot is characterized by very heterogeneous land use patterns that reflect its diverse geomorphological structure and its strong economic development. Urban and peri-urban areas are concentrated along the central plain, where a dense network of settlements and industrial districts has progressively expanded over recent decades. The Central and Southern plains are predominantly characterized by agricultural land, including arable crops, vineyards, orchards, and horticultural systems, while mountainous areas in the Northern and Western part of the region are mainly covered by forests, grasslands, and natural or semi-natural ecosystems.

The total agricultural area makes up about 49% of the total regional territory. Arable crops cover approximately 558,000 ha, with the largest share devoted to cereals for grain production (53.2%). Permanent tree crops are also widespread, with vineyards accounting for 77.4% of the total area, followed by fresh fruit orchards (13.5%) (ISTAT, 2024) (Table 12).

Water-related infrastructure plays a fundamental role. The dense network of irrigation canals (18.000 km) support agricultural production while drainage systems serve as hydrogeological protection of the territory. In addition, reservoirs and dams contribute to both hydropower electricity generation and to downstream water management.

Table 12. Farms with Utilized Agricultural Area (UAA) by type of crop. Source: ISTAT 6th agriculture census, 2020

Crop type	UAA - ha	Farms - UAA
Totale	808.093	81.556
Arable crops	557.987	64.388
<i>Cereals</i>	295.663	39.514
<i>Legumes</i>	5.407	1.473
<i>Potatoes</i>	2.953	1.570
<i>Greenhouse arable crops</i>	2.567	2.124
<i>Sugar beet</i>	9.570	1.159
<i>Fodder root crops</i>	531	238
<i>Industrial crops</i>	122.183	21.963
<i>Vegetables</i>	14.051	5.374
<i>Flowers and ornamental plants</i>	262	401
<i>Temporary forage crops</i>	87.427	18.481
<i>Seeds and seedlings</i>	1.071	249
<i>Fallow land</i>	13.089	8.004
<i>Other arable crops</i>	3.247	1.641
Permanent crops	128.770	33.726

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<i>Citrus</i>	67	50
<i>Vineyards</i>	100.939	26.773
<i>Olive trees</i>	4.365	5.665
<i>Fruit</i>	19.909	8.582
<i>Nursery</i>	3.064	1.084
<i>Other permanent crops</i>	409	380
<i>Greenhouse permanent crops</i>	16	35
<i>Kitchen gardens</i>	797	13.551
<i>Permanent grassland and pastures</i>	120.504	13.415

5.4 Unlocking opportunities for NexusLabs solutions

Veneto represents the largest-scale Living Lab within the project framework, providing the ground for replication and upscaling of WEFE solutions developed and tested at local scale. Owing to its territorial complexity, economic diversification, and high pressure on natural resources, Veneto offers a strategic context for assessing the feasibility, scalability, and transferability of integrated WEFE Nexus innovations and Nature-based Solutions (NbSs).

Water management represents a central challenge. Although Veneto has historically benefited from relatively abundant water resources sustained by snow reserves, increasing climate variability, reduced snowpack accumulation, and more frequent drought events are affecting water availability. Irrigation demand during summer months places significant pressure on surface water bodies and aquifers, while competition among productive sectors and ecosystems intensifies during dry periods. Water quality concerns, including nitrate pollution from agriculture and PFAS contamination in specific areas, further complicate water resource management and governance.

Soil degradation is another pressure observed in the region. Intensive farming practices in parts of the plain contribute to soil compaction, erosion, and organic matter decline, while urban expansion and infrastructure development have led to significant soil sealing and landscape fragmentation.

These dynamics reduce ecosystem service provision and increase hydrogeological risks, reinforcing the need for site-specific soil management strategies. Also, increased soil salinity in the coastal areas represents a significant threat for agricultural production. In terms of **energy**, the large share of electricity produced from hydropower, increases the interdependencies between the energy sector and water management and highlight the relevance of integrated planning across WEFE Nexus.

The highly interconnected mosaic of alpine, lowland, riverine, and coastal **ecosystems** that provide essential ecosystem services to society and the regional economy is progressively affected by multiple and interacting pressures.

The complex and multifaceted socio-ecological dynamics make Veneto a regional-scale laboratory

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particularly suitable for testing integrated resource management strategies under different environmental and socio-economic conditions and enabling the validation and scaling-up of solutions.

5.4.1 NbSs and Smart Tools Currently Implemented

Different NbSs have already been implemented in Veneto, particularly for water management and climate change adaptation.

Forested Infiltration Areas (FIAs) are a successful example for the pilot site. FIA are forest areas aimed to recharge aquifers by channeling surface waters during times of excess into designated areas that have been planted with various species of trees and/or shrubs. This NbS originated from experimental initiatives developed within the Living Lab itself to cope with two major problems. First, the decreasing aquifers' level and the consequent disappearance of wetlands and springs. Second, water quality degradation due to the impacts of agriculture activities (e.g. fertilization). Besides the groundwater recharge function, FIAs favor water purification and add significant naturalistic value for the local ecological network, while providing ecosystem services such as biomass production and carbon sequestration and storage. With an extension of 2.5 hectares, Bosco Limite (in Carmignano di Brenta, Padua) is the largest FIA within Veneto region. It has been developed on private land which was previously used to grow maize (Figure 19).

Figure 19. Bosco Limite in Carmignano di Brenta. Credits: Etifor

WUAs have shown strong commitment to environmental issues and, over time, have promoted and implemented several NbSs. The adoption of NbS interventions such as drainage and irrigation channels and watercourses allows the combination of hydraulic safety and ecological protection, contributing to improved water quality, bank stabilization, and enhanced biodiversity. A relevant example is the so-called “Piano laghetti” (i.e. Small Reservoirs Plan) aimed at creating reservoirs and retention basins distributed across the regional territory, including the reuse of abandoned quarries, to store water and make it available during the irrigation season and in drought periods.

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Supported by the Rural Development Program, numerous farmers in Veneto have adopted sustainable farming practices and NbSs to enhance soil health, improve water retention, and strengthen crop yields and quality. NbSs include cover cropping, crop rotation, mulching, green manure and agroforestry.

5.4.2 NbSs and Tool Implementation in the LL

Veneto pilot site will serve as a living laboratory for upscaling NexusLabs Tools and NbS. Within the framework of water management, water accounting and water footprint together with HIDROmore will be considered for implementation in specific demo sites. Moreover, NbS for increasing water retention and water storage.

For soil management, different NbS such as green manure, mulching, reduced tillage, and crop rotation practices will be proposed to selected demo sites with the aim of improving soil quality, enhancing soil fertility, and improving microbial activity.

Alongside tools and NbSs, innovative policy and governance frameworks for resource and WEFE management will also be considered, together with the WEFE audit and the assessment of WEFE conditions through the application of WEFE indicators (WP4). To strengthen stakeholder engagement and foster participatory knowledge co-creation, dedicated training sessions will be organized for farmers and other key stakeholders, complemented by roundtable discussions within regional meetings.

5.4.3 Description of experimental demo sites

For the Veneto pilot, the identification and selection of demo sites is currently being defined.

5.5 Data sources and methodology for baseline assessment

For the definition of a common and comprehensive baseline understanding of the pilot's current state, different components have been considered such as *Clima, Crop, Demo, Economy, Energy, Geo, Land, Use, Water, Soil, Management and Policy* (Table 13).

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Table 13. Data sources and methodology for the Veneto pilot (from WP3 database)

	DATA	Source
Clima	Hydrometeorological data	ARPA Veneto
	Climate change/variability and sinks.	ARPA Veneto
Crop	Crop types and features	Regione Veneto, Veneto Agricoltura
	Crop prices	ISMEA (2000–2025) (<i>Not all crops are included; to be integrated with the Italian database</i>), ISTAT data
	Crop types and their practices (primarily irrigation)	ISTAT Agricultural Census, SIGRIAN (National Irrigation Information System) for the year 2022, Irriframe.
	Irrigation water requirements and cost	ANBI Veneto, Irriframe
Demo	Demographic data at the pilot scale	ISTAT, Regione Veneto (Sistema statistico regionale)
	Social characterization of the Living Lab	Regione Veneto (Sistema statistico regionale)
Economy	Territorial economic data	
	Management costs	Prezziario opere forestali, 2022
	Energy prices	ARERA, Interviews
Energy	Energy consumption for agriculture	Literature review, Interviews
	Current primary energy sources	TERNA data
	Energy allocation	TERNA data
	Primary energy sources requiring water	TERNA data
Geo	Cartography study area and pilots (cadaster, water management unit, etc.)	Geoportale Regione Veneto
	Rivers and lake bodies	Geoportale Regione Veneto
	Land Use/Cover data and its dynamic changes	Geoportale Regione Veneto, Corine dataset
Land Use	Land use maps definition (period of time, spatial scale, and legend)	Geoportale Regione Veneto, Corine dataset
	Records of natural disasters (floods, fires, erosion, etc.)	Regione Veneto, ARPA Veneto
	Future land use/ land use change scenarios	N.D.
	Demand for natural resources - water and land (current and future)	N.D.
Water	Renewable (surface and groundwater) water sources and stocks	ARPA Veneto
	Water demand per land use type/class	N.D.
	Water demand and its distribution among uses (for potable use, irrigation/agriculture, industry),	ISTAT, District Basin Authority
	Description of water management (irrigation systems, policy, assignment of volumes, etc.)	Regione Veneto, ANBI Veneto
	Desalination	WUA, Literature review

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	DATA	Source
Soil	Treated water	N.D.
	Water footprint	N.D.
	Soil types and/or hydrologic groups	ARPA Veneto
	Soil map types (classification of soils)	ARPA Veneto (soil type map)
	Relevant local/regional/national planning documents and/or regulations	Piano Gestione Acque
Management and Policy	Relevant international regulations	EU Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC); EU Nitrates Directive (91/676/EEC); EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) 2023–2027; EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030.
	List of key stakeholders	Public authorities and governance bodies: Associazione dei Consorzi di Bonifica del Veneto (ANBI Veneto); Autorità di Bacino Alpi Orientali, Consiglio di Bacino Brenta, Regione Veneto (Bonifica e irrigazione). Research and education institutions: UNIPD, Il Centro Interdipartimentale di Ricerca in Viticoltura ed Enologia (CIRVE), Università di Venezia Ca' Foscari. Environmental and civil society organizations; Legambiente Veneto. Private sector and producers: Water and energy utilities, Farmers association (CIA, Coldiretti), farms owners.
	Main WEFE challenges at the pilot scale	Water management, water availability during drought periods, soil salinity, soil degradation, ecosystem deterioration
	New or under consultation action plans/strategies for WEFE management	Piano laghetti (ANBI)
	Potential funding sources for NEXUS relevant solutions (green deal, Interreg, etc.)	Horizon Europe (Cluster 6); LIFE Programme (subprogram Environment & Climate); Interreg Euro-MED; Green Deal Calls; PSR Veneto 2023–2027 Misure su gestione risorse idriche e sostenibilità. PRIMA, Private foundations funds.
	Scenarios of interest in the Living Lab	

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6. Baseline description of Koiliaris LL (Greece)

6.1 Geographic and environmental context

The Koiliaris River watershed (Figure 20), located in north-western Crete near the city of Chania, is a designated Critical Zone Observatory (CZO) and part of both the European and Greek Long-Term Ecological Research (LTER) Networks. Over the past 20 years, it has served as a key reference site for understanding Mediterranean geo-environmental processes, sustainable land and water management, and the interactions between ecological systems and human activities. Its long history of active stakeholder engagement has also established the Technical University of Crete and the Koiliaris research team as trusted local institutions and facilitators of social consensus in addressing environmental and agricultural challenges.

Covering 132 km², the watershed spans elevations from 0 to 2120 m, creating strong gradients in climate, vegetation, and land use. The climate is Mediterranean semi-arid, with most rainfall occurring in winter and long, dry summers that increase vulnerability to drought. These conditions, combined with centuries of intensive agriculture and overgrazing, have resulted in severely degraded soils that are considered at high risk of desertification and soil carbon loss under projected climate change scenarios.

The watershed's hydrology is strongly influenced by karstic geology, including limestones, dolomites, marbles, and schists. Extensive karst systems in the White Mountains feed major springs such as Stylos and Anavreti, which provide permanent and intermittent flows respectively. The drainage network includes the Koiliaris River and tributaries such as Keramianos, an intermittent stream prone to flash floods when rainfall exceeds 120 mm. Hydrologic studies using the Karst-SWAT model show that precipitation is partitioned among evapotranspiration, surface runoff, and significant groundwater contributions from the extended karst area outside the watershed boundary. The system is highly responsive during extreme events, as illustrated by the February 2019 flood, when 70% of rainfall became surface runoff within five days.

Figure 20. Schematic of regional geology, the drainage network and the monitoring network of Koiliaris CZO (Lilli et al., 2020)

Land use reflects long-standing agricultural traditions. In many parts of the basin, abandoned terraces, intensive tillage, and lack of erosion control contribute to soil degradation, while urbanized areas near springs face risks from insufficient wastewater infrastructure.

Overall, the Koiliaris watershed represents a complex Mediterranean socio-ecological system where climate pressures, karst hydrology, intensive agriculture, and institutional fragmentation converge. Its rich monitoring history, stakeholder involvement, and environmental variability make it an ideal Living Lab for testing agroecological and Nexus-based approaches that enhance soil health, promote sustainable resource use, and build resilience to climate hazards.

6.1.1 Climate

The Koiliaris LL is located in the north-western part of Crete, Greece, within a Mediterranean semi-arid climate zone. The area is characterized by:

- Hot, dry summers and mild, wet winters.
- A strong precipitation gradient driven by elevation, with mean annual precipitation around 1,430 mm.
- Marked seasonal variability, including intense winter rainfall that can trigger flash floods, and long summer droughts that create water scarcity for irrigation and ecosystems.
- Increasing pressures from climate change, including a projected decline in soil moisture and increased desertification risk, consistent with IPCC projections for the Eastern Mediterranean.

This climatic variability strongly influences hydrologic processes, agricultural practices, and water availability, particularly for emerging high-water-demand crops such as avocado.

6.1.2 Soil

Soils in the Koiliaris basin are shaped by centuries of intensive agricultural use, grazing pressure, and a complex geological substrate. Key characteristics include:

- Severely degraded soils in many parts of the watershed, primarily due to overgrazing (10–14 animals/ha vs. carrying capacity of 1–2 animals/ha) and unsustainable tillage practices.
- High vulnerability to erosion, especially on steep slopes and on abandoned terraces, which no longer retain soil effectively.
- Soil carbon depletion and increased susceptibility to desertification, a major regional threat.
- Significant variability associated with parent materials: marls, schists, limestones, dolomites, and alluvial deposits.
- In agricultural zones, heavy use of fertilizers, pesticides, and herbicides contributes to soil and water quality pressures.

Ongoing soil analyses under the Living Lab support mapping soil health indicators, and carbon storage potential.

6.1.3 Water

The Koiliaris watershed (132 km²) is a Critical Zone Observatory (CZO) with a well-studied hydrologic regime dominated by an extensive karstic system extending beyond the basin boundary.

Key hydrological features:

- Karstic springs (Stylos, Anavreti) contribute the majority of the basin's baseflow (total mean contribution: 75.4%).
- Surface runoff accounts for ~12.4% of annual rainfall; heavily concentrated during intense storm events.
- Intermittent tributaries such as Keramianos exhibit high sensitivity to extreme rainfall events; >50% of its flow is lost through karstic faults.
- Flash floods are common during high-intensity rainfall (e.g. the 25 Feb 2019 event, where >5 million m³ of water discharged in one day).
- Summer low-flow periods and droughts intensify water scarcity for irrigation.

Water use context:

- Springs of Stylos provide ~120 Mm³/yr, Armenoi ~25 Mm³/yr, while total water consumption is ~13 Mm³/yr—suggesting abundant water resources but poor water management.
- Water quality conflicts arise, notably elevated chloride concentrations affecting avocado production.

Governance is fragmented, with several institutions (Development Organization of Crete, municipalities, irrigation cooperatives) lacking coordinated management.

6.1.4 Energy

Energy use in the Koiliaris Living Lab is primarily linked to:

- Agricultural energy demands, especially for pumping irrigation water during summer months.
- Local rural settlements, where energy consumption is dominated by household use and small-scale agro-industrial activities (olive mills, greenhouses).
- No major energy production infrastructure within the watershed (e.g. hydropower, large renewables).
- Opportunities exist for improving energy efficiency in irrigation (smart scheduling, soil moisture sensors) and for integrating renewable energy systems (PV-powered pumps), but these remain largely underdeveloped.

Given the region’s climate and morphology, energy considerations are closely linked to water management, particularly in the context of drought adaptation.

6.2 Socio-economic characteristics

6.2.1 Demographic profile

The Municipality of Apokoronas (Figure 21) had a permanent resident population of 12,245 people according to the 2021 national census

(https://www.citypopulation.de/en/greece/mun/admin/kr%C3%ADti/7402__d%C3%ADmos_apokor%C3%B3nou/). This reflects a slight decline from 12,807 residents recorded in 2011. The municipality comprises 75 villages, with population concentrations in larger settlements such as Vryses (the municipal seat), as well as in coastal and valley areas where economic activities and services are more active. Seasonally, the area experiences significant population increases due to tourism, especially during spring and summer months, although these temporary residents are not counted in the census figures.

Figure 21. Total population in Municipality of Apokoronas for the years 1960-2010.

6.2.2 Gender mainstreaming

Gender distribution is nearly balanced, with 6,248 males and 6,000 females. The age structure reveals a mixed demographic profile: 1,789 children (0–14 years), 7,250 individuals of working age (15–59 years), 3,211 seniors (65+ years), indicating a modestly aging population typical of rural Mediterranean contexts.

6.2.3 Economic activities and territorial specialization

The local economy is characterized by a combination of agriculture, livestock, and tourism. Agriculture remains a primary livelihood, with major crops including olive groves (~11,037 acres), citrus orchards (~1,005 acres), vineyards (~430 acres), and annual crops (~1,414 acres). Emerging crops such as avocado are gaining economic significance due to higher market value. Livestock production includes

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sheep (85,778), goats (28,126), pigs (1,420), and other domestic animals, contributing to local dairy and meat production.

The major economic activity of the area is tourism, with the municipality providing 13,920 tourist beds in 2015 (Table 14), concentrated in coastal settlements, like Georgioupoli and Vamos. The sector strongly influences seasonal water demand, local employment, and service provision. Economic development is constrained by small farm sizes, fragmented land ownership, and limited infrastructure, highlighting the need for integrated planning across agriculture, tourism, and natural resource management.

Table 14. Tourist potential (beds) of the Municipality of Apokoronas per year

Municipal Unit	2009	2011	2015
Armenoi	1281	-	1749
Vamos	1432	-	3142
Georgioupoli	6854	-	8710
Krionerida	81	-	319
Sum	9648	11431	13920

6.3 Land use and infrastructures

Land use in the Koiliaris watershed is dominated by grazed shrubland and pastures, covering approximately 67.3% of the basin, while agricultural lands, including olive groves, citrus orchards, vineyards, vegetables, and avocado plantations occupy 32.1% of the area. Mixed forest represents only 0.6% of the basin. The total watershed area is 132 km², with altitudes ranging from 0 to 2120 m amsl and slopes varying from 1–2% in the valley to 43% at higher elevations, conditions that strongly influence cultivation practices and soil erosion. Olive groves dominate the higher elevations (11,037 acres), requiring 3,311,250 m³/year of irrigation water, while citrus orchards (1,005 acres) consume 502,850 m³/year and annual crops (1,414 acres) use 707,000 m³/year (Table 15). Emerging avocado plantations contribute to increasing irrigation demand, with the total agricultural water requirement of Municipality of Apokoronas estimated at 4,690,000 m³/year, representing two-thirds of the basin's total water demand (7,040,000 m³/year). (Figure 22) shows the changes of land uses in years 1961, 1971, 1991, 2000, 2009 and (Table 15) presents the annual water consumption per crop type.

The basin's water infrastructure relies heavily on karstic springs, including Stylos (permanent flow, 55.1% of total spring flow) and Anavreti (intermittent flow, 44.9%), supplemented by small reservoirs and irrigation networks managed locally. Surface streams and ephemeral tributaries, such as Keramianos and Anavreti, generate substantial runoff during wet periods, with up to 70% of extreme rainfall events contributing to flood flows. Transport infrastructure is concentrated in lowland areas, while steep and high-altitude zones are only partially accessible, limiting mechanized agriculture. Abandoned terraces and extensive livestock grazing (10–14 animals/ha versus the sustainable 1–2 animals/ha) exacerbate soil erosion, while small farm sizes hinder mechanization and efficient resource use. Collectively, these quantitative land use patterns and infrastructure constraints shape the environmental, hydrological, and

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agricultural dynamics of the Koiliaris watershed, emphasizing the need for integrated management strategies.

Table 15. Annual water consumption per crop type

Crop type	Water demand (m^3 /acre/year)	Area (acres)	Annual Water Consumption (m^3 /year)
Annual crops	500	1414	707000
Olive trees	300	11037	3311250
Citrus trees	500	1005	502850
Vineyards	350	430	150640
Uncultivated	50	304	15240

Figure 22. Land use evolution for the municipality of Apokoronas.

6.4 Unlocking opportunities for NbS solutions

The Koiliaris River Basin is characterized by tightly interconnected water, soil, and agricultural challenges. Water management is increasingly stressed by pronounced seasonal variability, summer droughts, and rising irrigation demands from crops. Inefficient irrigation practices, combined with strong surface - groundwater connectivity, increase pressure on groundwater resources and exacerbate water quality risks. At the same time, soil degradation is widespread, driven by long-term overgrazing, intensive tillage, abandonment of terraces, and cultivation on steep slopes, resulting in high erosion rates, reduced soil water-holding capacity, and declining soil carbon stocks. These soil conditions directly undermine agricultural productivity and increase vulnerability to both drought and extreme rainfall events.

Agricultural systems in the basin are therefore caught in a reinforcing cycle of declining soil health, increasing water demand, and heightened climate sensitivity. Fragmented land ownership, small farm sizes, and limited access to integrated advisory services further constrain the adoption of sustainable practices. Within this context, NbS and other enabling tools supporting NbS, offer a compelling pathway to simultaneously address soil restoration, water efficiency, and agricultural resilience. The Koiliaris watershed provides a favorable setting for such interventions due to its strong environmental gradients, extensive hydrological and soil monitoring, and long-standing engagement with farmers and local authorities.

3.4.1 NbSs and Smart Tools Currently Implemented

Within the Koiliaris LL, the most advanced and operational tool currently implemented relate to water efficient irrigation management in agriculture, with a particular focus on avocado plantations, an emerging high-value but water-demanding crop in the basin. The enabling tool supporting irrigation based NbS developed and tested in the area combines soil-plant-water system understanding, soil moisture monitoring, and process-based modelling to align irrigation practices with actual crop water requirements. The objective of the experiment conducted, was to determine the actual irrigation needs of the avocados by specifically focusing on individual avocado trees. An avocado plantation in the Koiliaris river basin was instrumented for this purpose. The field instrumentation consisted of NDVI and PRI cameras (for the determination of productivity), a meteorological station (to calculate ET), soil moisture probes located at different soil depths (to estimate soil water storage and percolation to ground water) and flow meters to determine the amount of irrigation. The infrastructure comprises of wireless, autonomous monitoring stations which transmit data from their attached sensors, to a remote database server for storage and analysis. The study was initiated in 2019. The field-scale experiments have applied soil moisture-driven irrigation scheduling, supported by the HYDRUS-1D model, to simulate water flow and root water uptake under local soil and climatic conditions. This approach optimizes irrigation timing and volumes by enhancing soil water retention and minimizing deep percolation losses. The results demonstrated that significant reductions in irrigation water use can be achieved without compromising crop productivity (Lilli et al., 2024). This tool operates at the farm and plot scale, is already implemented at pilot and demonstration level, and shows high potential for scaling up across the basin. Beyond water savings, the approach delivers co-benefits consistent with NbS principles, including improved soil moisture stability, reduced energy demand for pumping, and increased resilience of

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agricultural systems to drought. As such, it represents an enabling tool supporting NbSs that directly addresses key water–food nexus challenges in the Koiliaris watershed while remaining compatible with existing farming practices and infrastructure.

Local NbSs Design Under Development

A major NbS currently being designed for the Koiliaris LL focuses on restoration of the native riparian forest along the river corridor to address flood risk, erosion, and ecosystem degradation, grounded in both biophysical modelling and participatory decision-making processes. Recent research has assessed the biophysical and economic potential of restoring riparian forests along the Koiliaris River, demonstrating that re-establishing native vegetation along an expanded buffer zone can significantly increase runoff retention, enhance carbon sequestration, and improve habitat quality compared to business-as-usual conditions, while also showing economic sustainability with a payback period of roughly five years under a cost–benefit analysis (Masiero et al., 2024). Complementing this, a vision-based decision-making methodology has been developed specifically for the Koiliaris context to guide NbS design, co-design, and implementation in a way that overcomes technical, social, and institutional barriers. This approach engaged local stakeholders, including farmers, municipal authorities, regional agencies, and researchers, to build a shared vision for ecosystem restoration (Lilli et al., 2020).

3.4.2 NbS and Tool Implementation in the LL

Within the framework of NexusLabs, the Koiliaris LL will implement a set of enabling tools that support NbS, aimed at enhancing sustainable water, land, and agricultural management. The primary focus is on irrigating based on the actual needs of the plants, using smart irrigation systems that link real-time field measurements to smartphones and other digital interfaces, ensuring user-friendly operation for local farmers. Complementing the smart irrigation initiative, the LL will showcase the benefits of agroecological practices with measurements, with systematic monitoring of soil health, crop productivity, and carbon sequestration.

The vision of NexusLabs in Koiliaris includes documenting the effectiveness of these solutions through field measurements, performing cost-benefit analyses, and evaluating their potential for upscaling and wider adoption. Within the framework of Nexuslabs, at least 10% of Koiliaris CZO farms already integrated into the smart irrigation network, and this initiative aims to engage more farmers to join the network by engaging through training, exchange visits, and participatory demonstrations (Figure 23). Through the combined deployment of smart irrigation and documenting of the effectiveness of agroecological practices, the Koiliaris LL strives to become a replicable model for sustainable Mediterranean agriculture, balancing productivity, resource efficiency, and ecosystem health at the local and regional scales.

Figure 23. Phases of the methodology implemented in the Koiliaris LL.

3.4.3 Description of experimental demo sites

Figure 24. Koiliaris river basin experimental demo site.

The experimental demonstration sites of the Koiliaris LL consist of twelve agricultural fields distributed across the Koiliaris River Basin (**Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.**), selected to represent the dominant irrigated perennial cropping systems of the area, namely avocado, olive, and citrus (orange) groves (**Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.**6). These sites will serve as the primary locations for the implementation, testing, and scaling of smart irrigation systems, as well as for systematic monitoring of agroecological practices within the framework of NexusLabs.

The selected fields cover a wide range of plot sizes, from approximately 1,049 m² to 33,530 m² (Table

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16). Avocado groves dominate the experimental network, reflecting their increasing economic importance and high irrigation demand, while olive groves provide comparative systems with lower and water requirements. This diversity enables evaluation of smart irrigation performance across different crop types, water demands, and management regimes under the same climatic and hydrological conditions.

Table 16. Annual water consumption per crop type

no	Plot ID	Plot Area m ²	Land Use
1	GR-KRB-AV-001	2778	Avocado Grove
2	GR-KRB-OR-002	2103	Orange Grove
3	GR-KRB-AV-003	2300	Avocado Grove
4	GR-KRB-AV-004	1244	Avocado Grove
5	GR-KRB-AV-005	1775	Avocado Grove
6	GR-KRB-AV-006	1049	Avocado Grove
7	GR-KRB-OL-007	2390	Olive Grove
8	GR-KRB-OL-008	23246	Olive Grove
9	GR-KRB-OL-009	33530	Olive Grove
10	GR-KRB-AV-010	7500	Avocado Grove
11	GR-KRB-AV-011	4000	Avocado Grove
12	GR-KRB-OL-012	4000	Olive Grove

All demo sites will be equipped with smart irrigation infrastructure, including soil moisture sensors, and flow meters to quantify irrigation volumes. Data will be transmitted in real time to a centralized digital platform accessible to farmers via user-friendly interfaces (e.g. smartphones), supporting irrigation scheduling based on actual plant water needs. The smart irrigation system builds directly on the pilot irrigation experiment previously implemented in the basin, enabling its replication and scaling across the Koiliaris LL.

In parallel, these 12 fields will function as monitoring sites, where soil samples will be collected periodically to assess soil health, soil moisture dynamics, and carbon-related indicators. Together, the twelve demo fields constitute a representative, operational network for demonstrating the effectiveness, scalability, and co-benefits of smart irrigation and agroecological practices under Mediterranean conditions.

6.5 Data sources and methodology for baseline assessment

The Koiliaris River watershed is a Critical Zone Observatory (CZO) (www.koiliaris-czo.tuc.gr) on the island of Crete and part of the European LTER (Long Term Ecological Research) Network and the LTER-Greece Network and has been extensively studied over the past 20 years.

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Meteorological data are acquired by two meteorological stations within the basin, installed and managed by the Laboratory of Hydrogeochemical Engineering and Remediation of Soil (H.E.R.S. Lab) of the Technical University of Crete, at Samonas (380 m amsl) (M2) and Psichro Pigadi (948 m amsl) (M1) (Figure 20) (Rain gauge, Tipping Bucket Rain Gauge, DeltaOHM (GHM Group), Selvazzano Dentro, Italy). These stations have been recording precipitation and temperature data every 10 min since 2004. Also, daily precipitation data are available from three rain gauge stations managed by the Region of Crete since 1973 (Askifou at 740 m amsl (M4), Kalives at 24 m amsl (M3), and Mouri at 86 m amsl (M5)) (Figure 20) (VANTAGE PRO2, Davis Instruments, Hayward, CA, USA). The hydrologic monitoring of Kolliaris CZO has also been carried out since 2004, with the installation of the hydrometric station at Agios Georgios (R1), strategically located downstream of the confluence of Keramianos tributary with the main, permanent river that drains the Stylos (S1) and Anavreti (S5) springs, recording water level data every 10 min (Water level & Temperature logger, Level TROLL 500 Data Logger, In-Situ Inc., Fort Collins, CO, USA). H.E.R.S. Lab has also installed two hydrometric stations (Figure 20) along the Keramianos tributary, one at the gorge entrance and one at the gorge exit, monitoring water level data every 10 min since 2013 (Water level & Temperature logger, HOBO Water Level, Onset Computer Corporation, Bourne, MA, USA). Three rating curves of water level vs. flow have been developed for the three hydrometric stations by acquiring simultaneous measurements of flow and stage, thus allowing for the estimation of flow every 10 min for all three monitoring locations. Finally, monthly records of the Stylos springs discharge have been recorded for the 1973–2004 period by the Region of Crete.

There are 9 sampling locations within the basin where monthly water sampling of surface and groundwater is taking place. The sites are: Agios Georgios stream (R1) located at the junction of Stylos karst springs and Keramianos, Katochori spring (S2) located near the entrance of Keramianos gorge and Katochori temporary river (R2), Stylos spring (S1) located at the center of Stylos village, Dug well (G2) located at Stylos village, Anavreti spring (S5) located near Nio Chorio village, Zourpos spring (S4) located at Kalives village, Armenoi spring (S3) located at Armenoi village and finally, Kampoi well (G3) located near Kampoi village (Figure 20). Field and laboratory measurements are conducted once a month. The field studies include the measurement of pH, electrical conductivity, water temperature and dissolved oxygen.

The laboratory measurements include the measurement of metals (Na, Mg, Al, Si, K, Ca, Fe, V, Cr, Hg, Mn, Pb, Ni, Cu, Zn, As, Se, Cd) and nutrients (N-NO₃, N-NH₃, P-PO₄, total carbon (TC), inorganic carbon (IC), total organic carbon (TOC), total nitrogen (TN), dissolved organic nitrogen (DON), SO₄, Cl, CO₃, HCO₃). All metals are analyzed by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS, Agilent 7500-CX, Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA 95051, USA). All forms of carbon and total nitrogen are analyzed with a multi N/C 2100S Reactor (N/C elemental analyzer, Analytik Jena, Jena, Germany). Nutrients are quantified by the use of UV-VIS spectroscopy including a HACH 2800DR spectrophotometer (Methods: LCK311, LCK153, LCK339, 8051, 8038 developed by HACH LANGE, Düsseldorf, Germany).

All the data available are also described in the DEIMS-SDR site of the LTER research Infrastructure: <https://deims.org/65d7bf15-841a-4fb7-a36e-6f4d95a8d64e>

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7. Baseline description of Pinios LL (Greece)

7.1 Geographic and environmental context

The Living Lab is situated at the eastern boundary of the Pinios River Basin (PRB) in central Greece, one of the most productive agricultural basins in the country (Figure 25). Spanning roughly 11,000 km², the PRB in central Greece serves as a vital agricultural hub and the country's pilot basin for the Water Framework Directive (WFD). Despite its diverse hydrogeological landscape, the region suffers from a lack of systematic water governance, leading to excessive groundwater abstraction and a chronic water deficit since late 1980's. Irrigation is the primary driver of demand, accounting for over 90% of total consumption sourced from both surface and groundwaters. Administratively, the PRB is the core of Water District EL08, representing more than 80% of its total area.

Figure 25. Location map of the Pinios Living Lab Living Lab.

The Pinios Living Lab area is located in the Agia watershed, which constitutes the core of the Pinios Hydrologic Observatory (PHO) (Pisinaras et al., 2018). The PHO is a highly instrumented site and a member of both the Hellenic (LTER-Greece) and International Long-Term Ecological Research (LTER) networks. The Agia watershed covers an area of approximately 55 km² but for the purposes of the NexusLabs project, this area has been slightly expanded to 63 km². It presents a highly diversified topography, characterized by a distinct relief:

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- Northern Sector: This area is mountainous with steep relief, dominated by the Kissavos (Ossa) mountain range. Altitudes here range from roughly 400 m up to 1,520 m amsl.
- Southern Sector: This area consists of a quasi-flat alluvial plain where the altitude drops to as low as 94 m amsl. This plain is the focal point of anthropogenic activity and intensive agriculture.

From a hydro-lithological perspective, the watershed is complex. The southern plain and the transition zone between the mountains and the plain are characterized by alluvial deposits that host the local aquifer systems. According to the River Basin Management Plan (RBMP) (Hellenic Ministry of Environment and Energy, 2024), these aquifers are part of the Mavrovounio-Ossa 2 groundwater system (code EL0800272), which covers a wider area of about 40 km² and is generally considered to be in good quantitative and qualitative status, although local issues exist, mainly in the form of elevated NO₃⁻ concentrations.

Regarding surface hydrology, the Agia watershed forms part of the Amiros River basin, which drains an area of about 120 km² and discharges into Lake Karla. The hydrological regime is influenced by the steep topography, with surface runoff from the northern mountains recharging the alluvial aquifers in the plain. Small springs located in the mountainous parts are significant for the local water budget; these are often captured to feed small private reservoirs used for irrigating chestnut crops in the upper slopes.

7.1.1 Climate

The climate of the study area is classified as Mediterranean (Csa according to Köppen), characterized by mild, wet winters and hot, dry summers. The climatic analysis is based on data from three (3) meteorological stations of the Hydrologic Observatory, as presented by Pisinaras et al. (2018), established along an altitudinal gradient (Lowland: ~110 m, Semi-mountainous: ~550 m, Mountainous: ~1000 m). The mean annual air temperature ranges from 15.1°C in the lowlands to 12.4°C in the mountainous zone. A notable feature of the local microclimate is the regular occurrence of temperature inversions. While the altitudinal gradients of maximum temperatures align with global lapse rates, the gradients for minimum temperatures exhibit significant variability (ranging from positive to negative), driven by frequent atmospheric instability and inversion episodes. Mean annual precipitation shows a strong orographic effect, increasing from ~710-810 mm in the lower zones to ~1100 mm in the mountainous area. Seasonality is pronounced, with the majority of rainfall occurring during the wet season (October–April). A recent significant hydrological event was the extreme storm "Daniel" (September 4–8, 2023). During this 4-day period, the stations recorded precipitation totals between 395 mm and 455 mm. This amount corresponds to approximately 50% of the area's mean annual precipitation, highlighting the critical importance of the PHO in monitoring flash flood potential and extreme water balance dynamics.

7.1.2 Soil

The soil conditions of the LL were investigated by exploiting a previous dataset including soil samples collected on the year 2020. The dataset comprises 215 geo-referenced soil samples collected from 116 locations, offering a detailed snapshot of the area's pedological status. The parameters determined in

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the corresponding soil samples include mechanical composition percentages (Sand, Silt, Clay, and Gravel), which determine the physical soil texture, as well as chemical indicators such as pH, Electrical Conductivity (EC), Organic Carbon, and Organic Matter. The sampling strategy, where possible, followed a stratified approach, primarily categorizing the soil profile into two distinct horizons: the surface layer (0-50 cm), representing the active root zone, and the subsurface layer (50-100 cm), which provides insight into the deeper pedological characteristics and drainage potential.

The interpretation of the data reveals a soil system characterized by a coarse-to-medium texture, predominantly classified as Sandy Loam to Loam as illustrated in (Figure 26). The physicochemical footprint suggests a calcareous environment, evidenced by a mean pH value of approximately 7.45, which indicates a slightly alkaline reaction typical of Mediterranean agro-ecosystems. Salinity levels, measured via electrical conductivity, average around 544 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. While this suggests that the soil is generally free from severe salinization issues, the standard deviation is significant, and specific localized zones exhibit elevated values exceeding 2600 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, indicating potential "hotspots" of salt accumulation. The biological component of the soil is notably deficient, with organic matter averaging 1.36% across the entire dataset. This figure highlights a critical lack of humic substances, which serves as the primary limiting factor for cation exchange capacity and water retention in this specific environment.

Figure 26. Distribution of Soil Texture Classes by Depth in Agia area

The textural classification analysis (Figure 26) demonstrates a considerable homogeneity in the soil's physical framework. The majority of samples fall within the Sandy Loam and Loam classes, with a distinct absence of heavy clay or silty clay horizons. This particle size distribution, characterized by a sand fraction averaging near 56% and a clay fraction limited to roughly 14%, dictates a soil profile with potentially high macroporosity and hydraulic conductivity. Such a structure facilitates rapid internal drainage and excellent aeration, effectively mitigating the risk of root asphyxia. However, this textural

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uniformity also implies a low specific surface area for the soil particles, inherently limiting the soil's natural ability to store water and nutrients against gravitational leaching. The consistency of these textural classes suggests that the soil has not undergone significant weathering or clay translocation that would form restrictive layers.

The comparative analysis between the surface (0-50 cm) and subsurface (>50 cm) horizons, as presented in (Figure 27) uncovers the vertical dynamics of the field. A slight vertical gradient is observed in soil reaction, with pH values increasing marginally with depth. Interestingly, electrical conductivity presents an inverse trend, being slightly elevated in the surface layer compared to the subsoil. This phenomenon points towards an evaporative concentration of salts or anthropogenic inputs from fertilization that have not been adequately leached. The most significant stratification is found in organic matter content, which drops from a modest mean of 1.64% in the surface to a critical 1.04% in the subsurface. Conversely, the mechanical composition remains uniform across depths, confirming the absence of an argillic horizon (clay pan) and ensuring uninterrupted vertical water movement throughout the profile.

Figure 27. Variation of key soil physicochemical properties for surface and sub-surface soil samples in Agia area.

The spatial analysis of soil organic matter presented in (Figure 28) indicates the heterogeneity of soil fertility across the landscape. The surface layer exhibits significant spatial variability in organic matter, revealing distinct patches of higher fertility interspersed with depleted zones. This patchy distribution suggests that management practices or historical land use have not been uniform across the sampled area. In contrast, the subsurface map depicts a more generalized state of organic depletion with less

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variability. The geospatial visualization confirms that while the soil matrix is geologically uniform regarding texture, the biological fertility is highly localized and heavily influenced by surface management rather than inherent pedological properties. The lack of continuity in high organic matter zones indicates that the soil's biological buffering capacity is fragmented, making specific areas more susceptible to nutrient exhaustion than others.

Figure 28. Spatial Variability of soil organic matter for surface and sub-surface soil in the plain part of the Pinios Living Lab.

7.1.3 Water

As mentioned above, in the Pinios Living Lab, the hydrological regime is dominated by the "Mavrovouni-Ossa 2" groundwater body. Water needs are almost exclusively satisfied by its groundwater, as there is no significant surface water network available for irrigation. The aquifer is recharged primarily directly from precipitation, but also laterally from the transition zone that hydraulically connect the mountainous and plain area. Groundwater abstraction is performed through a dense and complex network of deep wells, with depths of up to 150 m. These groundwater wells are managed almost exclusively by private farmers operating their own wells in groups, while a small number of groundwater wells are operated by the Municipality of Agia. Consumption patterns in Agia are intensive; for apple orchards, which constitute the main crop, the average actual irrigation water consumption has been estimated at approximately 670 mm (6,700 m³/ha) per cultivation period (Pisinaras et al., 2025). However, this figure fluctuates based on individual farmer practices, with evidence of over-irrigation in several cases (Tsakmakis et al., 2023). The dependency on deep groundwater abstraction creates a direct link between water security and energy costs, as the water table depth in the aquifer requires considerable power for abstracting. Another element regarding water in Pinios Living Lab is the gradually-developing construction of small, private reservoirs at the mountainous part of the watershed, driven by the expansion of chestnuts cultivation. These reservoirs are fed by small springs located close to them. Despite the fact that in an average hydrological year water reserves may be characterized as sufficient to cover demand, during the peak of irrigation periods in hydrologically poor years, water deficient areas do occur especially at the margins of the watershed.

7.1.4 Energy

Energy use in the Pinios Living Lab is mainly associated with agriculture, especially the pumping of irrigation water during the summer, as well as with local settlements where consumption is driven largely by households and by facilities for the storage, trade, and processing of agricultural products—particularly large refrigerated warehouses that store produce and, depending on market demand, sort and pack fruit into crates for sale. There is no major energy production infrastructure within the watershed, such as hydropower plants or large renewable installations. There is clear potential to improve irrigation energy efficiency through measures like smart scheduling and soil-moisture sensors. Moreover, there is large interest by individuals and farmers groups and cooperatives to revert to renewable sources of energy through PV and agrivoltaics that however seem to be constrained by the lack of adequate energy grid in conjunction with the national policy which seems to be currently oriented to large renewable energy plants.

7.2 Socio-economic characteristics

The Municipality of Agia presents a socio-economic profile typical of many Mediterranean rural territories in transition: a strong primary-sector base, gradual service-sector expansion, persistent demographic contraction, and pronounced intra-municipal spatial disparities. The local development pattern is shaped by the interaction between (i) demographic ageing and out-migration pressures, (ii) agricultural specialization (notably apples and chestnuts), and (iii) an increasingly visible—yet still seasonal—tourism economy.

The municipality covers approximately 668.26 km² and includes four Municipal Units (Agia, Melivoia, Evrymenes, Lakereia), each with distinct socio-economic trajectories. This internal heterogeneity is essential for interpreting demographic and economic indicators and for targeting policy and NbS-related implementation actions at appropriate sub-territorial scales. The Pinios Living Lab is located in its major part in Municipal Unit of Agia, while a small part is located in the Municipal Unit of Lakereia.

7.2.1 Demographic profile

According to data retrieved from the Hellenic Statistical Authority (<https://www.statistics.gr/en/home/>), the Municipality of Agia has experienced a sustained population decline over the last two decades. Permanent population decreased from 13,120 (2001) to 11,470 (2011) and further to 10,711 (2021) as presented in (**Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.**7). This corresponds to a cumulative reduction of about 18% since 2001, confirming structural demographic pressure despite a slower decline in the most recent decade.

Table 17. Permanent population change in Agia Municipality (2001–2021)

Census year	Permanent population	Absolute change	% change
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2001	13,120	-	-
2011	11,470	-1,650	-12.58%
2021	10,711	-759	-6.62%

Demographic dynamics are uneven across Municipal Units. The Municipal Unit of Agia, which is the core of the Pinios Living Lab, remains the most resilient demographic core (5,466 residents in 2021), while Lakereia exhibits the strongest contraction pattern. The Evrymenes unit also records significant decline, whereas Melivoia reflects mixed dynamics linked to mountain/coastal seasonality. These trends indicate that demographic decline is not homogeneous; instead, it follows local economic structure, accessibility, and service concentration.

7.2.2 Gender mainstreaming

Gender mainstreaming in Agia should be approached through evidence-based inclusion in rural transformation processes, rather than treated as a stand-alone social indicator. The socio-economic profile indicates no extreme gender imbalance at aggregate population level, but it highlights structural rural challenges (ageing, sectoral specialization, migration) that may affect men and women differently in access to employment, entrepreneurship, and services. Women are highly active in agricultural production, but remain comparatively less visible in ownership, formal decision-making, and leadership positions in major producer structures.

The municipality already has a relevant institutional basis, as the Municipal Gender Equality Committee was established in 2010, while a Local Gender Equality Action Plan was compiled in the year 2024. The key priority is effective implementation: equal participation in governance and training, better access to funding and digital tools, and systematic monitoring of women's representation and benefits.

For the Pinios LL, this translates into practical measures: (i) balanced participation targets in co-creation activities, (ii) support for women-led entrepreneurship and cooperative leadership, and (iii) care-sensitive and time-accessible capacity building to reduce participation barriers linked to unpaid care work. In this context, gender mainstreaming is both an equality objective and a condition for stronger local innovation uptake.

7.2.3 Economic activities and territorial specialization

As presented in (**Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.**8), the Municipality of Agia retains a strongly specialized productive base in the primary sector, despite gradual tertiarization. The trend reported for 2001–2021 shows:

- Primary sector: still dominant, though mildly decreasing (from 58.2% to an estimated 52.0%).
- Secondary sector: limited and relatively stable (around 10%).
- Tertiary sector: steadily increasing (from 30.0% to 38.0%), mainly tourism, trade, and services.

Table 18. Employment by sector (2001–2021 trend) (Source: Regional Development Programme of Thessaly (Region of Thessaly, 2021))

Sector	2001	2011	2021 (est.)	Trend
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Primary	58.2%	57.0%	52.0%	Decreasing (mild)
Secondary	11.7%	9.0%	10.0%	Broadly stable
Tertiary	30.0%	34.0%	38.0%	Increasing

The economically active population is approximately 4,283 persons, with around 3,774 employed, implying unemployment close to 12%. This reflects both the absorptive capacity of specialized agriculture and the complementary role of services.

Agia’s territorial specialization is anchored in high-value agriculture and supported by selective diversification:

- Apples constitute the flagship product, with strong market orientation and significant contribution to local income.
- Chestnuts are central in specific upland zones.
- Additional crops (e.g., cherries/kiwi in broader municipal patterns) support diversification dynamics.
- Tourism (mainly coastal and seasonal) functions as a second pillar but remains structurally seasonal.

This combination creates a “specialized-but-exposed” economy: high value potential, but vulnerability to climatic shocks, price volatility, and labor constraints.

The household income distribution of 2024, as presented in (**Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.**9), indicates a substantial middle-income base and a notable share of high-income households, likely linked to successful years in commercial agriculture.

Table 19. Household income distribution in the Municipality of Agia, estimates for year 2024. (Source: Municipality of Agia (2024))

Monthly income category	Number of households	Share
Low (<€800)	791	19.9%
Middle (€800–€3,000)	2,182	55.0%
High (>€3,000)	992	25.1%
Total	3,966	100%

7.3 Land use and infrastructures

The analysis of land use patterns in the Agia watershed is based on two complementary spatial datasets, which provide different levels of resolution and thematic detail and are presented in Figure 29. The first dataset is the Corine Land Cover (CLC) 2018, which offers a macro-scale overview of the landscape,

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delineating broad categories such as forests, semi-natural areas, and agricultural zones. According to the CLC 2018 map, the northern and mountainous parts of the basin are dominated by mixed forests and transitional woodland-scrub vegetation, which are critical for the hydrological balance and aquifer recharge.

Figure 29. Spatial distribution of land cover categories according to CLC2018 (left) and crop categories according to the Hellenic land parcel information system of year 2021 (right)

However, for a precise characterization of the agricultural landscape, data from the Land Parcel Information System (LPIS) of 2021 have been utilized. The LPIS dataset provides highly accurate, parcel-level information that captures the specific crop distribution within the cultivated zones. As presented in the relevant table (Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.), the LPIS 2021 data reveal that the agricultural economy of the Agia watershed is heavily specialized, as tree crops cover almost 75% of total agricultural land (excluding fallow). Pome fruits (mainly apples) orchards are the absolute dominant crop, covering the vast majority of the irrigated land, followed by stone fruits (mainly as cherries), nuts (mainly as almonds for the plain area and chestnuts for the mountainous), and olive groves. This distinction is crucial, as the CLC 2018 map classifies these areas in general categories, whereas the LPIS 2021 data allow for a detailed quantification of the considerable monocultural intensity of apple production, which drives the local water demand.

LPIS data (Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.) identify a further structural challenge in the Pinios Living Lab: pronounced land fragmentation, with an average agricultural parcel size of just 0.48 ha. This pronounced land fragmentation can significantly constrain WEF Nexus performance by increasing operational complexity and costs across all pillars. In water management, it makes irrigation planning, monitoring, and equitable distribution more difficult, often reducing overall efficiency. In energy terms, fragmented service areas tend to raise unit energy use and limit economies of scale for upgrades such as efficient pumping and solar-based solutions. For food systems, small and dispersed plots can reduce productivity, hinder mechanization and standardization, and weaken farmers' capacity to invest in innovation. At the ecosystem level, fragmentation can prevent coordinated landscape-scale measures, leading to uneven uptake of soil, biodiversity, and water-protection practices. Overall, these structural

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conditions may also increase coordination burdens among stakeholders, slow collective decision-making, and reduce the pace and magnitude of measurable Nexus outcomes.

Regarding hydraulic infrastructure, the Agia watershed relies on a highly developed but energy-intensive system tailored to this specific land use pattern. Unlike areas served by surface water gravity networks, irrigation in Agia is supported almost entirely by groundwater abstraction. The infrastructure consists of a dense network (~180 boreholes) of mid-depth (60m) to deep (170m) boreholes tapping the "Mavrovouni-Ossa 2" aquifer. These extraction points are managed mainly through a mixed governance model involving mostly private individuals or groups of individuals operating independent wells and to a very small degree the Municipality of Agia. Water distribution is achieved around groundwater wells through pressurized closed-pipe networks. This approach significantly reduces conveyance losses compared to open canals but increases the energy footprint of agricultural production due to the need for constant pressurization. Additionally, the area hosts significant post-harvest infrastructure (cold storage, sorting plants) and specialized research equipment belonging to the Pinios Hydrologic Observatory established by the Soil and Water Resources Institute.

Table 20. Summary of land parcel information system data for year 2021 in Pinios Living Lab.

Crop	Area (ha)	% of Cultiv. Area	No of fields	Crop Category	Area (ha)	% of Cultiv. Area	No of fields
Pome fruits	790.9	45.3	1,588	Trees	1,294	74.1	3,076
Stone fruits	281.7	16.1	859				
Nuts	97.0	5.6	215				
Other crops - Trees	86.8	5.0	257				
Olives	37.9	2.2	157				
Wheat & other cereals	289.0	16.5	337	Annual	341	19.5	390
Forage	52.4	3.0	53				
Other	110.5	6.3	196				
SUM	1746.3	100	3662	SUM	1746.3	100	3662

7.4 Unlocking opportunities for NexusLabs solutions

The Pinios Living Lab enters NexusLabs with a strong implementation baseline: locally tested measures and operational monitoring experience through the H2020 ATLAS (<https://www.atlas-h2020.eu/>) and PRIMA LENSES (<https://www.lenses-prima.eu/>) projects, and a participatory governance legacy from previous Nexus projects (PRIMA LENSES). In this context, the key transition challenge is not the identification of candidate solutions, but the structured consolidation and scaling of those already recognized as both effective and acceptable.

A critical strength of Pinios LL is that solution prioritization has already been co-produced with stakeholders. According to Malamataris et al. (2025), the top-ranked measures co-identified with the

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engagement of the stakeholders are the following: (i) efficient soil-water management through irrigation scheduling (NbS), (ii) improvement of advisory/support structures (governance solution), (iii) water-saving infrastructure options (gray measures, e.g., small reservoirs/rainwater harvesting), and (iv) agroecological weed/biomass management, i.e., mulching (NbSs). This provides direct social validation for the Agia intervention logic.

In Agia, the main challenges are strongly interconnected. The area remains highly dependent on irrigation during the dry season, which increases pressure on water resources and raises the system's sensitivity to climatic variability. At the same time, soil functionality constraints—especially those related to organic carbon and moisture buffering—limit resilience under drought-prone conditions and reduce the efficiency of applied irrigation water. These biophysical pressures are reinforced by economic factors, as irrigation dependence is directly linked to water-energy costs at farm level. In parallel, long-term continuity of improved practices still depends on stronger advisory and support structures, while governance and inclusion gaps—among them the effective participation of women in decision-making and innovation processes—can constrain adoption speed and social ownership of the transition.

Despite these constraints, Agia presents a particularly strong opportunity window. The local portfolio is already stakeholder-endorsed, and the two key NbS measures (irrigation scheduling and mulching) have produced measurable pilot-scale results under real field conditions. In addition, model-based upscaling capacity is available for ex-ante assessment of wider impacts, allowing the LL to move from empirical pilot evidence to structured territorial planning. This opportunity is further reinforced by a strong scientific underpinning from conference and journal outputs linked to the same implementation ecosystem, which supports both policy relevance and scaling credibility.

7.4.1 NbSs and Smart Tools Currently Implemented

In Agia, previously implemented NbSs are at pilot (field/orchard) scale. Their broader territorial implications have been explored through simulation workflows, but this should not be interpreted as full-watershed implementation.

A. Efficient soil-water management through irrigation scheduling (NbS)

It was applied in instrumented apple orchards using soil-moisture monitoring, meteorological inputs, and forecast-informed irrigation rules to optimize timing and applied volumes. Pilot evidence shows substantial water-saving potential under real farming conditions, while maintaining acceptable agronomic performance in monitored cases (Tsakmakis et al., 2023). Project quantification further confirms the direction of impact: scenario analyses indicate significant average reductions in irrigation volumes under scheduling-based management. These larger-scale values are simulation-derived, informed by pilot data (Pisinaras et al., 2025).

B. Agroecological weed/biomass management through mulching/mowing (NbS)

A second implemented NbS is agroecological weed/biomass management through mulching/mowing (Malamataris et al., 2023) and crop residues incorporation. In Agia apple orchards, targeted field campaigns compared plots under systematic herbicide use with plots applying mowing and mulching

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and crop residues incorporation. In the 2022 campaign, 96 soil samples were collected from 8 orchards (4 NbSs, 4 herbicide), at two depths (0–10 cm and 10–30 cm), and SOC was analysed with the Walkley–Black method. Results showed statistically significant differences (t-test), with SOC under mulching being 31% higher in the upper layer (0–10 cm) and 7% higher at 10–30 cm relative to herbicide-managed plots. These findings were further reinforced by the broader Agia monitoring dataset used in PRIMA LENSES, where 532 soil samples (2022–2023) from orchards under mulching/mowing versus herbicides indicated mean SOC increases of +1.2 percentage points (0–10 cm) and +0.6 percentage points (10–30 cm). This supports the interpretation that NbS improves soil functional quality and contributes to better soil-water retention behavior and drought resilience at pilot scale.

The Agia LL already has an evidence-based and stakeholder-endorsed NbS core. Irrigation scheduling and mulching/mowing are both operational at pilot level, while advisory/governance strengthening is in place as an enabling pathway for scale-up. This provides a strong starting point for NexusLabs to move from validated pilots to structured local implementation.

7.4.2 NbSs and Tool Implementation in the LL

In the framework of NexusLabs, the Pinios Living Lab pillar tool is the “Irrigation Connectivity Hub” which implements field sensors and digital tools, aiming to improve decision support and enhance resource efficiency and promote sustainable agricultural practices. The “Irrigation Connectivity Hub” acts as the digital backbone of the Living Lab, aiming to enhance farmers’ decision-making regarding irrigation scheduling. This infrastructure is being deployed, in the Pinios Living Lab, as well as in the Koiliaris Living Lab, after appropriate parameterization for each Living Lab.

- **Infrastructure & Deployment:** The Hub establishes a shared LoRaWAN infrastructure through the installation of gateways at strategic locations, ensuring broad coverage and reducing entry costs for farmers. For demonstration purposes, 10 fields have been selected in the Pinios Living Lab to act as frontrunners and presented in detail in the following section. These fields represent the variability of local farming practices (organic, conventional, agroecological) and irrigation methods (microsprinkler, drip).
- **Sensor Technology:** In each selected field, different types of soil moisture sensors are installed and tested, including low-cost solutions. This comparative evaluation allows for the assessment of reliability, data quality, and trade-offs between cost and accuracy, offering farmers a broader range of technological options.
- **User Interface:** The Hub includes a user-friendly frontend interface optimized for mobile devices, transforming raw data from sensors, water meters, and weather stations into actionable, easy-to-understand information (e.g., soil water availability) for farmers working in the field.

In addition to the smart irrigation efforts, the Pinios Living Lab will highlight the advantages of agroecological practices by implementing a robust monitoring framework for soil health and crop yields. The overarching goal of NexusLabs in this area is to validate the effectiveness of these solutions through on-site data collection, perform comprehensive economic assessments, and assess the feasibility of scaling up these practices for wider implementation. Together with the Irrigation Connectivity Hub, the

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HIDROMOREweb platform will be appropriately parameterized for the Pinios Living Lab in order to provide water accounting and footprint data. Finally, weather forecasting implemented by partner DREVEN will provide further information that will support irrigation scheduling.

7.4.3 Description of experimental demo sites

The experimental demonstration sites of the Pinios LL consist of ten agricultural fields distributed across the Agia watershed (Pinios Hydrologic Observatory) (Figure 3030), selected to represent the dominant irrigated perennial cropping systems of the area, namely apple and cherry orchards (**Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.**). These sites serve as the primary locations for the implementation, testing, and scaling of smart irrigation support methodologies, as well as for systematic monitoring of soil within the framework of NexusLabs. The selected fields cover a range of plot sizes and reflect the existing variability in irrigation methods (microsprinkler and drip irrigation) and farming practices (organic, conventional, and agroecological). Apple orchards dominate the experimental network, reflecting their high economic importance and significant irrigation demand in the region, while cherry orchards provide a comparative system. This diversity enables the evaluation of smart irrigation performance and agroecological practices across different crop types, water demands, and management regimes under the same climatic and hydrological conditions.

Figure 30. Pinios Living Lab experimental demo sites

All demo sites will be equipped with smart irrigation infrastructure (except from fields 9 and 10, which are already equipped from previous projects), including two different types of soil moisture sensors (comprising low-cost options) and water meters to quantify irrigation volumes. Data will be transmitted in real time via a shared LoRaWAN infrastructure to a centralized digital platform (Irrigation Connectivity Hub) accessible to farmers via user-friendly interfaces (e.g., smartphones), supporting irrigation scheduling based on actual plant water needs and soil water availability.

In parallel, these ten fields will function as monitoring sites, where soil samples will be collected periodically and in-field measurements will be carried out to assess soil health and soil moisture dynamics. Together, the ten demo fields constitute a representative, operational reference network for

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demonstrating the effectiveness, scalability, and co-benefits of smart irrigation and agroecological practices under Mediterranean conditions.

Table 21. Basic information of Pinios Living Lab experimental demo sites

no	Field ID	Area (ha)	Crop	Cultivation Type	Water Source	Energy Source	Irrigation Method
1	GR-PHO-AP-001	0.44	Apples	Organic	Groundwater	Electricity	Sprinkler
2	GR-PHO-AP-002	0.70	Apples	Conventional	Groundwater	Diesel	Drip
3	GR-PHO-AP-003	0.95	Apples	Conventional	Groundwater	Electricity	Sprinkler
4	GR-PHO-AP-004	1.00	Apples	Conventional	Groundwater	Electricity	Drip
5	GR-PHO-AP-005	0.18	Apples	Conventional	Groundwater	Electricity	Sprinkler
6	GR-PHO-CR-006	0.65	Cherries	Conventional	Groundwater	Electricity	Sprinkler
7	GR-PHO-AP-007	0.90	Apples	Conventional	Groundwater	Electricity	Drip
8	GR-PHO-AP-008	0.90	Apples	Conventional	Groundwater	Electricity	Sprinkler
9	GR-PHO-AP-009	1.21	Apples	Conventional	Groundwater	Electricity	Sprinkler
10	GR-PHO-AP-010	1.40	Apples	Conventional	Groundwater	Electricity	Sprinkler

Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.

7.5 Data sources and methodology for baseline assessment

The Agia watershed functions as the core of the Pinios Hydrologic Observatory (PHO), which is actively integrated into both the Greek and International Long Term Ecosystem Research (LTER) networks. Over recent years, the area has been extensively studied and instrumented, providing a robust, high-resolution scientific foundation for establishing the baseline conditions.

Environmental and agricultural monitoring in the area relies on a network of telemetric meteorological stations and two instrumented pilot apple fields (namely GR-PHO-AP-009 and GR-PHO-AP-010). Intensive soil moisture monitoring is continuously performed in those 2 fields using sensor clusters installed at multiple depths (e.g., 5, 20, and 50 cm) to track water dynamics within the crop root zone. In parallel, actual irrigation water consumption is systematically recorded using telemetric water meters installed at specific irrigation blocks, allowing for the precise quantification of agricultural water demand. Furthermore, extensive soil sampling campaigns, as presented in the corresponding section, have been conducted to analyze physicochemical properties, with a strong focus on quantifying Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) variations under different weed removal practices such as mulching, mowing, and herbicide application.

To establish a comprehensive baseline understanding of the pilot's current state, these high-resolution

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physical measurements are complemented by a wide variety of secondary data sources. These sources have been systematically screened to cover, as possible, critical components, including climate, crop types, demographics, economy, energy use, spatial geography, land use (utilizing both CORINE and LPIS data), soil characteristics, and farm management practices.

The resulting information is consolidated into the NexusLabs WP3 Database (**Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.**), which summarizes the data types collected, details the specific sources, and provides critical comments on the methodology and scope of each dataset. This baseline data is intended to serve as a shared resource, functioning as a centralized, common reference point for all project activities.

Table 22. Data sources and methodology for the Pinios Living Lab (from WP3 database)

	Data	Comments/Specs	Info
Clima	Hydrometeorological data	10-min precipitation, net radiation, air temperature, wind speed/direction, air humidity, bar. pressure	Data from 3 meteorological existing the oldest from late 2015
	Climate change/variability and sinks.	Report	Plan for Adaptation to Climate Change of Thessaly Region (in Greek)
Crop	Crop types and features	Shapefile for crop types, xlsx for crop yields	Crop type on parcel scale from the Hellenic Land Parcel Information data of year 2021, crop yield data from agricultural statistics for main crops
	Crop prices	Single values for 2025	For the WEF E audited plots (apples and cherries)
	Crop types and their practices (primarily irrigation)	Shapefile for crop types, expert opinion for practices	Hellenic Land Parcel Information data of year 2021 for crop types, expert knowledge from previous project and audited farms input
	Irrigation water requirements and cost	Single values	For the WEF E audited farms
Demo	Demographic data at the pilot scale	National statistics	Population,
	Social characterization of the Living Lab	Local and Regional Reports	Household income, Employment by sector
Economy	Territorial economic data	Excel file	Employment by sector in Municipality of Agia
	Management costs	Single values for year 2025	For the WEF E audited farms
	Energy prices	Single values for year 2025	For the WEF E audited farms
Energy	Energy consumption for agriculture	Single values for year 2025	As reported by 4 WEF E audited farms for electricity and diesel, highly variable depending on pump type, groundwater abstraction depths and distance from groundwater source to irrigated field
	Current primary energy sources		Not available
	Energy allocation		Not available
	Primary energy sources requiring water		Not available
Geo	Cartography study area and pilots (cadaster, water management unit,...)	shapefiles	Living Lab boundary, data from River Basin Management Plan of Thessaly Water District (EL08)
	Rivers and lake bodies	shapefiles	Groundwater bodies, river bodies, sub-basins from River Basin Management Plan of Thessaly Water District (EL08), hydrographic network from DEM analysis

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Land Use	Land Use/Cover data and its dynamic changes	Shapefiles	Corine Land Cover 1990, 2000, 2006, 2012, 2018 + LPIS of year 2021
	Land use maps definition (period of time, spatial scale, and legend)	Shapefiles	Corine Land Cover 1990, 2000, 2006, 2012, 2018 + LPIS of year 2021
	Records of natural disasters (floods, fires, erosion, etc)		No significant natural disasters were officially identified
	Future land use/ land use change scenarios		Not available
Water	Renewable (surface and groundwater) water sources and stocks	Georeferenced ESRI ASCII grid file	Long-term groundwater recharge map for the period 1971-2000 from Pisinaras et al. (2023) https://doi.org/10.3390/su15054343
	Water demand and its distribution among uses (for potable use, irrigation/agriculture, industry),	Single value estimates from previous project	Estimated through a water accounting approach in the context of LENSES project, will be updated since the area was expanded
	Description of water management (irrigation systems, policy, assignment of volumes,...)		No official document for the Living Lab
	Treated water		-
Soil	Soil types and/or hydrologic groups	1. Geotiff format 2. xlsx format	1. Bulk Density, Coarse Fragments, Clay Content, Nitrogen, pH water, Sand Content, Silt Content, Soil Organic Carbon Content, Soil Organic CarbonStocks from SoilGrids2.0 2. Sand, clay, silt, gravel, soil organic matter, pH, electrical conductivity from 215 soil samples representing 2 different soil depths
	Soil map types (classification of soils)		Not available
Management and Policy	Relevant local/regional/national planning documents and/or regulations	Reports	1. Regional development plan of Thessaly Region 2. The existing mobility situation for the Municipality of Agia, including useful socio-economic data 3. Regional Plan for Adaptation to Climate Change of Thessaly
	Relevant international regulations		EU Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC); EU Nitrates Directive (91/676/EEC); EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) 2023–2027; EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030.
	List of key stakeholders		Please refer Deliverable 1.1, see also Malamataris et al. (2025) https://doi.org/10.3389/frwa.2025.1469762
	Main WEFE challenges at the pilot scale	Scientific papers	Pressure on water resources for irrigation; Water quality (nitrates); Soil health; Energy efficiency. Previous projects in the Area: LENSES, ATLAS. See also Malamataris et al. (2025) https://doi.org/10.3389/frwa.2025.1469762
	Potential funding sources for NEXUS relevant solutions (green deal, Interreg, etc)		Horizon Europe (Cluster 6); LIFE Programme (subprogram Environment & Climate); Interreg Euro-MED; Green Deal Calls
	Scenarios of interest in the Living Lab		Sustainable management scenarios for soil and water resources including climate change adaptation scenarios focused on reducing irrigation demand, increasing water use efficiency, and enhancing soil water retention

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8. Baseline description of Middle Jordan Valley LL (Jordan)

8.1 Geographic and environmental context

The Middle Jordan Valley (MJV) (Figure 31) is part of the central section of the Jordan Rift Valley, lying between -200 m to -350 m below sea level, making it one of the lowest inhabited agricultural zones in the world. This unique topographic position strongly influences its microclimate and agro-ecological characteristics.

Figure 31 -Location map of the Jordan Living Lab.

8.1.1 Climate

The region experiences a hot arid to semi-arid climate, shaped by desert influences from the east and Mediterranean winter rainfall systems. The region is characterized by long, extremely hot summers from May to October, with daytime temperatures commonly between 35–40°C and often reaching 42–45°C during heat waves. Warm summer nights between 25–30°C further limit nighttime cooling and increase evapotranspiration. In contrast, winters from December to February are mild, featuring daytime temperatures of 15–22°C and minimal frost occurrence. While this thermal environment supports year-round vegetable production, it significantly increases crop water requirements and the risk of heat stress.

Annual rainfall is very low, typically ranging from 100–300 mm depending on the local gradient and distance from the highlands. This precipitation is highly variable across years, concentrated in the short winter months of December through February, and often delivered through sporadic, high-intensity storm events. Increasing climate variability has led to longer dry spells, shifting rainfall timing, and reduced predictability of early winter rains. These changing patterns reduce natural groundwater recharge and increase the region's dependence on irrigation systems.

The valley exhibits very high potential evapotranspiration, often exceeding 2000–2400 mm per year. During the summer, daily evapotranspiration rates for crops may reach 7–9 mm, driving intense irrigation demand. Depending on the specific location, the aridity index classifies the region as hyper-arid to semi-arid. Such high rates of evapotranspiration intensify soil salinity buildup and increase water stress during peak growth periods.

Observed and projected climate trends for the Middle Jordan Valley include rising mean annual temperatures and more frequent extreme heat events. Rainfall is becoming reduced and more erratic, while irrigation water salinity is increasing due to scarcity and overuse. Furthermore, higher evapotranspiration is expected to raise irrigation requirements by 10–20%. These pressures challenge sustainable agriculture, particularly for high-value crops such as tomatoes, peppers, cucumbers, and bananas. The climatic constraints in the Middle Jordan Valley result in a nearly total reliance on irrigation for commercial crop production. This creates a strong need for efficient irrigation technologies, such as drip systems and moisture sensors, and highlights the growing importance of greenhouse climate control. Consequently, there is increased interest in rainwater harvesting, protected agriculture, early warning systems for heat stress, and the development of drought-resilient cropping systems.

Overall, the climate of the Middle Jordan Valley represents a key driver for innovation within the NexusLabs Living Lab, requiring integrated solutions across water, energy, soil, and crop management.

8.1.2 Soil

Soils in the Jordan Valley typically derive from alluvial deposits carried from the highlands and mixed with fluvial-lacustrine elements of the Jordan River system. A considerable proportion of agricultural soils in the Jordan Valley demonstrates salinity and sodicity issues, with research indicating that a substantial segment of valley soils is salty, ranging from moderate to moderately saline across numerous transects. Soil texture ranges from sandy loams to denser alluvial clays based on local depositional conditions; organic matter is typically minimal in intensively cultivated regions lacking targeted soil amendments.

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These soil limitations necessitate proactive salinity management, regular leaching, and the application of amendments (e.g., gypsum, organic matter).

They exhibit significant spatial variability but share several common characteristics. Soil types and texture range from sandy loam near river terraces and loam and clay loam in central cultivated lands to clayey soils in low-lying zones where fine sediments accumulate. This variability affects infiltration, water-holding capacity, and irrigation design needs. The general soil fertility characteristics include moderate to high calcium carbonate content, low organic matter (typically < 1%) due to high temperatures and rapid decomposition rates, and moderate to high potassium levels, though phosphorus availability remains variable. Additionally, micronutrient deficiencies in zinc, iron, and boron occur especially under intensive vegetable production. Consequently, soil fertility management requires continuous monitoring and tailored fertilizer programs. Soil salinity is one of the major limiting factors in the MJV. Electrical conductivity (ECe) may range from 1–6 dS/m, with localized hotspots exceeding 8 dS/m, while sodicity—characterized by a high sodium adsorption ratio—occurs where drainage is poor or where saline water sources are used. Salinity dynamics are influenced by high evapotranspiration, insufficient leaching, and the use of marginal-quality irrigation water. These conditions affect crop growth, root function, and soil structure stability. Key soil constraints in the region include high compaction layers due to repeated tillage, low aggregate stability, limited natural drainage, high evaporation leading to salt crusting, and the accumulation of chemical residues under protected agriculture.

8.1.3 Water

Water resources for irrigation in the Middle Jordan Valley are a mix of surface water (King Talal Dam releases and King Abdullah Canal), groundwater from alluvial aquifers, and increasing use of treated/reclaimed wastewater and blended water sources for irrigation. Groundwater and irrigation water salinity vary spatially and seasonally; recent national groundwater baselines show strong temporal and spatial variability in salinity across the Jordan Valley aquifers. Water quantity is under pressure from competing uses (municipal, industrial, environmental) and from reduced inflows in dry years. Water quality and quantity vary seasonally with increasing salinity risks, and they are the central challenges shaping agriculture in the Middle Jordan Valley.

The main irrigation sources include the King Talal Dam (KTD), which delivers water through the King Abdullah Canal (KAC) as the primary source for vegetable and greenhouse irrigation. This water is mixed with treated wastewater during parts of the year, leading to seasonal quality variations where electrical conductivity typically ranges from 1.2 to 2.2 dS/m. Treated wastewater itself consists of effluent from the As-Samra treatment plant blended with surface flows; while it provides a reliable quantity for open-field crops and some greenhouse systems, it requires careful monitoring of salinity and nutrients. Groundwater wells offer a limited and declining alternative due to over-extraction, often exhibiting high salinity levels of 2 dS/m to 4 dS/m or more, and are primarily used when canal water is insufficient. Additionally, farm-level storage ponds are utilized to buffer supply and support regulated irrigation schedules.

Water quality varies considerably throughout the year due to the blending proportions of treated wastewater and freshwater, seasonal demand patterns, and evaporation losses from canals. This leads to major challenges such as salinity buildup in soils, high bicarbonate and sulfate levels, potential

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microbiological loads if treatment is insufficient, and issues with sedimentation and algae growth in open water canals.

Furthermore, water shortages result from climate-induced reductions in surface water flows, competing municipal and industrial demand, limited groundwater recharge, and rising evapotranspiration rates. Consequently, improving irrigation efficiency is essential. While drip irrigation is widespread, it is not always optimized, and precise scheduling is often lacking. Additionally, leaching fraction management remains inconsistent, and greenhouse rainwater harvesting continues to be an underutilized resource.

8.1.4 Energy

Irrigation and water pumping in the Jordan Valley rely heavily on electricity and diesel-powered pumps; Jordan is dependent on imported fuels for much of its energy needs. This creates both an operational cost burden and vulnerability to supply shocks. There is increasing interest and pilot activity to integrate renewable energy (solar PV) for irrigation pumping to reduce costs, enhance sustainability and greenhouse gas emissions and to increase energy independence for farm-level water supply.

Energy use in the Middle Jordan Valley is driven primarily by irrigation and greenhouse operations.

The main energy sources include electricity, which is used for pumping from wells and ponds as well as for pressure regulation systems. However, costs have risen significantly, directly affecting farm profitability. Diesel is also widely used, particularly for mobile pumps, though it is characterized by high operational costs, low efficiency, and its contribution to air pollution in densely farmed areas.

Solar energy is an emerging source, with solar pumping systems being increasingly adopted due to the region's high solar radiation throughout the year, the potential for reducing irrigation costs, and its suitability for off-grid pumping locations. Despite these benefits, adoption remains limited by high upfront investment costs and the requirement for specialized technical and maintenance expertise.

The primary energy challenges facing the sector include high energy consumption driven by high-pressure irrigation systems and rising electricity tariffs. Furthermore, there remains a persistent dependence on diesel during peak demand periods and a limited integration of renewable energy systems within farm clusters.

8.2 Socio-economic characteristics

The Middle Jordan Valley is one of Jordan's most important agricultural production zones and hosts a diverse population whose livelihoods are closely tied to irrigated horticulture, agro-processing, and agricultural services. The socio-economic profile of the area reflects a combination of traditional farming heritage, commercial agriculture, labor migration, and evolving gender roles.

8.2.1 Demographic profile

The Middle Jordan Valley's population includes a mix of established farming households, seasonal agricultural labour, and peri-urban communities. Rural population percentages in Jordan are low

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nationally (10 %), but the valley hosts concentrated agricultural communities and labour forces associated with intensive irrigated agriculture and greenhouse production. The area hosts concentrated farming communities and agricultural labor, with population profiles varying across municipalities such as Deir Alla. The population of the Middle Jordan Valley—particularly in key municipalities such as Deir Alla, South Shouneh, and Karamah—is composed of several distinct groups. Local farming households consist of families engaged in long-term agricultural activity, often spanning multiple generations. Medium and small-scale farms dominate this group, with plots ranging from 0.5–10 hectares depending on access to water and land tenure systems. The valley also hosts a large population of migrant workers, including Egyptian agricultural laborers and seasonal workers of other nationalities. These workers form the backbone of labor-intensive horticultural production, especially for greenhouses and packing facilities. Regarding youth demographics, individuals aged 18–35 represent a significant proportion of the local population. However, youth engagement in agriculture is declining due to limited income stability, high input costs, and a preference for urban employment opportunities, a trend that poses long-term challenges for the sustainability of agricultural systems. Finally, in terms of population density and distribution, settlements tend to cluster along the King Abdullah Canal, central road networks, and near agricultural service centers, while remote areas show limited services and infrastructure.

8.2.2 Gender mainstreaming

Gender roles in the valley are context-specific: women participate in farm labour, post-harvest handling, packing, and some extension activities; however, decision-making, land tenure and access to mechanized assets and capital tend to be male-dominated in many communities. Local climate-action and development plans (e.g., Deir Alla) emphasize the need for gender-sensitive measures in training, capacity building and NbSs adoption to ensure equitable benefits and uptake. Project interventions should integrate gender-targeted outreach, female-friendly training schedules, and monitoring of gender-disaggregated impacts.

Women play a critical yet often under-recognized role in agriculture within the Middle Jordan Valley, where they are active in sorting, grading, and packaging vegetables, as well as greenhouse production tasks such as pruning, picking, and transplanting. On family farms, their work extends to irrigation control and fertigation monitoring, and they are also instrumental in local markets and micro-enterprises involving pickles, herbs, and food processing.

Based on recent statistical reports from the Jordan Department of Statistics (DoS), gender roles in the Jordan Valley are characterized by a high volume of informal labour contrasted with very low formal ownership and decision-making power.

- **Informal Workforce:** The agricultural sector has the highest rate of informal employment in Jordan. Approximately 16% of women in agriculture work informally, compared to only 5% of men.
- **Agricultural Laborers:** While official national figures often show women making up a small percentage of the *formal* workforce, in specific rural areas like the Jordan Valley, women can represent 40–50% of the actual agricultural labor force when seasonal and family labor are included.
- **Home-Based vs. Paid Labor:** About 73% of women in these rural contexts are engaged primarily in home-based or small-scale family farming, while only 26% are engaged in paid agricultural labor.

Despite these significant contributions, women face several systemic hurdles, including limited land

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ownership and restricted access to credit and agricultural inputs. Furthermore, they often encounter insufficient training in irrigation, soil fertility, and resource management, alongside cultural constraints that limit their access to leadership roles.

- **Land Tenure:** Women's land ownership remains one of the most significant hurdles. Only 6% of agricultural holdings in Jordan are owned by women.
- **Extension Services:** Interestingly, there is a push for gender parity in advisory roles. As of 2023–2024, 58% of agricultural extension agents in Jordan were female, though they often face mobility challenges in reaching remote farm sites.
- **Access to Skilled Roles:** The percentage of "skilled workers" in the sector is notably low for both genders but disproportionately so for women: 1.8% for males vs. 0.3% for females.

A recent study on female farmers in the Jordan Valley highlight the climate impact on female workers

- **Climate Impact:** 88.7% of female workers reported a decrease in crop production due to climate change (heat and drought).
- **Information Gap:** 65.1% of female agricultural workers had never heard of the formal concept of "climate change," relying instead on practical experience for adaptation.
- **Income Reduction:** A 1°C increase in long-term average temperature is associated with a 34% reduction in the total income of female-headed households compared to male-headed households.

To address these challenges, several opportunities for gender inclusion exist. These include training women in precision irrigation, greenhouse operation, and soil health monitoring, as well as encouraging their participation in cooperatives and producer organizations. Additionally, supporting women-led micro-enterprises in value-added processing and integrating women's labour into the implementation and monitoring of Nature-Based Solutions can provide significant benefits. Ultimately, gender-sensitive interventions are essential to enhance equity and empower women in agricultural decision-making.

8.2.3 Economic activities and territorial specialization

The Middle Jordan Valley is an agricultural hub specialized in intensive irrigated horticulture (tomato, pepper/capsicum, cucurbits, cut-flowers, and vegetables), field crops in the surrounding areas, and livestock for local markets. Protected agriculture (greenhouses, multi-span tunnels) is widely used for off-season and high-value crops. The Valley also includes agro-processing, cold storage and packing facilities that support export and domestic supply chains. Irrigation services and farm mechanization-related businesses are part of the local rural economy.

Agriculture is the primary economic activity in the Middle Jordan Valley, supported by complementary sectors that strengthen local value chains. The valley serves as a national hub for vegetable production including tomatoes, peppers, cucumbers, and eggplants, as well as greenhouse and net-house farming, banana and citrus orchards in specific zones, and forage crops for livestock systems. This region supplies Jordan's main wholesale markets and various regional export chains.

The broader economic activities include packing houses, cooling and refrigeration units, agricultural suppliers for fertilizers, seeds, and drip systems, and nurseries for seedling production. These industries create employment and strengthen the agricultural economy by providing direct work for local households and indirect employment through services, transport, input supply, and processing. Seasonal employment typically peaks during transplanting seasons, harvest periods, and export

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preparation cycles. The region specializes in high-value irrigated horticulture and intensive greenhouse systems, utilizing the warm valley climate to maintain year-round production cycles of export-quality produce for high-income markets. However, several main challenges impact economic stability, such as high production costs related to energy, fertilizers, and water fees, along with market fluctuations and export restrictions. Additionally, soil salinity and water scarcity reduce overall productivity, while climate change pressures continue to increase risk and uncertainty.

8.3 Land use and infrastructures

The valley's land use is dominated by irrigated agriculture (greenhouses, field vegetable plots, orchards), irrigation canals and conveyance infrastructure (King Abdullah Canal, distribution channels), local storage ponds, access roads and farm service infrastructure (packing, cooling). Urban and peri-urban development occurs near towns (e.g., Deir Alla), occasionally competing for land and water. Infrastructure challenges include aging conveyance networks, leakage, and need for modern pumping and filtration at farm level. Transport access is generally adequate for produce movement to national markets, but some farm-to-market roads need upgrading for improved logistics.

Land use in the Middle Jordan Valley (MJV) is shaped by the region's unique biophysical characteristics, irrigation-based agricultural systems, and the presence of major national water infrastructure. The area is one of Jordan's primary zones for intensive horticulture, greenhouse production, and irrigated cropping systems. Infrastructure development is strongly tied to irrigation networks, agricultural services, transportation, and local market facilities.

8.3.1 Land Use Patterns

Agriculture is the primary economic activity in the Middle Jordan Valley, supported by complementary sectors that strengthen local value chains. The valley serves as a national hub for vegetable production including tomatoes, peppers, cucumbers, and eggplants, as well as greenhouse and net-house farming, banana and citrus orchards in specific zones, and forage crops for livestock systems. This region supplies Jordan's main wholesale markets and various regional export chains.

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Land use in the Jordan Valley is distinct from the rest of Jordan due to its sub-tropical climate and its

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role as the nation's primary "food basket." While it accounts for only a small fraction of Jordan's total land area, it produces over 60% of the country's vegetables and fruits.

Below are the key percentages defining land use patterns as of 2024–2026:

The Jordan Valley (JV) is a narrow strip representing approximately 5.6% of Jordan's total land area.

- Irrigated vs. Non-Irrigated: Unlike the highlands, agriculture in the JV is almost entirely dependent on irrigation. Nearly 100% of cultivated land in the Valley is irrigated, primarily through the King Abdullah Canal (KAC).
- Cultivated Area Stability: Recent 2025 data show a "false stability" in land use. While the total cultivated area declined slightly by 3.4% (from 29,000 to 28,000 hectares), the type of land use has shifted radically toward high-value crops.

The land use pattern has shifted from traditional field crops to intensive horticulture and fruit trees, as described in Table 23.

Table 23. Crop types in the Jordan Valley in 2025.

Crop Category	Cultivated Land (%)	Trend (1990 – 2025)
Vegetables (Open Field)	45%	Decline
Fruit Trees (Citrus, Bananas, Date)	35%	Increase
Greenhouses	15%	Growing
Grains/Forage	<5%	declined by >60%

Land use varies significantly between the North and South Ghors:

- Northern Jordan Valley: Dominated by Citrus orchards, which account for a large portion of the permanent crop land.
- Middle Jordan Valley: A mix of Vegetables (tomatoes, cucumbers, peppers) and growing areas for Protected Agriculture.
- Southern Jordan Valley (Ghors): Increasingly specialized in Date Palms (specifically Medjool dates) and Bananas, which are high-value but water-intensive.
- Smallholdings: Approximately 88% of agricultural holdings in the Valley are smaller than 3 hectares (30 dunums).
- Land Consolidation: Despite the prevalence of small farms, there is a 2025 trend toward "resource concentration," where high-capital investors (often for Date Palm plantations) are managing larger contiguous tracts of land to maximize water efficiency.

The "use" of the land is dictated by the water source:

- Surface Water (Yarmouk/Wadis): Supplies the majority of northern and middle farms.
- Treated Wastewater (TWW): Now accounts for a significant portion of irrigation in the middle and southern areas, allowing for the continued cultivation of fodder and certain fruit trees despite freshwater scarcity.

8.3.2 Irrigation and Water Distribution Infrastructure

Water infrastructure is central to agricultural productivity in the valley, with the King Abdullah Canal (KAC) serving as the backbone of irrigation in the MJV. The KAC conveys blended water, consisting of surface and treated wastewater, along the valley to supply both large-scale and smallholder irrigation networks through various intake points and secondary canals.

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At the farm level, irrigation systems are dominated by drip technology due to persistent water scarcity. These include low-pressure drip systems specifically for greenhouses and fertigation systems designed for precise nutrient delivery. However, these systems face several challenges, such as aging emitters, clogging caused by water quality issues, and uneven pressure distribution.

Storage ponds and on-farm reservoirs—which vary in size and lining quality from plastic-lined to earthen—provide essential buffering of the water supply. These structures allow for the sedimentation of solids and offer night storage for the following day's irrigation needs.

Finally, drainage infrastructure in the region remains a significant concern. There is limited natural drainage, which leads to occasional waterlogging in heavy clay zones. The current lack of systematic drainage networks contributes directly to increasing salinity build-up across the landscape.

8.3.3 Transportation and Market Access

Road infrastructure in the valley is well-developed, with north–south agricultural roads and access roads linking farms directly to packing facilities. Its proximity to Amman, roughly 50 km from Deir Alla, and established transport routes enable the rapid movement of fresh produce to Jordan's central wholesale markets and export routes to Gulf countries via land borders or airport shipments. Despite these connections, challenges remain, such as narrow or deteriorated farm roads, the negative effects of dust and heat on produce during transport, and limited cold-chain logistics available on smaller farms.

Digital and communication infrastructure is currently moderate to good, allowing for access to mobile internet, agricultural applications, and digital monitoring tools like soil moisture sensors and weather stations. However, the adoption of digital agriculture is hindered by training gaps, and existing data systems remain fragmented across various institutions.

Several infrastructure constraints are particularly relevant to the implementation of NbSs. These include insufficient drainage leading to salinity accumulation, aging irrigation infrastructure, and the limited use of modern filtration systems. Furthermore, inconsistent maintenance of drip irrigation, a lack of renewable-energy-powered irrigation systems, and the underutilization of rainwater harvesting in greenhouses persist. These constraints underscore the necessity for innovative NbS and Nexus-based solutions to improve soil, water, and energy efficiency within the living lab.

8.4 Unlocking opportunities for NexusLabs solutions

This section summarizes the main challenges and opportunities, and then lists NbSs already present and NexusLabs NbSs to be implemented.

Key challenges & opportunities:

- Water quantity & allocation pressures: limited reliable freshwater, variable inflows, and competition among uses → opportunity for water-saving irrigation and alternative sources (rainwater harvesting, blended water, treated wastewater reuse).
- Soil degradation & salinity: substantial salinization in many valley soils → opportunity for targeted soil amendments, salinity-tolerant crops, managed leaching and improved drainage.

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- Water quality concerns (mixed/reclaimed water): risk of salinity and microbial contaminants → opportunity for simple treatment trains, monitoring, and safe reuse protocols.
- Energy & pumping costs: high energy costs for pumping → opportunity to deploy solar pumping and energy-efficient systems.
- Knowledge and institutional gaps: need for farmer training in NbS practices, data-driven irrigation, and cross-sector cooperation → opportunity for Living Lab knowledge exchange and capacity building.

The Middle Jordan Valley faces interconnected challenges related to water scarcity, soil degradation, energy costs, and climate vulnerability. At the same time, the area presents strong opportunities for the deployment of integrated Nature-Based Solutions and sustainable agricultural technologies. The NexusLabs Living Lab acts as a testbed for innovations that combine water, soil, energy, and climate-smart practices.

NbSs and Nexus-based interventions offer significant potential to enhance resilience, reduce input costs, improve soil and water health, and enable sustainable agricultural intensification in the valley.

8.4.1 NbSs and Smart Tools Currently Implemented

Several Nature-Based and low-tech solutions are already in use across parts of the Jordan Valley, although their adoption remains uneven. Drip irrigation and micro-irrigation systems are widespread, particularly in protected agriculture, where they serve as vital water-saving technologies that reduce runoff and enhance efficiency; however, these systems often lack optimization due to pressure variations and clogging. The regional-scale reuse and blending of treated wastewater also supports water security and provides beneficial nutrients for crop production, though it requires careful management to prevent soil salinity buildup.

On-farm soil conservation measures, such as the incorporation of organic amendments like manure and compost, mulching to reduce evaporation, and basic crop rotation in open fields, help maintain moisture and fertility, yet they are applied inconsistently. Similarly, small-scale rainwater harvesting through infiltration pits and terraces is present in some spots. While solar pumping pilots featuring small-scale photovoltaic pumps have been installed on a limited number of farms to reduce reliance on diesel and electricity, they are not yet widely accessible due to cost barriers. Furthermore, greenhouse protected agriculture—utilizing plastic tunnels and multi-span structures—acts as an indirect Nature-Based Solution by regulating microclimates, enhancing water-use efficiency, and improving crop uniformity.

NexusLabs interventions in the Living Lab focus on optimizing these existing practices through rainwater harvesting on multi-span greenhouses, blended water use strategies, and precision irrigation based on soil moisture sensors. Additionally, efforts are directed toward filtration and water pre-treatment systems, as well as comparative performance evaluations conducted under different water sources.

8.4.2 NbS and Tool Implementation in the LL

Planned NexusLabs interventions (pilot → local scale) for the Middle Jordan Valley Living Lab include:

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Greenhouse roof rainwater harvesting + storage for high-value crops (e.g., paprika/tomato) and demonstration of blended supply strategies.

Precision drip irrigation + fertigation with soil moisture sensor feedback and automated controllers to optimize water & nutrient use.

Soil salinity management pilots (gypsum applications, leaching schedules and salt-tolerant cultivar trials).

Solar-powered pump systems to offset energy costs for water lifting and to demonstrate cost-effective renewables integration.

Digital decision-support tools (simple dashboards and mobile apps for farmers/extension) to share sensor data, irrigation schedules and NbS guidance.

NexusLabs will introduce advanced, integrated Nature-Based Solutions (NbS) and digital tools specifically designed to address the valley's interconnected challenges. One key intervention involves multi-span greenhouse rainwater harvesting systems, which collect runoff from greenhouse roofs to feed on-farm reservoirs for supplementary irrigation, thereby reducing the overall demand on canal water. Additionally, the introduction of precision irrigation using soil moisture sensors will allow for automated irrigation based on actual soil moisture depletion. This improvement in water productivity, coupled with reduced over-irrigation, is further enhanced by integration with fertigation systems for optimal nutrient use.

To ensure the safety of high-value crops and maintain infrastructure, water pre-treatment systems involving filtration and UV disinfection will be implemented. These systems help manage water quality variability and reduce the frequent clogging seen in drip systems. Alongside water quality, soil salinity management and remediation strategies will be deployed, focusing on leaching strategies and the application of organic matter and soil conditioners while monitoring salinity gradients across different cropping seasons.

The integration of solar energy for pumping and filtration will further support the long-term sustainability of irrigation systems by reducing operational costs and enabling off-grid operations in remote farms. These physical interventions are complemented by digital Decision-Support Tools (DSS), which provide real-time monitoring dashboards that integrate data from sensors, weather stations, and fertigation units to improve decision-making regarding irrigation scheduling and resource use. Finally, the initiative prioritizes farmer training and capacity building through practical demonstrations and hands-on training at the Deir Alla pilot site to ensure high adoption rates and long-term project sustainability.

8.4.3 Description of experimental demo sites

The Deir Alla multi-span greenhouse demo compares two irrigation water sources—harvested rainwater and mixed irrigation water—using drip irrigation with sensors and automated control to evaluate yield, soil responses, and water-use efficiency (Figure 32).

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Figure 32. Deir Alla Multi-span irrigation system.

The experimental demonstration site for the Middle Jordan Valley Living Lab is located at **Deir Alla**, an important agricultural hub within the central Jordan Valley.

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Table 24 summarize dier All's living lab pilot. The site has been selected due to its representative environmental conditions, intensive horticulture production, existing greenhouse infrastructure, and proximity to farmers, research institutions, and water distribution systems. The demo site operates as a field laboratory for testing and validating innovative water–soil–energy Nexus solutions under real farming conditions.

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Table 24. Summary of Dier Alla's Living Lab.

Category	Detail
Site & climate	
Location	Deir Alla, Middle Jordan Valley
Elevation	–200 to –250 m below sea level
Climate	Hot, semi-arid; high potential evapotranspiration
Soil type	Alluvial
Farm & crop	
Farm type	Multi-span greenhouse (protected agriculture)
Crop	Roman pepper
Plant spacing	1.5 m between rows × 0.30 m between plants
Max root depth	60 cm (at full crop development)
Water sources (two independent lines)	
Treatment A	Harvested rainwater — collected from greenhouse roof, stored in a dedicated lined reservoir
Treatment B	Mixed irrigation water — from King Talal Dam via station storage pond (surface water + treated effluent)
Irrigation & fertigation system	
Laterals	16 mm drip laterals (2 per planting line); PC emitters at 0.30 m spacing, 2 L/h
Sub-mains	20 mm PE
Main pipeline	50 mm PE
Per-line components	1.5-inch pump → ¾-inch hydraulic fertilizer injector → 1.5-inch auto disc filter → digital water meter → pressure gauges → 1.5-inch electric valve
Automation & soil moisture control	
Sensors	3 soil moisture sensors per treatment zone, installed at 25 cm depth
Trigger (start)	Pump activates at 32% volumetric moisture; irrigation triggers at 30% available water
Target (stop)	System refills to field capacity: 38% volumetric water content
Monitoring parameters	
Soil	EC, pH, salinity (before/after season), moisture dynamics
Water quality	EC, pH, nutrients, microbial tests
Crop	Growth parameters, fruit yield
Efficiency	Water use efficiency (WUE), fertilizer use efficiency (FUE), energy consumption for pumping
Socioeconomic	Farmer acceptance and practical usability
Objectives & expected outputs	
Operational goal	Compare agronomic performance, soil impact, and WUE between rainwater-only, mixed-water, and blended irrigation treatments
Expected outputs	Demonstrate rainwater harvesting feasibility in protected agriculture; develop replicable NbS models for dryland scale-up across the Jordan Valley

8.5 Data sources and methodology for baseline assessment

Baseline data will be collected from meteorological services, groundwater reports, soil surveys, farm records, and sensor logs. Methods include water and soil testing, agronomic monitoring, statistical analysis, and socio-economic surveys.

The baseline assessment for the Middle Jordan Valley Living Lab builds upon a combination of primary field measurements, secondary data sources, and institutional datasets. The methodology integrates biophysical, socio-economic, and spatial information to characterize the current conditions related to water, soil, energy, land use, and farming systems. Data is collected at both the pilot level (Deir Alla greenhouse site) and the broader territorial level (Middle Jordan Valley region). Table 25 illustrates data sources and methodology for Deir Alla pilot

Main data sources

- Meteorological & climate data: Jordan Meteorological Department; local station records for Deir Alla and Jordan Valley (monthly rainfall, ETo, temperature).
- Hydrological & water quality data: Ministry of Water & Irrigation (MWI) groundwater baseline, Jordan Valley Authority water allocation records, King Talal Dam release records.
- Soil data & salinity assessments: Published soil salinity studies for the Jordan Valley; NARC soil surveys and lab analyses.
- Socioeconomic & demographic data: Department of Statistics (Jordan in Figures), municipal/local development plans (e.g., Deir Alla local plan).
- Energy & pump data: National energy studies and local energy analysis for irrigation (e.g., Deliverable D3.3 energy analysis).
- Project and local operational data: Farm records, WP3 DB farm/pilot entries, field sensor logs and lab reports collected during pilot implementation.

Methodology (pilot level)

- Baseline mapping: combine remote sensing (land use), local soil maps and field transects for baseline soil salinity and texture characterization.
- Water accounting: measure inflows from each source (metered), storage, and irrigation deliveries per plot; compute water balance and WUE.
- Water/soil testing: standard laboratory analyses for EC, major ions, SAR, nutrients and microbial indicators following APHA/ISO methods.
- Agronomic monitoring: standardized plant growth and yield measurements, sampling protocols for tissue and fruit quality, and regular soil sampling (0–20, 20–40 cm) for salinity trend analysis.
- Statistical design & analysis: randomized complete block design (RCBD) for treatments, ANOVA and post-hoc tests to evaluate differences, regression to relate yield to water quality and volumes.
- Stakeholder & gender analysis: structured interviews, farmer focus groups and disaggregated monitoring to capture socio-economic impacts and gendered outcomes.

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Table 25. Data Sources and Methodology for the Deir Alla Pilot (Middle Jordan Valley, Jordan)

Data Theme	Data / Variable	Comments / Specifications	Source / Institution
Climate	Hydrometeorological data	Includes historical climate averages, monthly and daily data	Jordan Meteorological Department (JMD); NARC Deir Alla Station
	Climate change and variability	Trends in temperature rise, rainfall decline, extreme heat, drought frequency	JMD long-term data; Ministry of Environment; IPCC regional assessments
	Evapotranspiration & crop water demand	Penman–Monteith model, high ET values (>2,000 mm/year)	NARC; FAO AquaCrop; JMD datasets
Crops	Crop types and agronomic characteristics	Tomatoes, cucurbits, peppers, forage crops, citrus; greenhouse and open-field systems	Ministry of Agriculture (MoA); NARC; farmer surveys
	Crop prices	Seasonal and yearly price volatility for vegetables and fruits	MoA price bulletins; Jordan Exporters and Producers Association
	Crop practices (irrigation, fertigation)	Highly reliant on drip irrigation; greenhouse fertigation systems	NARC; Water User Associations (WUAs); field interviews
	Irrigation water requirements and cost	Based on climate data, soil properties, and pump energy costs	WUA Deir Alla; JVA; NARC irrigation trials
Demography & Society	Demographic structure	Includes local farming communities and large number of migrant agricultural workers	Department of Statistics (DOS—Jordan)
	Social characterization	High dependency on smallholder agriculture; gendered labor roles in sorting, picking	Local community offices; MoA; field interviews
Economy	Territorial economic indicators	Agricultural-based economy, dominated by horticulture and marketing chains	DOS; MoA annual reports
	Management costs	Input costs (fertilizers, pesticides, seeds, irrigation hardware)	Local market surveys; Jordan Valley farming cooperatives
	Energy prices	Electricity tariffs for agricultural pumping: variable by tariff category	Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources (MEMR); JEPCO
Energy	Energy use in agriculture	Mainly for pumping, cooling systems in greenhouses, fertigation	NARC trials; farmer surveys
	Primary energy sources	Grid electricity and diesel; emerging solar PV systems	MEMR; local energy providers
	Energy allocation	Pumping constitutes 45–60% of farm energy use	NARC studies
Geographic / GIS	Cartography and Living Lab maps	Georeferenced polygons of farms, greenhouses, water lines	NARC GIS Unit; JVA GIS Portal
	Rivers and water bodies	King Abdullah Canal, drainage canals, seasonal wadis	JVA; Ministry of Water and Irrigation (MWI)
Land Use	Land use/cover categories	Intensive irrigated horticulture; greenhouses; forage crops	Ministry of Agriculture; NARC remote sensing unit
	Land use change	Urban expansion and greenhouse increase	Satellite imagery (Sentinel-2, Landsat), NARC RS Unit
	Natural disasters (drought, salinity, floods)	Soil salinity hotspots, canal breach flooding, drought impacts	MWI; NARC; National drought monitoring reports
Water	Surface & groundwater availability	Canal water from King Talal Dam; groundwater wells (declining)	MWI; JVA; NARC water monitoring

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Data Theme	Data / Variable	Comments / Specifications	Source / Institution
	Water demand & allocation	Agriculture accounts for >55% of regional water use	JVA; basin-level planning documents
	Water management systems	Pressurized drip systems; WUA-managed allocations	Water User Associations; JVA regulations
	Treating water & quality	Blending of treated wastewater with surface water; salinity 1.2–3.0 dS/m	MWI; NARC central laboratories
Soil	Soil types and hydrologic groups	Alluvial soils: sandy loam, loam, clay loam	NARC Soil Laboratory; National Soil Map
	Soil classification & properties	Moderate fertility; risk of salinity; low organic matter	NARC Soil Physics & Chemistry Labs
Management & Policy	Local/regional policies	JVA irrigation policies; MoA cropping recommendations	JVA; MoA
	International regulations	FAO standards; water safety guidelines; climate resilience frameworks	FAO; ICARDA; international partners
	Key stakeholders	JVA, NARC, MoA, WUAs, cooperatives, private greenhouse owners	Partner list compiled under NexusLabs WP3
	Main WEFE challenges	Water scarcity, water quality deterioration, soil salinity, high energy costs	Previous NARC projects; IWMI and ICARDA studies
	Funding opportunities	FAO, IFAD, USAID, EU Delegation, Horizon Europe	Funding agencies
	Scenarios of interest	Water-saving scenarios, rainwater harvesting, salinity mitigation	NARC models; WEFE scenario analyses

9. Baseline description of the Menemen LL (Türkiye)

9.1 Geographic and environmental context

The area of 17,500 km² makes the Gediz River Basin one of the most important basins in the west of Türkiye. The Gediz Basin lies between northern latitudes of 38°04'–39°13' and eastern longitudes of 26°42'–29°45'. It covers 2.2% of the total area of Türkiye. Menemen plain, is the sub-region, has the highest agricultural potential of the region. The Menemen Plain in the Lower Gediz River Basin is located in Izmir Province. The area is intensively agriculturally used – the main crops are cotton, wheat and maize - and irrigated mainly by furrow irrigation.

Geomorphological Conditions; The Menemen Plain is a large alluvial plain located on the delta plain where the Gediz River reaches the Aegean Sea. The plain consists of low-slope (0–2%), fine-grained (silt-clay predominantly) alluvial deposits and has high agricultural production potential. However, flood risk, near-surface groundwater levels, and salinity problems in some areas are the main factors limiting land use.

The Gediz River delta, on which the Menemen Plain is located, contains four different ecosystems – saline ecosystems (saltlands), freshwater ecosystems (reedbeds), grasslands, and hilly areas. The delta includes very different habitats such as lagoons, reedbeds, estuaries, saltlands, freshwater marshes, saline marshes, saline meadows, temporary wetlands, alluvial islands, agricultural areas, and Mediterranean-type shrublands. Ecologically, the Gediz Delta has multiple national and international conservation statuses, including Ramsar Site, First Degree Natural Site and Wildlife Conservation Area.

9.1.1 Climate

The Menemen Plain exhibits typical Mediterranean climate characteristics (Figure 33). The region experiences high temperatures and low rainfall in the summer, while the winters are warmer and wetter.

Figure 33. Climatic data (temperature and rainfall) of the Menemen Meteorology Station for 2015-2025. (Source: General Directorate of Meteorology data, 2026)

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The long-term average annual precipitation (1954-2025) for the region is around 543 mm. The graph in Figure 33 shows the changes in temperature and precipitation observed in Menemen over the last 10 years. In particular, precipitation in 2022 and 2025 was significantly lower than the long-term average, causing irrigation problems and severe droughts in the intensively farmed plain. On the other hand, increases in average temperatures are also causing difficulties in agricultural production conditions in the region. The long-term average temperature is 17.1°C, and since 2018, it has been above 18°C. This leads to increased evaporation and higher irrigation needs. Furthermore, the temperature of 43.8°C measured in July 2025 is recorded as the highest July temperature measured in the plain in 71 years.

9.1.2 Soil

A large portion of the Menemen Plain's soil is medium to medium-heavy in texture, generally sandy texture along the old Gediz riverbed and becoming heavier texture towards the west. The Menemen Plain encompasses alluvial lands and colluvial mountain foothills. The plain is surrounded by steeply sloping hills to the east and north. The Gediz alluvial plain's altitude is 0-6 m, while the side alluvials are 6-30 m, and the surrounding mountains reach an altitude of approximately 1100 m. There are 16 soil series within 5 soil groups in the plain. Excluding the Ulucak series, which is largely formed on high terrain, the main soil series in the top three ranks of the plain soils are the Süzbeyli series (24.5%), the Gediz series (17.8%), and the Eskiyatak series (13%). Although the soils on the alluvial and colluvial deposits in the plain are well-drained, the Gediz and airport region soils are moderately to poorly drained, while the Gürle, Süzbeyli, and Tuzcullu soils in the low-lying areas are poorly drained. The delta and plain filled by the Gediz River are suitable for agriculture, while there are saline marshes at sea level. (Topraksu, 1971).

The most important problem in agricultural areas at the outlet of the Gediz delta is soil salinity. Moreover, soil degradation and pollution due to intensive agriculture compacted in certain areas will threaten agricultural lands in the future. Soil degradation index (SDI) values for the Menemen Plain were calculated by considering five important soil parameters: organic matter (OM), soil reaction (pH), soil salt content (SSC), lime content (CaCO₃), and exchangeable Na (ESP) content, which are vital for plant growth. Accordingly, the SDI values of soil samples from the Menemen Plain range from 0.001 to 0.803. Salinization, with its high SDI value, is the main factor in soil degradation in the plain. While salinization is the most significant problem in agricultural areas at the outlet of the Gediz Delta, poor management practices associated with intensive farming in the plain are causing degradation of the physical properties of the soil in certain areas, reductions in productivity capacity, and soil pollution, posing a threat to agricultural land in the future. In this context, the NexusLabs project will provide an opportunity for stakeholders to actively participate in producing region-specific solutions by conducting a more comprehensive assessment of areas at high risk of soil degradation in terms of geomorphological structure, parent material properties, land use patterns, and necessary measures.

9.1.3 Water

Regarding water, major challenge is to improve the water resources management of the Gediz basin. Essential difficulties related to water in the Gediz delta are summarized as follows:

- Difficulties in reaching quality water due to infrastructural deficiencies in water distribution,
- In the coastal parts of the Menemen Living Lab, the salt concentration of the groundwater has

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increased due to the sea water intrusion,

- Widespread use of surface irrigation methods, since the irrigation network in the Menemen Plain section of the Living Lab is not suitable for pressurized irrigation systems,
- Fluctuation in water reserve and water scarcity due to drought,
- Use of poor quality water (drainage water), for agricultural irrigation in dry periods,
- Increasing stress on groundwater resources due to excessive water losses in the irrigation network.
- Since the Menemen plain located at the outlet of Gediz, the water pollution load is high.

Gediz river is the main source of water for irrigation in Menemen plain. Less than 10% of the agricultural land in the pilot are irrigated with groundwater. Main channel of Gediz River is 401 km long and has an average annual flow rate of 60.48 m³/s. The total drainage area of the basin is 1.713.697 ha where the average height is 10.3 m. Gediz River Basin is regulated by several reservoirs in order to meet agricultural demand by large irrigation districts situated in the basin. The main reservoir is Demirkopru Dam, which supplies around 600 hm³ irrigational water to Adala, Salihli, Ahmetli, Manisa and Menemen plains. Those irrigational districts cover more than 100.000 ha of agricultural land that are generally irrigated by surface open channel systems. Menemen Water Users Association carries out irrigation water allocation and distribution in Menemen Living Lab.

While making their agricultural production decisions, producers are mostly affected by changes in irrigation water supply for various reasons. In addition, increasing urbanization and industrialization pressure in the Living Lab threatens the existence of agricultural land and clean water supply.

The average irrigated plot size in the Living Lab is small with 1.3 ha. The government has already taken measures to avoid further field fragmentation. Almost all plots (98%) are irrigated with furrow irrigation. However, drip irrigation systems are installed for vineyards, vegetables and orchards as well.

9.1.4 Energy

Menemen is located within the İzmir Metropolitan Area. The region operates within the framework of national energy and climate policies, including Turkey's 2053 Net Zero Emissions Target and the Turkey National Energy Plan (2022–2035). While these policies are defined at the national and metropolitan levels, their spatial impacts are particularly evident in Menemen, where intensive agricultural activities, irrigation infrastructure, and increasing renewable energy investments intersect.

İzmir has progressively shifted from fossil-fuel-dominated electricity generation toward renewable-based capacity expansion and currently hosts approximately 4,640 MW of installed renewable energy capacity. As an alternative energy source, wind energy represents the dominant share, complemented by geothermal, solar photovoltaic (PV), and biogas resources.

Within this transition, the Menemen Plain, one of Western Türkiye's most productive irrigated agricultural areas, has increasingly attracted interest for ground-mounted solar PV installations. Although these projects align with national decarbonization targets and emission reduction commitments, their location on fertile agricultural land raises concerns regarding spatial compatibility, long-term soil protection, and food security.

Agricultural production in Menemen is highly dependent on irrigation systems powered largely by

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electricity. Consequently, fluctuations in electricity prices and broader energy market dynamics directly affect irrigation costs, farm profitability, and rural livelihoods. Under projected climate change conditions, characterized by rising temperatures and increasing evapotranspiration, irrigation demand is expected to intensify, further strengthening the link between energy consumption and agricultural resilience. Menemen does not host large-scale fossil-fuel power plants; instead, its energy profile is primarily shaped by agricultural electricity consumption and small-to-medium scale solar photovoltaic (PV) installations.

9.2 Socio-economic characteristics

9.2.1 Demographic profile

With a history dating back to 1000 BC, Menemen is surrounded by Aliağa and Foça to the north, Çiğli, Karşıyaka, and Bornova to the south, Manisa to the east, and the Gulf of İzmir to the west. Located approximately 30 km from the center of İzmir, Menemen District is a settlement with a significant folkloric past, including pottery and wicker basket weaving.

Karagöl Nature Park and Bird Sanctuary are among the district's exquisite natural treasures. The Kemal Bey Monument, Kubilay Monument, Agios Konstantinos Church, Mavradis Mansion, Kubbeli Market, Mühürlü Sultan Tomb, Surp Sarkis Armenian Gregorian Church, Teikhos, Larissa, Görece Castle, Taşhan, a 17th century monument, and Gazez Mosque are among the historical riches of the district.

Table 24 shows population trends in Menemen District. Menemen's population growth rate for 2025 is 3.16%. Approximately 50.71% of the total population is male and 49.29% is female. The Menemen plain is an important agricultural area, with 35-40% of the total population in the Living Lab earning their living from agriculture. Due to its agricultural and industrial potential, the region has a young population aged between 25 and 45.

Table 26. Menemen Population by Year

Year	Menemen Population	Male Population	Female Population
2025	220.510	111.820	108.690
2024	214.409	108.965	105.444
2023	207.748	105.902	101.846
2022	200.904	102.544	98.360
2021	193.229	98.451	94.778
2020	186.182	95.118	91.064
2019	179.881	91.913	87.968
2018	174.564	89.163	85.401
2017	170.090	86.857	83.233
2016	163.565	83.431	80.134
2015	156.974	79.935	77.039
2014	148.662	75.002	73.660

9.2.2 Gender mainstreaming

Gender distribution in the Living Lab is fairly balanced (approximately 49,29% women vs. 50.71% men). In agriculture, male farm ownership and management is still predominant, although female involvement is on the rise, primarily in livestock, organic farming, and cooperatives.

9.2.3 Economic activities and territorial specialization

Agriculture holds a very important place in Menemen due to its geographical location, geological and topographical structure suitable for multiple crop farming, advanced agricultural mechanization, industry, and experienced farmer potential. Two crops, sometimes three, can be harvested annually in the district. In the villages located in the western and southern parts of the district, cereal farming, primarily cotton, is practiced.

Menemen district has two other important sectors besides agricultural industry, which includes cotton ginning factories, grape and fig processing factories, canning factories, and poultry farm production and slaughtering facilities. These are the pottery and leather sectors. Strawberries produced in the Emiralem region are among the region's important commercial products.

The percentage of people working in the industrial sector in the district is 3.61%. Nearly half of this percentage is employed in the leather free zone and Ulukent organized industrial zones.

Menemen, one of the districts with the largest amount of land in the northern region of Izmir, has a Mediterranean climate, which is suitable for growing almost all types of crops. In terms of agriculture and the food sector for the district of Menemen, since all of the plain soils are deep profile and generally medium-heavy alluvial, vineyards, vegetables, olives, and various fruits are cultivated in these areas.

Products supported under the Turkish Agricultural Basins Production and Support Model in Menemen district include barley, wheat, maize (grain), cotton (lint), sunflower (oil), fodder crops, olives, olive oil, and potatoes. In addition, seedless grapes, peaches, figs, apricots, plums, tomatoes, melons, watermelons, peppers, eggplants, strawberries, tangerines, spinach, and other products grown in the plain are also included. The distribution of agricultural areas in Menemen district by product type for 2024 is given in (Table 27).

Table 27. Distribution of Agricultural Areas in Menemen District by Product Type

Agricultural area type	Year	Area (ha)
Fruit and Spice Crop Area	2024	6532,3
Fallow Land	2024	90
Vegetable Area	2024	2711,8
Grains and Other Plant Products Area	2024	11759

Agricultural cooperatives operating in villages within the Menemen district are grouped under three main categories: agricultural development, irrigation, and fishery. A table detailing the activities of the cooperatives is provided in (Table 28).

Table 28. Agricultural Cooperatives Operating in Menemen

Cooperative name	Type	Activities
Belen Agricultural Development Cooperative	Agricultural Development Cooperative	Fertilization supporting plant production, plowing, sowing, hoeing, pruning related to fruit growing, etc.
Gerenköy Agriculture and	Agricultural	Credit activities of agricultural credit

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Livestock Agricultural Development Cooperative	Development Cooperative	cooperatives
Süleymanlı, Görece, İğnedere, Hasanlar Irrigation Cooperative	Irrigation Cooperative	Collection, purification, and distribution of water
Yahşelli Village Irrigation Cooperative	Irrigation Cooperative	Collection, purification, and distribution of water
Tuzçullu and Coastal Villages Fishery Cooperative	Fishery Cooperative	Retail trade of fish, crustaceans, and mollusks in stores dedicated to specific goods (including live, fresh, chilled, and frozen items, as well as products made from them, such as fish fillets)

The district of Menemen has products with branding potential that are unique to the region, some of which are geographically indicated. These include: Menemen pottery, Emiralem strawberry, tartamak (headscarf for farmers), a traditional Turkish egg dish (Menemen).

9.3 Land use and infrastructures

Menemen Plain (Gediz Basin) Located in western Türkiye, the Menemen Plain covers about 29.600 ha within the 17.000 km² Gediz Basin. The Gediz basin is among the important agricultural production areas of our country. Agricultural areas usually consist of irrigated arable land. In terms of production capacity, cotton, wheat and maize (silage) are among the main field products in Menemen plain, which is one of the important part of the Gediz basin. In addition, the development of cattle breeding in the basin has also improved the cultivation of forage crops.

According to the Corine 2018 land cover classes, the largest area in the Menemen plain is 22,154 ha, classified as “Permanently Irrigated Land.” The second highest land use class in terms of distribution is “Complex cultivation patterns” with 4,337 ha. The map showing the land use distribution is provided in Figure 34.

Figure 34. Corine 2018 Land Cover Classes of the Menemen LL.

Approximately 2.4% of the Menemen plain is covered by residential, industrial, and commercial areas. When looking at agricultural land use ratios, 74.8% of the Menemen plain is classified as “permanently irrigated land.” This is followed by 14.7% classified as “complex cultivation patterns,” 2.7% as “vineyards,” 1.3% as “fruit trees and berry plantations,” and 1% as “olive groves.” The graph showing this distribution is provided in (Figure 35).

Figure 35. Distribution of agricultural areas in Menemen Plain according to land use type

The region is facing drought and water shortages due to climate change. One of the most important problems of the Gediz delta is drainage and flooding/ponding in rainy seasons. Agricultural areas are under pressure due to urbanization, industrialization and transportation infrastructure in the region. Versatile (agricultural, urban and industrial) use of water resources causes water scarcity.

The Gediz basin is generally subject to land degradation due to improper land use, urbanization, industrialization, tourism, and especially intensive agricultural activities. Erosion causes serious problems in the basin, particularly in agricultural areas. Considering all these factors, the basin is among Türkiye's hotspots in terms of land degradation.

9.4 Unlocking opportunities for NexusLabs solutions

The Menemen pilot region, while an important plain in terms of agricultural production, faces many significant problems. In addition to the water shortage experienced in the region in recent years due to climate change, the plain is under environmental pressure. The conversion of agricultural lands into residential areas, their use for industry, land fragmentation in the form of hobby gardens, and construction threaten agricultural production. Soil quality is declining, and productivity is decreasing due to intensive farming. WEF Nexus approaches are critically important for the region in order to protect agricultural soils, water resources, and productivity. Widespread adoption of nature-based solutions in the Living Lab has become an unavoidable priority for sustainable agriculture.

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Agricultural production is threatened by drought resulting from the negative impact of climate change on water resources. While the main problem in the region is insufficient irrigation water, insufficient organic matter and salinity in the parts of the Gediz delta near the sea are significant problems. Inadequate drainage, the poor quality of drainage water, and the use of this water for agricultural production further exacerbate the problems. Unconscious use of irrigation water leads to the overexploitation of groundwater resources. Improving irrigation infrastructure, implementing nature-based solutions to increase water retention capacity, and efficient use of water resources will help alleviate problems in the region. The NexusLabs Project will implement nature-based practices in line with objectives such as efficient water use, planning alternative crop patterns with low water requirements, and soil moisture conservation.

Soil degradation and environmental pressure on land negatively impact agricultural production. Industrialization and urbanization are major threats to the plain. Integrated management of the plain with all users will contribute to the development of sustainable agriculture. This project will highlight new approaches and solutions in a Living Lab through the collaboration and synergy of policymakers and producers. Suggestions developed with the active participation of stakeholders will contribute to the development of sustainable agriculture in the Living Lab and similar areas.

9.4.1 NbSs and Smart Tools Currently Implemented

The Menemen Plain, one of Türkiye's most fertile agricultural areas, is the gateway to the sea for the Gediz Basin. The State Hydraulic Works (DSİ) 2nd Regional Directorate is the primary institution responsible for the construction, planning, and macro-level allocation of water resources (dams, regulators). Menemen Irrigation Associations are responsible for the operation, maintenance, and repair of the irrigation network constructed by DSİ, and for delivering water to farmers (distribution/rotation). Due to the irrigation water shortage experienced in the Menemen Plain Living Lab in recent years, water distribution has been replanned in the region. Especially during drought periods, a fair distribution of water is ensured according to the schedule announced by the irrigation associations. Water loss is prevented by supplying water to specific canals on specific days. This revision in water planning has triggered a change in the crop pattern in the plain. The seasonal water distribution planning has led to the widespread cultivation of crops such as sunflower and wheat, which consume less water and are more tolerant to drought. The cultivation of winter vegetables and fodder crops with short growing seasons has become widespread in the Menemen Plain in recent years. Significant water savings are targeted through changes in crop patterns.

With the contribution of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry's district organizations and research institutions, studies are being carried out to promote efficient water use and the widespread adoption of modern irrigation techniques. Through training and demonstration activities, the aim is to popularize nature-based solutions, water conservation, and alternative crops in the Menemen Plain. These activities will prevent the problems from deepening further in the region in the short term.

9.4.2 NbSs and Tool Implementation in the LL

The challenges encountered in the Menemen region are as follows: periodic water shortages due to drought negatively affect agricultural production in the Living Lab, surface irrigation methods lead to unconscious and excessive water use, drainage problems and soil salinity, the reduction and

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degradation of agricultural land, and the disruption of ecosystem balance due to climatic fluctuations and environmental impacts. Awareness of these challenges has been raised through promotional activities carried out during the LENSES project and the sharing of project outputs. This awareness has strengthened producers' approaches and tendencies towards nature-based solutions. The project aims to spread the NbSs addressed through Menemen Pilot LL applications on a plain scale.

The Menemen Living Lab will serve as a living laboratory for testing and disseminating nature-based solutions. Within the framework of water management, digital irrigation, water conservation techniques (water harvesting, mulching), and testing alternative irrigation water sources (olive mill wastewater) will be addressed, while in soil management, green manuring, mulching, reduced tillage, and crop rotation practices will constitute the main activities. The Living Lab will primarily focus on water scarcity and soil quality issues. Improving soil quality, enhancing soil fertility, and improving microbial activity will significantly contribute to sustainable soil management. Reducing the use of chemical inputs and land traffic will have a positive impact on soil health. All these nature-based solutions will be implemented within a holistic approach that supports carbon sequestration.

Increasing soil organic matter, mulching, and reduced tillage methods will significantly contribute to water conservation. Crop rotation systems are important practices for sustainable productivity in agricultural production, and crop rotation systems that incorporate winter legumes will contribute to improving soil quality. Including crops that require less irrigation water in the crop rotation system and changes in the crop pattern in the plain will reduce pressure on water resources.

Through activities that can involve all stakeholders, the NbS solutions will be disseminated, and the NEXUS approach will be adopted throughout the plain.

9.4.3 Description of experimental demo sites

The applications in the Menemen Living Lab will be carried out on the research and trial fields of the International Agricultural Research and Training Centre Directorate (UTAEM). UTAEM was established on 9 September 1996 in Menemen, Izmir, under the name Agricultural Hydrology Research and Training Centre. The Centre was reorganized as the International Agricultural Research and Training Centre on 11 February 2009, with the aim of conducting national and international research and training activities to increase productivity and quality in agricultural production, protect natural and genetic resources, and promote the sustainable use of natural resources. On 3 June 2011, the Centre merged with the Menemen Soil and Water Resources Research Institute. Established in 1949 to focus on regional soil and water resource management, the combined entity continues its research and training activities today.

Within this framework, UTAEM conducts research on soil and water resources, climate change, agricultural technologies, agricultural economics, and rural development. Experimental studies (Figure 36) are conducted at UTAEM under the following departments: Plant Nutrition and Soil, Climate Change and Agricultural Ecology, Mechanization and Information Technologies, Agricultural Economics, Agricultural Irrigation and Land Reclamation, National and International Education, and Production-Management. UTAEM has 39.6 ha of land at its center and 59.6 ha in Ortaköy, 4 km away from the center. Wheat, cotton, maize, and forage crops are grown on these lands located in the Menemen plain. Sunflower cultivation has also been introduced in recent years. In addition, the Köyceğiz experimental and demonstration station has 140 ha of land consisting of olive groves and citrus orchards.

Figure 36. Menemen Living Lab Demo Site

9.5 Data sources and methodology for baseline assessment

The current status of the Menemen Plain Living Lab and the creation of a future-oriented strategy required the examination of verified and reliable data sources at the regional level. These sources encompassed various data components, including climate, vegetation, demographics, economy, energy, geography, land use, water, soil, management, and policy. The sharing of this data aims to achieve efficiency, success, and a proper approach to problems. Data from different sectors (climate, agriculture, energy, etc.) will increase the project's chances of success by enabling the NEXUS approach to be managed in a robust and multidisciplinary manner. This data can be considered a reference point for similar areas.

The WP3 database created for this purpose summarizes the collected databases. The sample table (Table 29. Data sources and methodology for the Menemen pilot (from WP3 database)) explains the data sources and methodology for the Menemen pilot.

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Table 29. Data sources and methodology for the Menemen pilot (from WP3 database)

	Data	Comments/Specs	Info
Climate	Hydrometeorological data	incl. historical variability	daily and annual precipitation, radiation, temperature, wind speed, humidity, precipitation record, temperature record etc.
	Climate change/variability and sinks.	incl. sinks (atmosphere, outflows to sea, percolation to groundwater) etc	Water and Climate
Crop	Crop types and features		List of crops produced in the Living Lab (types, varieties, yields, area cropped)
	Crop prices		List of crops produced in the Living Lab and their prices (time series)
	Crop types and their practices (primarily irrigation)	LPIS	Shapefile and text for crops and practices (irrigation pattern), text info
	Irrigation water requirements and cost		(m ³ /ha, Kwh, €/ha)
Demo	Demographic data at the pilot scale		Population and distribution - age, gender...
	Social characterization of the Living Lab		Reports, official plans
Economy	Territorial economic data		N., type and size (production, turnover, n. of employees) of water-demanding economic activities.
	Management costs		Agriculture management practices (including irrigation) and their unit costs (e.g. per ha or per crop production unit e.g. kg)
	Energy prices		Energy prices (Euro/KWh)
Energy	Energy consumption for agriculture	e.g. for pumping and irrigation	
	Current primary energy sources		(oil, biomass, gas, coal, nuclear, renewables etc)
	Energy allocation		(e.g. % eolic, % hydroelectric)
	Primary energy sources requiring water		(power plants, hydroelectric, etc.)
Geo	Cartography study area and pilots (cadaster, water management unit,...)	shapefile georeferenced	Shapefile
	Rivers and lake bodies		Shapefile, river flow records, levels etc
Land Use	Land Use/Cover data and its dynamic changes	RS data Classification + LPIS + CLC	Shapefile or raster data
	Land use maps definition (period of time, spatial scale, and legend)		Land use map (crops and forest)
	Records of natural disasters (floods, fires, erosion, etc)	Copernicus, etc.	Shapefile or raster data (e.g. flood zones. historical data etc)
	Future land use/ land use change scenarios		
	Demand for natural resources - water and land (current and future)		Text/Statistics (geospatial data if possible)

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Water	Renewable (surface and groundwater) water sources and stocks		
	Water demand per land use type/class	Shapefile or data records	
	Water demand and its distribution among uses (for potable use, irrigation/agriculture, industry),	spatially distributed/historical when possible	Text/Statistics
	Description of water management (irrigation systems, policy, assignment of volumes..)		
	Desalination		
	Treated water		
	Water footprint	if already available	
Soil	Soil types and/or hydrologic groups	Shapefile or raster data	
	Soil map types (classification of soils)		
Management and Policy	Relevant local/regional/national planning documents and/or regulations	Reports/docs	
	Relevant international regulations	Regulations	
	List of key stakeholders		
	Main WEF E challenges at the pilot scale	Reports, official plans, previous studies	
	New or under consultation action plans/strategies for WEF E management	Text (geospatial data if possible)	
	Potential funding sources for NEXUS relevant solutions (green deal, Interreg, etc)	Reports, official plans	
	Scenarios of interest in the Living Lab		
Nature-Based Solutions	Existing NbS solutions implemented in the field (if any)	Reports, official plans	
	Planned NbS solutions to be implemented in the field (if any)	Reports, official plans	
	NbS solutions susceptible of future implementation in the territory	Dossier	
	Knowledge on previous project/initiatives	Objectives achieved/not achieved, limits, bottlenecks, conflicts	

References

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TOPRAKSU, 1971. Menemen Ovası temel toprak etüdü. TOPRAKSU Genel Müdürlüğü Toprak ve Etüd Haritalama Dairesi Raporları. Seri No:24, 65 s, Ankara.

General Directorate of Meteorology, Reports, 2026

10. Baseline description of the Tensift LL (Morocco)

10.1 Geographic and environmental context

The Tensift basin, located in central-western Morocco (Figure 37), covers approximately 20,000 km², stretching from the High Atlas in the south to the Jbilet hills in the north, and from Marrakech in the east to the Atlantic Ocean in the west. The Living Lab is focused on the Haouz plain (6,000 km²) within the Al Haouz province, in the peri-urban area of Marrakech, where the nine partner farms are located: Les Domaines Graoua, Les Domaines Wazo, Le Domaine Agafay, Lahna, Les Domaines Yazid, Ounasda, GhabatChbab, Tighdouine, and Elmansouri.

The study area is characterized by an irrigated alluvial plain, bordered to the south by the foothills of the High Atlas, the main water source for the region via the Tensift River and its tributaries (including the N'Fis wadi). The High-Atlas Mountains are often referred to as the "water tower" for the Haouz plain, with average precipitation reaching 600 mm in the mountains, compared to only 250 mm on the plain (IDRC-CRDI, 2025). Agriculture is intensive and heavily dependent on irrigation, with a predominance of high-value perennial crops (citrus, olive trees).

Figure 37. (a) Overview map of the Tensift basin in Morocco and (b) images over the Tensift basin of MODIS NDVI, (c) elevation and (d) MODIS land surface temperature on 5 October 2013. (Merlin et al. (2015))

Geomorphological Conditions: The soils of the studied farms are predominantly silty-clay-sandy (Wazo, Lahna, Agafay, Yazid) to clay-loamy (Graoua). The topography is relatively flat, with gentle slopes, which favors mechanized agriculture but also exposes it to risks of water erosion during heavy storms. Research in the neighboring Ourika watershed (Fadili et al., 2015) has demonstrated that soil erosion is a significant concern, with soil loss below the tolerance level (<7 t/ha/year) representing only 4% of the area. Dense forests and arboriculture play a crucial role in soil protection by improving physical and chemical soil characteristics, facilitating water infiltration, and limiting runoff.

Ecological Importance: Although highly anthropized, the Tensift area includes riparian ecosystems along the wadis and temporary wetlands. Pressure on water resources constitutes the main threat to these ecosystems. The region is also recognized for the importance of its oasis systems and palm groves, although these are in decline.

The Tensift Basin hosts a diversity of ecosystems, including mountain forests and rangelands, river corridors, irrigated agro-ecosystems, and coastal environments. These ecosystems are increasingly stressed by water scarcity, land degradation, and climate variability. Environmental challenges include aquifer depletion, soil salinization, loss of natural vegetation, and reduced ecological connectivity.

10.1.2 Climate

The Tensift region is subject to a semi-arid Mediterranean climate, characterized by a hot, dry season and a cooler, wet season. Continental influence and proximity to the desert are felt, with significant temperature amplitudes.

Precipitation: Average annual rainfall is low and irregular, generally varying between 200 and 300 mm per year on the plain (IDRC-CRDI, 2025). Rains are concentrated from October to April. Climatic data from the Cadi Ayyad University consortium meteorological station (available for the Graoua, Agafay farms) show marked interannual variability, with recurrent severe drought episodes, as evidenced by the unanimous comments from farmers.

Temperatures: Summers are hot to very hot, with average maximum temperatures frequently exceeding 38°C in July and August, and can reach 45°C during heatwaves. Winters are mild, with minimum temperatures dropping to around 3-5°C in January. Reference evapotranspiration (ET₀) is very high during the summer season, far exceeding precipitation and making irrigation essential for any crop.

Recent Evolution: The region is facing an era of water scarcity, characterized by repeated droughts, increasing demand, and overexploitation of resources (Attou, 2025). Farm data confirm a trend of worsening water stress. All farms report "extreme drought events during the summer" and "increased evapotranspiration rates" over the years. This trend, combined with the depletion of groundwater resources, constitutes the major challenge for the sustainability of agricultural systems in the Tensift.

10.1.2 Soil

The soils of the Tensift Basin reflect the strong geographical and environmental diversity of the territory, marked by a sharp contrast between the mountainous areas of the High Atlas, the alluvial Haouz Plain, and the arid sectors in the western part of the basin. This pedological diversity strongly influences agricultural land use, hydrological dynamics, and environmental vulnerability.

In the mountainous areas of the High Atlas, soils are generally weakly developed, shallow, and stony, formed on limestone, schist, or magmatic substrates. They have a low water-holding capacity but play a crucial role in infiltration, groundwater recharge, and flow regulation. These soils are mainly used as rangelands, forests, and hydrological recharge zones, but they are highly sensitive to water and mechanical erosion.

The Haouz Plain is dominated by alluvial and colluvial soils, often deep to very deep, with textures ranging from silty-sandy to silty-clayey. These soils form the main support for irrigated agriculture in the basin. Their natural fertility is variable but generally favorable for tree crops, particularly olive trees. However, agricultural intensification and continuous irrigation have led, in some areas, to problems of salinization, sodicity, and soil structure degradation.

In the most arid and poorly drained sectors, particularly downstream areas and certain depressions, soils with high salt content are observed, sometimes associated with surface crusts that limit infiltration and agricultural productivity. These soils are especially sensitive to poor irrigation management and inadequate drainage.

From an environmental perspective, the soils of the Tensift Basin are subject to several major pressures, including erosion, depletion of organic matter, salinization, and loss of water storage capacity. These processes are exacerbated by climate variability, recurrent droughts, and the overexploitation of groundwater resources.

Soil analyses carried out on the different farms of the Living Lab by the farmers reveal a diversity of situations, but also common characteristics.

Physicochemical Characteristics:

- Texture: Variable depending on the site.
 - Silty-clay-sandy: This is the dominant texture (Wazo, Lahna, Agafay, Yazid). Clay content varies from 14% to 38%, sand from 25% to 55%.
 - Clay-loamy: Observed on the Graoua farm (36-38% clay).
 - Sandy-loamy: Present in some plots (El Mansouri, data not detailed).
- pH: All soils are alkaline, with a pH ranging from 8.1 to 8.4. The soils of the Lahna and Yazid farms are specifically described as "alkaline and calcareous."
- Soil Organic Carbon (SOC): Generally low to moderate.
 - *0-30 cm*: Values range from 0.66% (Agafay) to 1.44% (Lahna). Graoua shows 1.32%, Wazo 0.96%, Yazid 0.80%.

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- *30-60 cm*: Contents decrease with depth, ranging from 0.53% (Yazid) to 1.04% (Wazo).
- Salinity (electrical conductivity): Moderate values are observed, with localized peaks. The Lahna and Yazid farms present a specific risk of sodification (high chloride and sodium levels), which can lead to degradation of soil structure.

Main Soil-Related Challenges:

- Limited fertility: Low organic matter content reduces water holding capacity, biological activity, and nutrient availability.
- Induced deficiencies: Alkaline pH severely limits the availability of phosphorus and trace elements (iron, zinc, manganese), a problem explicitly mentioned for the Lahna and Yazid farms.
- Degradation risks: Nitrate leaching is an identified risk for the Agafay farm. Risks of sodification and salinization are present, particularly with suboptimal irrigation and fertilization management.

10.4.3 Water

Water is the central limiting resource in the Tensift Basin and the main driver of socio-economic development and environmental vulnerability. The basin is characterized by structural water scarcity, strong dependence on groundwater, and high exposure to climate variability.

Surface water resources are limited and highly irregular. The Tensift River and its tributaries are largely intermittent, with flows strongly dependent on rainfall and snowmelt from the High Atlas Mountains. Several dams regulate surface water for irrigation and domestic supply, but declining inflows and increased demand have reduced their buffering capacity during prolonged droughts.

Groundwater constitutes the backbone of water use in the basin. The Haouz aquifer supplies the majority of irrigation water as well as a large share of urban water demand, particularly for the city of Marrakech. Over recent decades, intensive pumping driven by agricultural expansion and urban growth has led to a continuous decline in groundwater levels, increased pumping depths, and rising energy costs. In some areas, groundwater quality is also affected by salinization and nitrate pollution.

Water demand in the Tensift Basin, especially in the Haouz plain, is dominated by agriculture, which use about 85% of available water. Irrigated farming systems, especially olive trees and orange trees, rely heavily on groundwater abstraction. Urban water demand is increasing rapidly due to population growth and tourism, intensifying competition between agricultural, domestic, and environmental uses.

Climate change exacerbates existing pressures by increasing temperature, reducing effective rainfall, and intensifying drought frequency and duration. These trends reduce natural recharge, increase evapotranspiration, and further stress both surface and groundwater resources.

Water management is at the heart of the Tensift Living Lab's challenges. All farms depend exclusively on groundwater pumped from the aquifer via private wells. The water resources face heavy demands from various competing sectors, including agriculture (over 273,000 ha of irrigated areas), water supply for more than 2 million inhabitants and about 2 million tourists annually (IDRC-CRDI, 2025).

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Resources and Infrastructure:

- Source: Irrigation is entirely dependent on individual boreholes and wells. The El Mansouri farm, with its 14 wells (only 8 operational), illustrates the pressure on the resource and the supply difficulties.
- Irrigation Method: 100% of cultivated areas are equipped with drip irrigation, a water-saving technology now widespread in the region, largely promoted by modernization policies such as the Plan Maroc Vert (Moucha et al., 2025).

Groundwater Status: Scientific studies reveal alarming trends:

- The groundwater table decreases at a rate of 1 to 3 meters per year (Fadili et al., 2015).
- The annual groundwater deficit is approximately 100 million m³ (IAEA, 2021).
- Agriculture accounts for 80% of the total water demand, and the net consumptive use of groundwater by agriculture represents 55% of the total water consumed by this sector (IDRC-CRDI, 2025).
- The groundwater depletion during the last decade is equivalent to 50% of the reserves lost during the previous 40 years (Attou, 2025).

Consumption and Costs:

- Water Volumes: They vary considerably depending on the crops.
 - Citrus (Afourer, Nour, Navel): Annual consumption ranges from 4,000 to 10,000 m³/ha. Most farms (Graoua, Agafay, Lahna, Yazid) are in a high range of 8,000 to 10,000 m³/ha/year, while the Wazo farm (Afourer and Navel) shows more moderate needs (4,000 - 8,000 m³/ha/year).
 - Melon: Consumes between 3,500 and 4,000 m³/ha/year (Graoua).
 - Olive Tree: Needs are difficult to quantify for the El Mansouri farm due to irregular well operation, sometimes with only one 4-hour irrigation cycle every 15 days.
- Water Cost: The cost is a major factor, varying from €0.18/m³ (Graoua, Wazo, Lahna, Yazid) to €0.35/m³ (Agafay), representing an annual cost per hectare that can exceed €3,000 for the most water-intensive citrus.

Major Challenges:

- Scarcity and Shortage: This is the number one challenge, cited by all farmers. The renewable water resources per capita are already around 500 m³/year, placing the region in a situation of absolute water scarcity (Attou, 2025).
- Energy Cost: The high cost of water is intimately linked to the cost of the energy required for pumping, an increasing economic burden for farms.
- Drip Irrigation Paradox: Research has shown that the widespread conversion to drip irrigation, often implemented without adequate regulation, has frequently led to crop intensification and expansion of irrigated areas, paradoxically aggravating groundwater overexploitation (Moucha et al., 2025). Modeling studies indicate that irrigation water use could almost double under extreme scenarios, with most of this drastic increase attributed to land use change, including irrigation intensification and expansion (IRD, 2024).

10.4.4 Energy

Energy plays a critical and growing role in agricultural production in the Haouz Plain, mainly due to the strong dependence of farming systems on groundwater irrigation. As surface water availability has declined and rainfall has become more erratic, energy consumption for water abstraction has become a central driver of agricultural costs and resource sustainability.

The dominant energy use in agriculture is related to groundwater pumping. Thousands of private and collective wells supply irrigation water to olive groves, citrus orchards, fodder crops, and vegetables. Pumping depths have increased significantly over recent decades due to groundwater table decline, resulting in higher energy demand per cubic meter of water extracted. Energy sources are diverse and include diesel generators, electricity grid, and increasingly solar photovoltaic systems.

Diesel-powered pumping remains common, particularly among small and medium farmers, but it is associated with high operating costs, fuel price volatility, and greenhouse gas emissions. Grid-connected electric pumping is more energy-efficient but contributes to rising electricity demand in rural areas. In response, solar-powered irrigation systems have expanded rapidly across the Haouz Plain, driven by declining solar costs and public support programs. While solar energy reduces fuel expenses and emissions, it can also lead to uncontrolled groundwater abstraction if not properly regulated.

Morocco's climate strategy heavily prioritizes renewable energy deployment—a cornerstone of both mitigation and energy security. Policies aim to achieve ~52% of electricity generation from renewables by 2030 (solar, wind, hydro) and reduce reliance on imported fossil fuels.

The link between energy and water is central to the sustainability of Tensift farms.

Consumption and Sources:

- Main Item: Pumping irrigation water is by far the largest energy consumption item.
- Energy Mix:
 - National Electricity Grid: All farms are connected to it.
 - Solar Photovoltaic Energy: Significant adoption is observed, with installations on the Graoua, Wazo, and El Mansouri farms. This reduces dependence on the grid and smooths out costs, but does not cover all needs, especially during periods of high demand (summer).

Energy Management:

- Monitoring: According to the WEFE audits, none of the farms have an advanced energy consumption monitoring system or a dedicated energy manager. This represents a significant opportunity for optimization.
- Investment Constraints: Although not specified in the audits, the main constraints to investment in renewable energy or energy efficiency are likely financial (initial cost) and related to the complexity of administrative processes.

10.2 Socio-economic characteristics

10.2.1 Demographic profile

The Tensift Basin, located in central Morocco and centered around the city of Marrakech, is home to approximately 3 million people, with around 35% living in urban areas and 65% in rural zones. The population is relatively young, with about 30% under the age of 15 and 60% in the working-age group of 15 to 59 years, but agriculture faces a challenge in workforce renewal. Marrakech serves as the primary urban hub, exhibiting a high population density of over 300 inhabitants per km², while rural areas maintain lower densities ranging from 20 to 60 inhabitants per km². Household sizes tend to be larger in rural communities (around six members) compared to urban households (about 4.9 members). Economically, urban populations are engaged primarily in services, trade, and tourism, whereas rural populations rely on agriculture and livestock. The basin is experiencing gradual urbanization and moderate population growth, projected to reach 3.4 million by 2035.

10.2.2 Gender mainstreaming

Gender mainstreaming in the Tensift Basin is an essential component of sustainable water and climate management. Although women play a critical role in household water use, agriculture, and community resilience, their participation in formal decision-making and technical leadership remains limited. Moroccan national policies increasingly promote gender inclusion through legal reforms, quotas in water committees, and capacity-building programs. At the basin level, efforts are underway to empower women through training, participatory data collection, and involvement in water management and climate adaptation projects. Strengthening gender mainstreaming ensures that women's voices are incorporated into resource allocation and planning, promoting equitable access to resources, enhancing community resilience, and ensuring that development and climate strategies address the needs of all stakeholders.

10.2.3 Economic activities and territorial specialization

From a socio-economic perspective, irrigated agriculture is the dominant water user, with olive groves and cereal crops occupying large areas. Rapid urban growth in Marrakech, coupled with tourism development and rising energy demand for groundwater pumping, has intensified competition among water users. As a result, the Tensift Basin represents a critical hotspot where interactions between water, energy, food production, and ecosystems are particularly strong

Agriculture is the economic engine of the Living Lab, with a clear specialization:

- **Citrus Farming:** This is the dominant crop, represented by high-value varieties such as Nour, Navel, Clementine (Nules, Sidi Aissa) and especially Afourer (mandarin), grown on the Agafay, Lahna, Yazid, and Wazo farms.
- **Olive Growing:** The El Mansouri farm is entirely dedicated to olive trees of the Picholine marocaine variety, covering 275 ha, illustrating the importance of this sector in the region.
- **Diversification:** The Graoua farm presents a more diversified model, combining citrus, melon (double cycle), market gardening (beans), fruit trees (peach, palm) and ornamental plants.

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- **New Niches:** The presence of persimmon on the Wazo farm shows a trend towards diversification into high-value crops.

Workforce and Social Challenges:

- **Employment:** Large farms are significant employers, with substantial seasonal labor needs for pruning, thinning, and harvesting.
- **Major Challenge:** The difficulty in finding skilled labor is a problem shared by all farms. Labor costs for harvesting are high (e.g., €0.10/kg for citrus at Graoua). Manual weeding, although practiced, is also labor-intensive.

Table 30. Summary of Farms in the Tensift Living Lab.

Farm	Coordinates	Start Year	Total Area (ha)	Main Crops	Specific Features
Graoua	31.59004, -7.92075	2003	252 (134 cultivated)	Citrus (68 ha), Melon (42 ha), Olive (4.5 ha), various	Highly diversified model, double melon cycle, weather station, sensors, PV
Wazo	31.33348, -8.56238	2016	77	Citrus (Afourer 12 ha, Navel 15 ha), Persimmon (35 ha)	Specialization in citrus + persimmon, shredding and recycling of pruning residues, PV
Agafay	31.49711, -8.24378	1975	275 (40 studied)	Citrus (Afourer 40 ha)	Historic, well-equipped farm (station, sensors), high water cost
Lahna	31.528126, -8.221495	2001	42 (35.4 cultivated)	Citrus (Afourer 35.4 ha)	Specialization in Afourer, history of manure application (2001-2020)
Yazid	31.542293, -8.285405	2015	50 (24 cultivated)	Citrus (Afourer 24 ha)	Young, well-equipped orchard (station, sensors), 26 ha uprooted in 2025
El Mansouri	Not provided	1998	275	Olive (Picholine 275 ha)	Very large olive grove, 14 wells (8 operational), low monitoring equipment level

10.3 Land use and infrastructure

Land use in the Living Lab is dominated by intensive perennial crops.

- **Crop Distribution:** Citrus represents the largest cultivated area among partner farms, followed by olive trees. Annual crops (melon, market gardening) play a secondary but important role in diversification.
- **Modern Infrastructures:** The technological level of the farms is generally high.
 - **Irrigation:** 100% drip irrigation.
 - **Monitoring:** Most farms (Graoua, Wazo, Agafay, Lahna, Yazid) have on-site or nearby weather stations, and soil moisture and temperature sensors are being installed or already present. This provides a solid foundation for precision management.
 - **Energy:** Several farms have invested in photovoltaic solar power for pumping.
- **Land Pressures:** The proximity of Marrakech exerts significant land pressure, with a trend towards converting agricultural land to residential or tourist areas. Adaptation to recurrent droughts can also lead to the abandonment of agricultural land or the uprooting of orchards, as illustrated by the Yazid farm (26 ha uprooted in 2025).

10.4 Unlocking opportunities for NexusLabs solutions

The Tensift pilot region, while a key area for agricultural production in Morocco, faces significant interconnected challenges. In addition to the structural water shortage exacerbated by climate change, the pressure on groundwater, the decline in soil organic matter, and the increasing cost of inputs threaten the sustainability of farming systems. The WEF Nexus approach is critically important for the region to reconcile agricultural productivity, water resource preservation, and energy efficiency. The widespread adoption of nature-based solutions in the Living Lab is an unavoidable priority for sustainable and resilient agriculture.

Agricultural production is directly threatened by drought and the resulting decrease in groundwater levels. While the main problem in the region is the scarcity and cost of irrigation water, the decline in soil fertility, and the risks of salinization/sodification in some areas are significant issues. The intensification of production leads to a decrease in soil organic matter. Optimizing irrigation through precision management, implementing nature-based solutions to improve soil water retention and fertility (cover crops, reduced tillage, organic amendments), and reducing dependence on synthetic fertilizers will help alleviate problems in the region.

The NexusLabs Project will implement nature-based practices in line with objectives such as improving water use efficiency, increasing soil organic matter, and reducing the carbon footprint of agricultural production. The project builds on previous research initiatives in the region, including projects funded by IDRC and other international partners (IDRC-CRDI, 2025; IRD, 2024), which have focused on integrated water resource management, payment for environmental services, and climate change adaptation.

Soil degradation and environmental pressure on land negatively impact agricultural production. Urbanization and the increasing cost of water are major threats to the plain. Integrated management of the resource, involving all users, will contribute to the development of sustainable agriculture. This project will highlight new approaches and solutions in the Living Lab through the collaboration and synergy of farmers, researchers, and policymakers. Suggestions developed with the active participation of stakeholders will contribute to the development of sustainable agriculture in the Living Lab and similar semi-arid regions.

10.4.1 NbSs and Smart Tools Currently Implemented

The Tensift plain, one of Morocco's most productive agricultural areas for citrus and olives, benefits from a private dynamic of investment in water-saving technologies and some agroecological practices.

- **Drip Irrigation:** All farms in the Living Lab are equipped with drip irrigation systems, representing a fundamental water-saving measure. However, research indicates that the evaluation of irrigation efficiency depends on the analytical framework: if deep percolation is considered as beneficial groundwater recharge, surface irrigation may appear more favorable; if seen as a loss, drip irrigation is more efficient (Moucha et al., 2025). This nuance is critical for water resource management at the basin scale.
- **Organic Amendments:** The application of manure is a common practice on several farms (Graoua

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annually, Agafay every two years, Lahna historically) to maintain soil fertility.

- Recycling of Pruning Residues: The Wazo farm stands out for its practice of shredding and leaving pruning residues on the soil surface, contributing to organic matter recycling.
- Manual Weeding: All farms practice manual weeding, significantly reducing or eliminating the use of herbicides.

These practices form a solid foundation. The project aims to systematize them, evaluate their impact quantitatively, and introduce complementary SFNs within a coherent WEFE framework.

10.4.2 NbS and Tool Implementation in the LL

The challenges encountered in the Tensift region are as follows: chronic and increasing water scarcity, high water and energy costs, decline in soil organic matter, risks of soil degradation (sodification, fertility loss), and difficulty in finding skilled labor.

The Tensift Living Lab will serve as a living laboratory for testing and disseminating nature-based solutions. Within the framework of water management, precision irrigation (using soil sensor data) will be a key activity. Research using stable water isotopes ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$) has shown that subsurface drip irrigation stabilizes the root water uptake zone, maintaining it beyond 30 cm depth and making it less sensitive to evaporation (IAEA, 2021). In contrast, surface irrigation induces more superficial and variable water uptake, with summer isotopic enrichment due to evaporation.

In soil management, cover crops/green manuring, reduced tillage, and optimized fertilization will constitute the main activities. The Living Lab will primarily focus on water scarcity and soil quality issues. Improving soil quality, enhancing soil fertility, and improving microbial activity will significantly contribute to sustainable soil management. Studies have shown that groundwater recharge processes in the area involve not only streamflow losses and subsurface inflow from the mountain front, but also surface water leakage beneath irrigated crops, which contributes significantly to alluvial aquifer recharge (Fadili et al., 2015).

Reducing the use of chemical inputs will have a positive impact on soil health. All these nature-based solutions will be implemented within a holistic approach that supports carbon sequestration and farm resilience.

Increasing soil organic matter through cover crops and reduced tillage methods will significantly contribute to water conservation by improving the soil's water holding capacity. Crop rotation systems (for annual crops like melon) are important practices for sustainable productivity, and incorporating legumes into the system would contribute to improving soil quality. Adapting crop choices and patterns to water availability is already an implicit strategy, but the project aims to provide quantitative data to support these decisions.

Through activities that can involve all stakeholders, the NbS solutions will be disseminated, and the NEXUS approach will be adopted throughout the Living Lab.

10.4.3 Description of experimental demo sites

The applications in the Tensift Living Lab will be carried out on nine private partner farms, each representing a distinct production system and level of intensification. This diversity allows for the testing of NbSs in a range of real-world conditions. The farms are all located in the Al Haouz province, within a radius of about 30 km around Marrakech.

The farms are managed privately with a high level of technical skill. Most have already invested in monitoring equipment (weather stations, soil sensors), providing a valuable database for the project. The experimental sites cover the main crops of the region: citrus (various varieties), olives, melon, and persimmon.

10.5 Data sources and methodology for baseline assessment

The establishment of the baseline situation for the Tensift Living Lab is based on the integration of multi-source, reliable, and verified data, at both the farm and territorial levels. These data form the foundation for deploying the WEFÉ approach and evaluating the SFNs.

Data Sources Used:

- **Field Data (Provided Excel Files):** Detailed information on management, soil, irrigation, fertilization, plant protection, and harvesting for nine representative farms.
- **Climatic Data:** Meteorological stations from the Cadi Ayyad University consortium, accessible for most farms.
- **Interviews and Surveys:** Data from the WEFÉ audits provide economic and energy framework information.
- **Scientific Literature and Technical Reports:** To contextualize local data (regional climate, Tensift basin, agricultural sectors), including research from IDRC-funded projects (IDRC-CRDI, 2025), EGU conference proceedings (Fadili et al., 2015), PhD theses (Attou, 2025), IAEA studies (IAEA, 2021), PLOS Water publications (Moucha et al., 2025), and IRD research projects (IRD, 2024).

The following Table 31, tabulates the data sources for the Tensift.

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Table 31. Data sources and methodology for the Tensift pilot – Example based on the Graoua farm (from WP3 database)

	Data	Comments/Specs	Info
Climate	Hydrometeorological data	incl. historical variability	Daily and annual precipitation, radiation, temperature, wind speed, humidity. Available from on-site meteorological station at Graoua farm. Regional studies confirm average precipitation of 250 mm/year on the plain and 600 mm in the mountains (IDRC-CRDI, 2025).
	Climate change/variability and sinks.	incl. sinks (atmosphere, outflows, percolation to groundwater) etc	Qualitative data from farmer interviews (increased ET, droughts). Graoua farm reports "extreme summer droughts" and "increased evapotranspiration rates." Research confirms an "era of water scarcity" with repeated droughts (Attou, 2025).
Crop	Crop types and features		List of crops produced: Citrus (Nour, Navel, Sidi Aissa, Clementines – 68.13 ha), Melon (double cycle – 42.4 ha), Olive trees (4.56 ha), and various other crops (6.41 ha). Yields: Citrus 35 T/ha, Melon 25 T/ha. Available from Graoua Excel file.
	Crop prices		List of crops produced and their prices (time series). Not available – to be collected.
	Crop types and their practices (primarily irrigation)	LPIS	Cropping system: Monoculture by sector for citrus, double cycle for melon, monoculture for olive. Residue management: Not specified. Available from Graoua Excel file.
	Irrigation water requirements and cost		Citrus & Olive: 9,000 m³/ha/year . Melon: 3,500-4,000 m³/ha/year . Water cost: €0.18/m³ . Available from Graoua Excel file.
Demo	Demographic data at the pilot scale		Population and distribution - age, gender... The basin has more than 3 million inhabitants , with one-third in Marrakech (Attou, 2025). Specific data for Graoua farm workers not available.
	Social characterization of the Living Lab		Reports, official plans. Partially available from research project documentation (IDRC-CRDI, 2025). Graoua farm employs seasonal labor for harvesting (110 persons/ha for citrus at €0.1/ha).
Economy	Territorial economic data		N., type and size of water-demanding economic activities. Agriculture accounts for 80% of total water demand (IDRC-CRDI, 2025). Graoua farm: 252 ha total, 134 ha cultivated.
	Management costs		Agriculture management practices and their unit costs. Partially available from WEFE audits. Graoua: Human labor costs specified for harvest.
	Energy prices		Energy prices (Euro/KWh). Not available – to be collected. Graoua farm uses PV + grid for pumping.
Energy	Energy consumption for agriculture	e.g. for pumping and irrigation	Presence of photovoltaic installation at Graoua farm, but no quantification of energy consumption.
	Current primary energy sources	(oil, biomass, gas, coal, nuclear, renewables etc)	Grid and PV. Available from Graoua Excel file.
	Energy allocation	(e.g. % eolic, % hydroelectric)	Not available.
	Primary energy sources requiring water	(power plants, hydroelectric, etc.)	Not available.
Geo	Cartography study area and pilots (cadaster, water management unit,...)	shapefile georeferenced	Graoua farm coordinates: 31.59004, -7.92075 . Shapefile not available – to be obtained from local authorities (ORMVAH).
	Rivers and lake bodies	Shapefile, river flow records, levels etc	Not available – ABHT data.

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Land Use	Land Use/Cover data and its dynamic changes	RS data Classification + LPIs + CLC	Graoua farm: Current land use includes citrus, melon, olive, and various (rosacea, palm, common bean). Research indicates conversion to tree crops in response to drip irrigation subsidies (Moucha et al., 2025).
	Land use maps definition (period of time, spatial scale, and legend)	Land use map (crops and forest)	Not available.
	Records of natural disasters (floods, fires, erosion, etc)	Copernicus, etc.	Shapefile or raster data. Erosion studies in Ourika watershed show significant soil loss (Fadili et al., 2015).
	Future land use/ land use change scenarios		Scenarios developed in recent research (Moucha et al., 2025).
	Demand for natural resources - water and land (current and future)	Text/Statistics (geospatial data if possible)	Research projects water use could almost double under extreme scenarios (IRD, 2024). Graoua farm currently uses ~9,000 m ³ /ha/year for citrus.
Water	Renewable (surface and groundwater) water sources and stocks		Graoua farm depends exclusively on groundwater via private wells. Groundwater deficit: 100 million m³/year (IAEA, 2021). Water table decline: 1-3 m/year (Fadili et al., 2015).
	Water demand per land use type/class	Shapefile or data records	Citrus & Olive: 9,000 m³/ha/year . Melon: 3,500-4,000 m³/ha/year .
	Water demand and its distribution among uses (for potable use, irrigation/agriculture, industry),	spatially distributed/historical when possible	Agriculture: 80% of total water demand (IDRC-CRDI, 2025). Graoua farm uses water exclusively for irrigation.
	Description of water management (irrigation systems, policy, assignment of volumes..)		Drip irrigation on 100% of cultivated area. Research on irrigation practices and their impacts (Moucha et al., 2025).
	Desalination		Not applicable.
	Treated water		Not applicable.
	Water footprint	if already available	Renewable water resources per capita: 500 m³/year (Attou, 2025).
Soil	Soil types and/or hydrologic groups	Shapefile or raster data	Graoua farm soil: Clay loam (36-38% clay). pH: 8.2 . SOC (0-30cm): 1.32% .
	Soil map types (classification of soils)		Not available – INRA, ORMVAH data.
Management and Policy	Relevant local/regional/national planning documents and/or regulations	Reports/docs	Not available – to be integrated (Green Morocco Plan, Generation Green, water contracts).
	Relevant international regulations	Regulations	Not available.
	List of key stakeholders		Research projects have identified stakeholders including government, civil society, communities, and women's groups (IDRC-CRDI, 2025). For Graoua: farm manager, workers, water users association.
	Main WEF E challenges at the pilot scale	Reports, official plans, previous studies	Available – synthesis of Graoua farm data, farmer interviews, and scientific literature. Main challenges: water scarcity, high water cost, labor shortage.
	New or under consultation action plans/strategies for WEF E management	Text (geospatial data if possible)	Research projects have developed strategic plans for integrated water resource management (IDRC-CRDI, 2025).
	Potential funding sources for NEXUS relevant solutions (green deal, Interreg, etc)	Reports, official plans	Not available.
	Scenarios of interest in the		Climate and land use change scenarios have been

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Nature-Based Solutions	Living Lab		developed in recent research (Moucha et al., 2025).
	Existing NbS solutions implemented in the field (if any)	Reports, official plans	Available from Graoua Excel file: manure application (annual), mulching, grass incorporation.
	Planned NbS solutions to be implemented in the field (if any)	Reports, official plans	Available – based on challenge analysis: precision irrigation, cover crops, reduced tillage, optimized fertilization.
	NbS solutions susceptible of future implementation in the territory	Dossier	Available – see Table 2.
	Knowledge on previous project/initiatives	Objectives achieved/not achieved, limits, bottlenecks, conflicts	Multiple research projects have been conducted in the Tensift basin (IDRC-CRDI, 2025; IRD, 2024).

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11. Baseline description of Júcar River Basin LL (Spain)

The potential for Nexus resource conflicts in the Júcar River Basin (Figure 38 and Figure 39) is intensified by water availability and high irrigation demand, which undermine the effectiveness of national and regional policies, including climate adaptation plans. Working in close collaboration with national, regional and river basin authorities, NexusLabs aims to assess the WEF Nexus and co-design solutions that cut across administrative boundaries and can be effectively integrated into planning frameworks.

Figure 38. Territorial scope of the Jucar River Basin District. Source: chj.es.

The Júcar River Basin, located in the south-eastern Mediterranean coastal area of Spain, has been selected as a Living Lab because it is a hotspot of water scarcity and climate risk. It covers approximately 42,735 km², hosts more than 5 million inhabitants, and is characterised by a Mediterranean climate with average annual precipitation around 500 mm, ranging from about 780 mm in wet years to just over 300 mm in dry years. Land use is dominated by agriculture (≈80% of the area), followed by urban land

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(≈16%) and industry and energy uses (≈4%). Active cooperation among stakeholders from the Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (MAPA), the Ministry for Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge (MITECO), the river basin authority and regional administrations, irrigation communities and individual farmers will improve understanding of the Nexus and support strategic decision making. By working closely with farmers and local actors on the ground, NexusLabs seeks to build a community willing to learn, experiment and advance more sustainable resource management practices.

Figure 39. Júcar River Basin landscapes.

11.1 Geographic and environmental context

11.1.1 Climate

The Júcar River Basin District is located in eastern Spain, with a predominantly Mediterranean climate characterised by hot, dry summers and mild, wetter winters. Average annual precipitation is around 500 mm (Figure 40), with strong spatial and inter-annual variability and recurrent droughts as well as occasional intense rainfall events that generate floods (e.g., DANA floods events near Valencia). Climate change is already aggravating water scarcity, increasing temperatures and altering hydrological regimes, which in turn stresses the WEFEE nexus in the basin.

Figure 40. Average annual precipitation in the basin. Source: chj.es.

11.1.2 Soil

Soils are typically Mediterranean, with a mix of calcareous (Figure 39), often shallow soils in upland areas and deeper alluvial soils in valley bottoms and coastal plains. Large parts of the basin show moderate to high erosion risk driven by steep slopes, sparse vegetation in some areas and intense rainfall events, which affects soil fertility and reservoir siltation. Irrigated agricultural areas on the coastal plains and in La Mancha Oriental are characterised by intensively managed soils where salinisation and organic matter depletion can locally be an issue under water stress and high input use.

AGRUPACIONES LITOLÓGICAS

- Sin información litológica
- A - Arcillas, margas y limos
- B - Esquistos / pizarras
- C - Calizas, dolomías y yesos
- D - Areniscas
- E - Alternancia de calizas, areniscas, arcilla, margas y calizas margosas
- F - Arenas y gravas con contenido en arcillas
- G - Metamórficas / ígneas
- H - Arenas, gravas y conglomerados
- I - Volcánicas
- J - Calizas y dolomías carstificadas

Figure 41. Júcar River Basin has a calcareous predominance. Source: chj.es

11.1.3 Water

The Basin covers more than 42,000 km² and hosts over five million inhabitants, relying on a combination of surface water, groundwater, inter-basin transfers, desalination and treated wastewater to meet demands. Total water demand is about 3,230 hm³/year, with agriculture accounting for roughly 79% of use and urban demands about 17%, making the system highly sensitive to drought and allocation conflicts. Droughts and floods are frequent, the balance between water supply and demand is fragile, and climate projections indicate decreasing surface water availability and growing crop water needs, especially under pessimistic scenarios. Water quality is affected by reduced dilution in low-flow periods, diffuse agricultural pollution and pressures on groundwater bodies, which may worsen under future climate conditions.

For detail information we invite users and readers to go through the river basin plans: [River basin management plan. Cycle 2022-2027](#)

11.1.4 Energy

As shown in Figures 43 and 44, the basin has an important hydropower park, mainly located on the Mijares, Turia and Júcar rivers (Table 32, Figure 44), with about 113 units and a total installed capacity of around 1,417 MW, representing roughly 8% of Spain’s hydroelectric capacity. Over the last decades, energy production in the territory has diversified, with growth of wind and biomass/cogeneration plants and increasing interest in integrating photovoltaic systems to power water transfers, pumping and irrigation infrastructure. The water and energy systems are strongly interlinked, as irrigation and urban supply require significant pumping energy, while hydropower generation depends on water allocation and storage decisions.

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Nota: Hasta 2005 se presentan agregados los datos de energía hidráulica, fotovoltaica y eólica.

Fuente: Series estadísticas del sistema eléctrico español (datos actualizados a junio 2020) y Datos a nivel nacional de los informes anuales de REE (El sistema eléctrico español 2011-2018)

Figure 42. Installed electric power evolution (KW) in the basin

Nota: Hasta 2005 se presentan agregados los datos de energía hidráulica, fotovoltaica y eólica.

Fuente: Series estadísticas del sistema eléctrico español y Datos a nivel nacional de los informes anuales de REE (El sistema eléctrico español 2011-2018)

Figure 43. Energy production evolution in the basin. Source: chj.es

	Hydroelectricals	
System of exploitation	Power production (MKwh)	% Power
Turia	19,604	1.30%
Mijares-Plana de Castellon	70,244	4.67%
Jucar	1,412,907	94.02%
Total	1,502,755	100%

Table 32. Comparison of energy production by exploitation systems, highlighting the relevance of the Júcar hydroelectric system. Source: River Basin Plan, www.chj.es.

Figura 39. Distribución territorial de la actividad hidroeléctrica.

Figure 44. Júcar River Basin hydropower installation capacities. Source: *chj.es*

11.2 Socio-economic characteristics

11.2.1 Demographic profile

The population is about 5.2 million inhabitants (permanent population), with an average density of roughly 119 inhabitants/km² and a significant seasonal population increase linked to tourism on the Mediterranean coast. Population is concentrated in coastal and peri-urban areas of the Valencian region and Alicante, while inland rural areas show lower densities and, in some cases, ageing and depopulation trends (high issue, no generational change). The presence of foreign residents and second homes is relevant, particularly in coastal municipalities, which increases peak water demand in summer.

11.2.2 Gender mainstreaming

Water, agriculture and energy sectors in the basin have traditionally been male-dominated, particularly in irrigation communities, farm management and technical water administrations. Recent participatory processes have explicitly sought to improve gender balance and representation in stakeholder dialogues on WEFE-nexus management, although women still tend to be under-represented in decision-making positions. NexusLabs can build on these ongoing efforts by ensuring gender-sensitive engagement strategies.

11.2.3 Economic activities and territorial specialization

The regional economy is dominated by the service sector (including tourism), followed by industry, while agriculture has a smaller share of GDP but occupies more than half of the territory, with approximately 350,000 ha under irrigation. Key irrigated crops include citrus fruits (especially in coastal areas), followed

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by cereals and other field crops such as maize and sorghum, as well as horticulture and vineyards in specific sub-basins. Industrial activities are significant in the Turia, Júcar and Vinalopó-Alacantí systems, with textiles, manufacturing, leather, tobacco and food industries among the main sectors. Tourism and real-estate development along the coast generate important income and employment but also high seasonal water demand and land-use pressures.

11.3 Land use and infrastructures

Land use in the basin is a mosaic of agricultural land (rainfed and irrigated), forest and shrubland, urban and industrial areas, and coastal wetlands and lagoons. Irrigated agriculture dominates many lowland and coastal plains, while upland areas host forests, shrubland and rangeland that provide key ecosystem services such as water regulation and erosion control. The basin includes major dams and reservoirs, complex irrigation and drainage networks, groundwater well fields, wastewater treatment and reclamation plants, desalination facilities and inter-basin transfer infrastructures, forming a highly regulated and interconnected water system. Transport and energy infrastructures (roads, railways, power lines, hydropower schemes, wind farms) intersect with water and land-use planning, creating both constraints and opportunities for integrated NbS deployment.

11.4 Unlocking opportunities for NexusLabs solutions

The basin faces combined challenges of water scarcity, drought and flood risk, soil degradation, biodiversity loss, water-quality deterioration and growing competition between agricultural, urban, industrial and environmental uses. At the same time, there is increasing interest in WEFE-nexus approaches, efficient irrigation, reclaimed water use, and NbS such as wetlands, sustainable farming practices and green infrastructure to enhance resilience.

11.2.1 NbSs and Smart Tools Currently Implemented

Existing and emerging NbSs in the basin include:

- Sustainable agricultural practices (e.g. cover crops, crop rotation, reduced or no-till, organic farming) to reduce erosion, improve soil health and enhance water retention.
- River and riparian restoration measures, including re-naturalisation of river stretches, riparian buffer strips and floodplain reconnection in selected areas.
- Groundwater recharge and habitat improvement, raising social awareness on NbS on nitrate polluted areas.

These NbSs are implemented at different scales, from farm and field level (conservation agriculture, on-farm wetlands) to landscape and river-reach level (floodplain and wetland restoration).

11.2.2 NbSs and Tool Implementation in the LL

In NexusLabs, the Júcar Living Lab will focus on NbS and tools that address water quantity, water quality, soil health and energy-water links at farm, pilot and landscape scale:

- On-farm NbS: optimisation of deficit irrigation strategies, soil-moisture-based irrigation scheduling, cover crops and reduced tillage to improve soil water retention and reduce erosion.
- Landscape / aquatic NbS: riparian buffers and recharge areas to enhance water quality and support ecological flows.

Nexus-oriented tools: WEFE-nexus modelling (PSDM simulations) to assess climate-change impacts, socioeconomics and co-benefits of NbS on water, energy, food and ecosystems. Decision-support and governance tools: participatory scenario building, and improved water accounting and monitoring.

11.2.3 Description of experimental demo sites

The “Spanish Júcar farm” is located in the Júcar Living Lab (approx. 39.38 N, -2.11 E), on alluvial terraces and piedmonts typical of the upper–middle Júcar basin. The farm has about 576 ha of cultivated land with a Mediterranean agricultural mosaic dominated by vineyards (rainfed and irrigated), rainfed almond and annual irrigated crops such as alfalfa, maize, rapeseed and wheat, plus rainfed cereals and legumes (barley, faba beans, camelina). Vineyards are the main crop (≈135.6 ha), followed by irrigated alfalfa (≈76.6 ha) and a mixed area of irrigated and rainfed wheat (~80 ha, about 45 ha irrigated and 35 ha rainfed on average). Soils are predominantly medium-texture (from sandy-loam to loam-clay loam) with calcareous, slightly alkaline conditions (pH 7.8–8.3), bulk density around 1.3–1.5 g/cm³ and relatively low organic matter (roughly 1–1.5% in vineyards, equivalent to 10–25 t C/ha in the top 0–30 cm). Main soil challenges include low organic matter, surface crusting, localized compaction in wheel tracks, erosion risk on gentle slopes where there is no cover and local salinity in areas with older irrigation systems.

Vineyards are managed as a permanent woody crop, with reduced tillage (2–3 passes/year between rows), no tillage on the vine line except occasional decompaction, and spontaneous grass-legume cover between rows that is mown or mulched in spring. Pruning residues are shredded and incorporated into the soil, so they represent a recurrent carbon input (roughly 0.2–0.4 t C/ha·year), and occasional compost or manure is applied (5–10 t fresh matter/ha every few years, equivalent to about 0.3–0.6 t C/ha). In alfalfa and wheat, tillage is conventional or reduced before establishment, with no tillage during the alfalfa stand and conventional/reduced tillage (chisel + cultivator, sometimes minimum tillage or direct drilling) for wheat rotations.

Irrigation is localised drip in vineyards and mainly sprinkler or surface/modernized systems for alfalfa and irrigated wheat. Deficit irrigation is applied in vineyards (typical gross depth about 1,800 m³/ha, with a range of 1,500–2,000 m³/ha·year), while alfalfa uses roughly 7,000–10,000 m³/ha·year and irrigated wheat 3,000–4,500 m³/ha·year, depending on rainfall. Typical water costs in irrigation communities (0.03–0.06 €/m³) translate into vineyard water costs of about 50–120 €/ha, with 3–5 hours/ha·year of

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labour and 1–2 hours/ha·year of machinery for irrigation operations. Key water-management issues are periodic allocation restrictions in dry years, rising water and energy costs and salinisation risk where drainage is limited.

Mineral fertilisation in vineyards relies on NPK compound fertiliser (e.g. 8-15-15) as basal dressing plus ammonium or calcium nitrate in top dressings or via fertigation, with typical annual nutrient inputs of roughly 60–80 kg N/ha, 30–50 kg P₂O₅/ha and 60–90 kg K₂O/ha; occasional compost/manure adds 0.3–0.6 t C/ha when applied. Alfalfa receives 200–300 kg N/ha·year (split after cuts) plus P and K according to offtake, whereas wheat typically receives 120–180 kg N/ha·year (less in rainfed parcels) with P and K at sowing, and in some cases sulphur with N. Challenges include adjusting N doses to maintain yield and quality (e.g. must quality in vineyards) without depleting soil fertility, dealing with spatial variability of nutrients and increasing organic matter inputs in a cost-effective way.

Plant protection includes integrated fungicide and insecticide programmes in vineyards (about 6–10 treatments/year is typical in intensive viticulture), herbicides for intra-row weed control, and targeted fungicides and insecticides in alfalfa and wheat when required. Herbaceous crops use herbicides for broadleaf and grass weeds and fungicides for rusts/septoria in wet years, with insecticides applied occasionally; some fields follow integrated pest management principles.

Agroecological and NbS-type practices already applied include spontaneous vegetative covers, incorporation of pruning residues, reduced tillage and controlled deficit irrigation in irrigated vineyards, combined with basic soil-moisture and phenological monitoring. Management issues noted by the farmer/stakeholders are weed pressure on the vine line, localised compaction, labour cost for pruning and cover management, and the need to balance water and nutrient inputs with climate and market variability.

Remote sensing is already used as additional management support, offering a basis for NexusLabs tools at the farm scale.

11.5 Data sources and methodology for baseline assessment

At farm level, detailed biophysical and management data from the experimental NexusLabs farm are used to parameterise and validate NbS options (cover crops, reduced tillage, deficit irrigation, organic inputs) in vineyards, irrigated alfalfa and wheat. The WP3 “Farm” sheet provides time-invariant structural characteristics (land use, soils, rotation, irrigation systems) and typical management calendars (tillage, irrigation, fertilisation, plant protection, labour and machinery use) to support model input preparation and field indicators.

At pilot/territorial level, we will work on soil health, WEF governance and mainstreaming NbSs.

The baseline for the Júcar pilot will combine (Table 33):

- River basin management and hydrological planning documents (Confederación Hidrográfica del Júcar, RBMPs, drought plans, socio-economic characterisation, water demands, infrastructure

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inventories), WEFE-nexus and climate-impact studies using hydro-economic and eco-hydrological models to simulate water allocation, demands and system performance under climate scenarios.

- Climate and hydrological datasets (historical and projections), remote sensing products and in-situ monitoring for flows, groundwater levels and water quality (as reported in Júcar case studies and climate-adaptation assessments).
- Socio-economic and stakeholder information from basin-level assessments of water users, economic activities, tourism and demographic trends, as well as WEFE-nexus stakeholder engagement exercises in the JRBD.

Table 33. Data sources and methodology for the Júcar pilot (indicative)

Data source / method	Pilot & territorial level	Field / farm level
RBMPs, CHJ reports, drought and climate plans	Water availability, demands by sector, infrastructure, policy context	Allocation rules, service levels, drought indicators
Hydro-economic & eco-hydrological models (NexusLabs models or FAO-56) HidroMORE software	Basin-scale WEFE analysis, climate scenario impacts on resources and demands	Crop water requirements, farm-scale irrigation performance
Monitoring networks & remote sensing	River flows, groundwater status, water-quality status, land-use/land-cover	Field evapotranspiration, crop development, soil moisture proxies
Statistical and socio-economic data (INE, regional authorities, CHJ, tourism statistics)	Population, economic structure, tourism, employment, gender indicators	Farm household characteristics where available
Stakeholder engagement and LL activities	Nexus governance, cooperation barriers, NbS acceptance and co-design	Farmer practices, perceptions and constraints
Data source	Pilot and territorial level	Field level
Existing NbSs implemented	Mapping of wetlands, river restoration, conservation-agriculture areas (CHJ, regional env./agri agencies, previous projects) AgriSat monitoring farms at different scales.	Farm records, project documentation and field surveys on soil and water practices
Planned NbSs to be implemented	NexusLabs design documents, RBMP measures, regional rural-development and climate-adaptation plans	Co-designed farm-level NbS packages (cover crops, on-farm wetlands, scheduling tools)
Existing knowledge	Scientific literature and WEFE-nexus case studies for Júcar, technical reports, previous EU projects on efficient irrigation and NbS.	Local experimental trials, demonstration sites and advisory service data

12. Conclusions

The NexusLabs deliverable 3.1 “Implementation Framework & Baseline Description” establishes a comprehensive and structured knowledge base for nine Living Labs (LLs) across the Mediterranean, laying the groundwork for integrated NexusLabs solutions co-design, implementation and evaluation within the WEFE Nexus framework.

Across all LLs, the baseline assessment reveals a set of shared, deeply interconnected challenges. Water scarcity emerges as the most pervasive and urgent issue, exacerbated by climate change, unsustainable groundwater extraction, and growing agricultural and urban demand. Soil degradation, declining organic matter, salinization risks, and biodiversity loss further compound these pressures, threatening the long-term productivity and resilience of farming systems. Energy costs tied to irrigation pumping represent an additional burden, particularly in areas dependent on deep groundwater.

Despite these shared vulnerabilities, a rich diversity of geographical, climatic, institutional, and socio-economic conditions can be found. From the alluvial plains of Tarquinia and the Pinios River Basin, to the semi-arid Tensift plain of Morocco and the drought-prone Júcar River Basin in Spain, each territory embodies distinct Nexus dynamics and governance contexts. This diversity is not a limitation but a strategic asset: it allows NexusLabs to develop and test context-specific solutions across a broad spectrum of Mediterranean conditions, which can subsequently be adapted and scaled across comparable regions beyond the project's boundaries.

Several NbS practices and resources saving tools are already in place across the LLs — including drip irrigation, cover crops, reduced tillage, riparian buffer strips, and organic amendments — forming a solid foundation upon which the project can build. The knowledge base developed in this D3.1 serves multiple interconnected purposes: it underpins the systematisation of existing NbS practices and other resource saving tools, enables the quantification of their impacts, and provides the foundation for co-developing context-specific innovations. It also supplies the data needed to design and carry out participatory processes that are both inclusive and gender-responsive.

Ultimately, the baseline documented in this deliverable will serve as the foundational reference for NexusLabs Deliverable 3.3, which will develop the roadmap for combined resource efficiency tools implementation across the project's LLs, providing practical guidelines for action across Mediterranean sites.

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